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THE NORCIA HISTORICAL PAPERS

A SERIES OF MONOGRAPHIC ARTICLES

THE 'NORCINI' IN ROME: SIX CENTURIES OF A MASTERLY PRESENCE

PIGS, BUTCHERS AND SALTED PORK MEAT¹

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PIGS, BUTCHERS AND SALTED PORK MEAT

by Michele Sanvico

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1. Introduction: the 'Norcini' in Rome, a story of (tasty) excellence

In our previous monographic article belonging to the series *The Norcia Historical Papers* we presented the story of the Precian surgeons, the proficient operators from Preci, a small hamlet lying near the town of Norcia, central Italy, who won for themselves the greatest renown and appreciation across the entire Europe, between the sixteenth and eighteenth centuries. In particular, it was in the very area subject to the rule of Norcia that, starting as early as the thirteenth century, something peculiarly unexpected occurred: the birth of an eminent, successful tradition concerning a number of specific medical treatments. It was the tale of the astounding, surprising story of the Precian Surgical School, which originated from a small Apennine castle and whose surgeons were known everywhere with the traditional name of 'Norcini'.

In the present essay, the second in the mentioned series, we want to tell another amazing story, which also relates to the 'Norcini'. However, this time, though marked by the same identifying name and originating from Norcia as well, they did not reach the farthest nations of Europe: they limited their historical presence to Rome. And they were no surgeons.

Instead, they were butchers. Butchers of pigs.

Contemporary studies have not yet addressed the remarkable story of the presence of the people of Norcia in medieval and early-modern Rome; however, the history of the local presence of the people from Norcia in the capital city of the Papal States is so strongly characterized that it deserves a special attention, under the significant consideration that the 'Norcini' are still present and visible in today's Rome, retaining in our contemporary age their fame as suppliers of the most palatable sausages, hams, salami and other salted pork meat products.

Starting from the fifteenth century, when Rome was living a period of growth and development, we will try to follow the traces of the early phase of the migration to Rome of the people from Norcia, in search of work opportunities and a way to earn a living, especially during the winter season, when a heavy blanket of frozen snow used to cover their native territory. We will illustrate the crafty tradition that, throughout the Roman times and the Middle Ages, marked the small town set at the foot of the

Sibillini Mountain Range, where pigs were raised amid extended forests of oak trees and fed on savory acorns, and their first-quality meat was then processed by salting, flavouring and seasoning, under the benevolent action of the fresh winds which blew from the peaks and ravines lying high up, in the close, elevated highlands.

Norcia and the pigs. A relationship we have also explored in our previous essay on the Precian Surgical School, with a particular role of the tradition concerning the slaughtering of pigs — a feast and a celebration for the rustic families of peasants, carrying with it a fundamental burden of allegorical meanings, with an intertwined narrative which tells an appalling, inspiring tale of life and death — in the appearance of a special, successful surgical know-how in the area of Norcia.

So we are going to address the story of pork meat in Rome, in connection with the main activity carried out by the 'Norcini' from Norcia in the city of the Popes. This is a story of butchers and cured meat and flavored sausages. Actually, it is a tasty story. It starts from ancient Latin authors and ends up, from the fifteenth century onwards, with our celebrated 'Norcini': the kings of cured pork meat and delectable salted food in the capital city of the Papal States, for centuries and centuries, and until very recent times.

We will see the 'Norcini' enter the specific, peculiar business framework of late-medieval Rome, with its regulated markets, rules on exclusivity and jealous, conflicting guilds and brotherhoods, in a setting where food had to be imported from the various papal provinces so as to prevent turmoil amid the populace and ensure social stability. Initially, a low-profile presence for our people from Norcia, who will gradually reach a most significant position in the capital's food market, in a space already occupied by the powerful local associations of Butchers and Grocers: a presence that will be 'celebrated' in a number of humorous plays staged in the theaters of Rome, with the 'Norcini' being represented as rough, rustic people talking an odd, funny language (the dialect of Norcia, still in use today), to the amusement of the Roman popular audiences.

But the 'Norcini' will soon emerge as the suppliers of the most tasty, palatable, juicy sausages in Rome, not to mention the many other sorts of food products based on salted pork meat: they all will enjoy a widespread

appreciation in town, by both the poorest layers of the population and the most aristocratic houses of princes and members of the Church.

Fig. 1 - A glorious exhibit of cascading sausages: the palatable tradition of the 'Norcini' in Rome

And, in a Rome inhabited by people coming from all over Europe and swarmed by pilgrims, travellers and diplomatic missions, their presence in town, in their multiple roles as skilled butchers, proficient surgeons and rustic workers, will be celebrated, in the seventeenth century, by the establishment of a powerful 'national' brotherhood dedicated to their beloved saints, Benedict and Scholastica, approved by Pope Paul V himself and owner of a small, charming church located not far from the Pantheon; and a guild, also including the people from Cascia, outlining their specific position within the regulated trade system in place at the time in the city of the Popes.

So let's begin our new journey across this new essay belonging to *The Norcia Historical Papers*. This new itinerary will bring us in the kitchen of Apicius, amid the taverns in the streets of Pompeii, and to the luscious banquet offered by Trimalchio to his distinguished guests in his Roman

villa; and then, even beyond through the Middle Ages — with a first, almost unexpected diversion towards Florence and its thriving medieval economy — and the streets of Rome in the Early Modern Period; subsequently, we will meet the 'Norcini' in Rome, their presence manifest and recognised across the seventeenth, eighteenth and nineteenth century; finally, we will get to our present days, when many 'norcinerie', the food shops still run by families originating from Norcia and living in contemporary Rome, will illuminate the congested streets of the city, by offering to today's Romans the same palatable craft and tasty quality that has been provided, for many centuries, to the former capital of the Papal States.

We are about to begin a journey through skill, craft and excellence. And this will be a journey for real gourmets.

2. A history of sausages: the Romans and the Lombards

2.1. Raising (savory) pigs in Roman times

Most probably the beginning of our story dates back to the Romans, who used to raise and breed pigs as livestock, eating pork meat especially at banquets and dinners arranged by the upper classes of well-to-do Rome.

Fig. 2 - The initial page of Apicius' *De re coquinaria*, with some of the pork recipes contained in Book VIII, from manuscript Urb. Lat. 1146 preserved at the Vatican Apostolic Library (ninth century), folia 4v, 44r, 48r, 50r

Many recipes, to be served as savory courses in social occasions, are listed in the famous book *De re coquinaria*, attributed to Caelius Apicius: porcellus farsilem duobus generibus (pork with two different stuffings), porcellus elixum farsilem (stuffed boiled pork), porcellus flaccianus

(Flaccus' pork), porcellus oenococius (pork cooked in wine), porcellus assus (roasted pork) are only a few of the many preparations included in Book VIII of this ancient cookbook, for the enjoyment of the aristocratic gourmets.

Actually large numbers of pigs were raised at farms in the countryside. Marcus Terentius Varro, a writer who lived in the first century B.C., stresses this very point by asking the reader the following rhetorical question in his *De re rustica*:

«Who is the owner of a farm, who does not have pigs?»

[In the original Latin text: «Quis enim fundum colit nostrum, quin sues habeat?»].

pecuariis: ea res nec non est cōmūis. Quis. n. fūndum colit nostrum: quin sues habeat? Et qui non audierit patres nostros dicere: ignauum & fum'

Fig. 3 - Pig breeding in ancient Rome according to Marcus Terentius Varro, from *De re rustica* (printed edition dating to 1482, Reggio Emilia), folium 66 (Book II, Chapter IV)

And the most appropriate place to breed swines and hogs was near a forest, as Lucius Junius Moderatus Columella states in the chapter dedicated to pigs (*De suibus*) of his first-century *De re rustica*, a book on farming and agriculture:

«Woods are utterly convenient [for pig breeding], especially those accommodating oaks, corks, beech trees, holm oaks, oleanders, tamarisks, hazelnut trees, fruit trees; and wooded areas with hawthorn, carob tree, juniper, lotus, pine tree, dogwood, strawberry tree, blackthorn, garland thorn and pear tree».

[In the original Latin text: «Nemora sunt convenientissima, quae vestiuntur quercu, subere, fago, cerris, ilicibus, oleastris, tamaricibus, corylis, pomiferisque; sylvestribus, ut sunt albae spinae, Graecae siliquae, iuniperus, lotos, pinus, cornus, arbutus, prunus, et paliurus, atque achrades pyri»].

Fig. 4 - The excerpt on pig breeding and feeding as found in a printed edition of Lucius Junius Moderatus Columella's *De re rustica* (London, 1548), Book VII, Chapter IX, p. 266 and 267

Certainly it must be noted that pigs can surely be raised everywhere, as they are adaptable, versatile animals which feed on almost any type of edible stuff. But one thing must be also pinpointed: when a pig feeds on the produce of a virgin, wealthy wood — especially on acorns, hazelnuts, truffles, roots, etc. — its meat will take on a delicious, fragrant taste, that will transform it in a sort of Elysian food, so toothsome that it will deserve the most sophisticated dining table as its final destination.

It is Varro, a century before the Christian era, who notes that «those animals feed particularly on acorns, then fava beans, barley, and any other sort of wheat; through this food not only they grow fatter, but their meat also acquires a more enjoyable taste» (in the original Latin text: «hoc pecus alitur maxime glande, deinde faba, et ordeo, et caetero frumento; quae res non modo pinguitudinem efficiunt, sed etiam carnis iucundum saporem»).

fere nequeant. Hoc autem pecus alitur maxime glande : deinde faba & hordeo & caetero frumento. Quae res non modo pinguitudinem faciunt: sed etiam carnis iucundum saporem. Pastum exigunt mane in aestate & anteq̄

Fig. 5 - Pig breeding in ancient Rome according to Marcus Terentius Varro, from *De re rustica* (printed edition dating to 1482, Reggio Emilia), folium 67 (Book II, Chapter IV)

And where could Romans find a perfect place for pig raising, as described by Columella, not far from their capital city and provided with gorgeous, intact woods and the healing, invigorating air of a mountainous setting?

That was in Norcia. Or, as they called it, ancient Nursia.

But we will be talking later about this. Now let's discuss another fundamental aspect relating to pork meat: we must present a brief history of cured pork meat, i.e. a most palatable preparation of that same food. So good that this sort of recipe has crossed the centuries so as to get to our contemporary world. And with the greatest success.

2.2 Salted pork: the origin of an ancient craft

Today sausages, ham and salami are just most palatable food we like to enjoy in our everyday life, with no additional concern about issues such as food availability and conservation.

But in Roman times cured pork meat represented the solution to primary food-related problems.

Of course, during the age of Rome's rule there were no such appliances as refrigerators, so food conservation represented a fundamental issue. As to pork meat, the better solution to ensure preservation was salting and seasoning. And the very first description of the recipe to obtain cured hams is provided by Cato the Elder, or the Censor (Marcus Porcius Cato). It is contained in the very last chapter of his *De agri cultura*, dating back to the second century B.C.:

«Method of curing hams and Puteolan meat. You should salt hams in the following manner, in a jar or large pot: When you have bought the hams cut off the hocks. Allow a half-modius of ground Roman salt to each ham. Spread salt on the bottom of the jar or pot; then lay a ham, with the skin facing downwards, and cover the whole with salt. [...] Spread salt above so that the meat shall not show, and level the whole. When they have remained five days in the salt remove them all with their own salt. [...]. Twelve days later take them out finally, brush off all the salt, and hang

them for two days in a draught. On the third day clean them thoroughly with a sponge and rub with oil. Hang them in smoke for two days, and the third day take them down, rub with a mixture of oil and vinegar, and hang in the meat-house. No moths or worms will touch them».

[In the original Latin text: «Salsura pernarum et offelae puteolanae. Pernas sic sallire oportet: in dolio aut seria. Cum pernas emeris: ungulas earum praecidito. Salis romaniensis moliti in singulas semodios. In fundo dolii aut serae salem sternito. Deinde pernam ponito. Cutis deorsum spectet. Sale obruito totam. [...] Sale insuper obrue, ne caro appareat. Aequalem facito. Ubi iam dies v. in sale fuerint, eximito omnes cum suo sale. [...] Post dies omnino duodecimum pernas eximito, et salem omnem detergito. Et suspendito in vento biduum. Die tertio extergito spongia bene. Perungito oleo. Suspendito in fumo biduum. Tertio die demito. Perungito oleo et aceto et commixto. Et suspendito in carnario. Nec tineae, nec vermes tangent»].

Fig. 6 - Preparation of salted ham as found in Marcus Porcius Cato's *De agri cultura* (printed edition dating to 1482, Reggio Emilia), folia 2 and 41 (Chapter CLXI)

As Cato says, by applying the curing process no moth or worms will spoil the meat: that was a perfect way to preserve the quality of pork food across time and ensure ready availability of food for instant consumption when needed. As a delectable side effect, it also represented a tasty recipe to make the most toothsome hams and sausages.

So the majority of farmers used to cure their own pork meat, as reported by Varro in his *De re rustica*, who in the first century B.C. asks himself another rhetorical question:

«Who has never heard our fathers say that it is a lazy man and a squanderer the guy who hangs in his meat-house a quarter of a pork taken from a butcher's shop rather than from his own estate?»

[In the original Latin text: «Qui non audierit patres nostros dicere ignavum et sumptuosum esse qui succidiam in carnario suspenderit potius e lanario quam e domestico fundo?»].

¶ fues habeat : Et qui non audierit patres nostros dicere : ignavum & sumptuosum esse qui succidiam in carnario suspenderit potius e lanario quam e domestico fundo , Ergo qui suum gregem uult habere idoneum : eligere

Fig. 7 - Pig breeding in ancient Rome according to Marcus Terentius Varro, from *De re rustica* (printed edition dating to 1482, Reggio Emilia), folium 66 (Book II, Chapter IV)

Nearly all farms had pigs, says Varro; and nearly all of them cured their meat, for their own use or for subsequent sale. We can easily imagine that this was also true when it came to the farms at Nursia (Norcia), where salted pork resulted even more palatable than elsewhere, owing to the nutrition of pigs based on the flavory products of the neighboring forests, and the exposition of the cured meat to the fresh air of the mountains during the maturation process.

Varro dedicates to domesticated pigs a full chapter (Book II, Chapter IV, «De sus»), in which he provides a number of interesting details on cured meat. For instance, large supplies of salted meat of pork were also imported from today's France:

«Gauls use to work large quantities of quality cured pork meat. A token of its quality is given by the fact that every year from Gaul to Rome are brought hams, strips of pork and pork shoulders. On the large supplies of cured meat from Gaul Cato wrote that 'in Italy three of four thousands pieces of this pork are found'».

[In the original Latin text: «E quis succidias Galli optimas et maximas facere consueverunt. Optimarum signum, quod etiam nunc quot annis e Gallia apportantur Romam pernae tomacinae, et taniacae, et petationes. De magnitudine Galliarum succidiarum Cato scribit his verbis. In Italia in scrobes terna atque quaterna milia aulia succidia»].

Fig. 8 - Cured pork meat from Marcus Terentius Varro's *De re rustica* (printed edition dating to 1482, Reggio Emilia), folium 67 (Book II, Chapter IV)

Today, in Norcia and at many other locations scattered across the Italian peninsula, the process for obtaining cured pork meat is well known and based on fully-established traditional procedures, locally elaborated often across hundreds of years. First-century Romans had their own procedures, too, as accurately described by Columella in his *De re rustica* (Book XII, Chapter LIII):

«On the salting of pork meat - [...] Before killing any animal, and mainly the pork, it is advisable to prevent him from drinking, so its flesh will be drier. [...] Then remove the bones, so as to get a cured meat with no defects and more durable. After that, with cooked salt, not excessively minced and better ground under the suspended grindstone, put salt meticulously [...]; then put the shoulders or slices over a wooden table and lay over them great weights so as to drain the blood. On the third day take the weights off and rub them all with salt by using your hands [...] and don't forget to rub them everyday until the cured meat is fully mature. [...] This process is to be carried out comfortably with the waning of the moon, especially at the winter solstice, but also before the Ides of February».

[In the original Latin text: «De salsura suillae carnis - [...] Omne pecus, et precipue suem pridie quam occidatur, potione prohiberi oportet, quo fit caro siccior. [...] Cum exossato. Nam ea res minus vitiosam, et magis durable salsuram facit. Deinde cum exossaveris, cocto sale, nec nimium minuto, sed suspensa mola infracto, diligenter salito [...]; supra tabulatum

tergoribus, aut frustis vasta pondera imposito, ut exanietur. Tertio die pondera removeto, et manibus diligenter salsuram fricato [...] nec desieris eius quotidie salsuram fricare, donec matura fit. [...] Haec salsura luna decrescente maxime per brumam, sed etiam mense Februario ante Idus commode fiet»].

Fig. 9 - How to salt pork meat, from Lucius Junius Moderatus Columella's *De re rustica* (London, 1548), Book XII, chapter LIII, p. 460

So what can we conclude from this articulated journey across food habits in use among the Romans as to pigs and their meat?

We can certainly say that in Roman times cured pork meat was commonly produced in farms and consumed in towns and villages. Certainly fresh cuts were also sold by butchers ('lanii') at markets and shops ('laniaria'), especially to their wealthier clients; however, hams obtained from salted and smoked pork shoulders were also common: that was a food which could easily be preserved across time, and possibly even available at lower prices, for consumption by normal, lower-class people.

Fig. 10 - The preparation of fresh meat cuts in a 'carnarium', with a butcher and his wife, while other fresh cuts and cured pork meat (ham) hang from a rod (marble panel possibly coming from a Roman tomb in Italy, second century A.D., preserved at the Staatliche Kunstmuseen Dresden)

But pork shoulders and hams do not make up the full list of tasty food available on the Roman markets through the curing process. Other types of delicious pork sausages were prepared and sold, and we are now going to see and appreciate some of them.

2.3 Perna, lucanicae and other tasty friends

Here is a short list of cured pork meat products as provided by Varro in his work on etymologies, *De lingua latina* (Book IV):

«The Latin word 'succidia' comes from pork slaughtering; it was the first animal that the owners began to kill and then salt, so as to preserve it. 'Tegus' is their skin. 'Perna' comes from the thigh. 'Offula' is said the minced meat, which in the sacred chant of Salii is the bowels, today named the 'Issitia', or the cut. 'Murtarum' comes from myrtle, whose berries are largely used to stuff the large intestine...».

[In the original Latin text: «'Succidia' ab suibus caedendis; nam id pecus primum occidere coeperunt domini et, ut servarent, salire. 'Tegus suis' ab eo quod eo tegitur. Perna a pede suis. 'Offula', ab offa minima suilla, ab eo quod insecta caro, ut in carmine Saliorum est, quod in extis dicitur nunc

Issitia, prosectum. 'Murtatum' a murta, quod ea large fartum intestinum crassum...»].

Fig. 11 - Examples of sausages made of cured pork meat from Marcus Terentius Varro's *De lingua latina* (printed edition dating to 1529, Paris), folium 19

Varro also mentions additional types of sausages, which we will omit here; however, amid all those luscious products we like to mention the delicious 'lucanica', a term which is still used in today's Italian language:

«They call another sausage 'Lucanica': its name comes from the soldiers of Lucania [the region of Basilicata in southern Italy - editor's note], the same way as they call 'Faliscum salami' a sausage coming from Falerii [an ancient Italian and Etruscan town - editor's note]».

[In the original Latin text: «'Lucanicam' dicunt, quod milites a Lucanis didicerunt, ut quod Faleriis faliscum ventrem»].

Fig. 12 - The lucanica from Marcus Terentius Varro's *De lingua latina* (printed edition dating to 1529, Paris), folium 19

The 'lucanica', possibly circulated by the legionaries coming from today's Basilicata or Lucania, in southern Italy, was so appreciated by all classes of the Roman society that we find a copious number of quotes, all mentioning its toothsome-ness.

A recipe for the lucanica is detailed by Apicius in Book II, Chapter IV of his *De re coquinaria*:

«Lucanica - Grind some pepper, cumin, savories [...] and mix with well-minced meat [...] stuff with it a piece of intestine, as thin as possible; then hang it by also exposing it to smoke».

[In the original Latin text: «'Lucanicae' - [...] Teritur piper, cuminum, satureja [...] et admiscetur pulpa bene tinsa [...] farcies intestinum perquam tenuatim productum; et sic ad fumum suspenditur»].

Fig. 13 - The lucanica sausage from Book II of Apicius' *De re coquinaria* (manuscript Urb. Lat. 1146 preserved at the Vatican Apostolic Library - ninth century), folium 10v

But what was the appealing strength of the *lucanica*?

It is no different from the contemporary might of cured meat like, for instance, the salami: it is easily transportable; it doesn't get spoilt with time; it can be drawn from a backpack or bought at a street shop and immediately consumed; it is a reliable reserve of food you can use when and where you wish, as required. And — last but not least — it is absolutely delicious.

Marcus Tullius Cicero was utterly fond of *lucanica* sausages. In writing to Lucius Papirius Paetus in 46 B.C. (*Epistula ad fam.* 9.16), he nicely pulls his friend's leg, by saying that he has no hope to be offered good dinners at Paetus' villa in Naples, especially when it comes to appetizers: «for in old times I found my appetite spoilt by your olives and Lucanian sausages» (in the original Latin text: «neque est quod in promulside spei ponas aliquid [...]: solebam enim antea debilitari oleis et lucanicis tuis»). But, of course, all he was saying «was just a joke» («*superiora illa lusimus*» in Latin) and he just looks forward to arriving in Naples at his friend's house and eating again those luscious *lucanicae*.

Fig. 14 - The *lucanica* sausage as mentioned in a letter (*ad fam.* 9.16) written by Marcus Tullius Cicero, from *Selected letters of Cicero* edited by Frank Frost Abbott, Boston, 1897), p. 192

So the *lucanica* becomes a sort of prince of the sausages, a king of cured pork meat. And the great Latin poet Marcus Valerius Martialis, in his humorous, ironical epigrams dating to the first century A.D., is glad to make a short presentation of the real '*lucanica*' sausage, as if it were a charming actress stepping on a stage (Book XIII, 35):

«Daughter of a Picene sow, here I come, a *Lucanica* sausage,
to me is given a most welcome crown of white polenta».

[In the original Latin text: «*Filia Picena venio Lucanica porca; Pultibus hinc niveis grata corona datur*»].

Fig. 15 - The *lucanica* from Martial's *Epigrams* (printed edition dating to 1644, Amsterdam), p. 423

Here we even find two interesting pieces of information: first, the toothsome sausage is to be enjoyed with an accompaniment of polenta, the cornmeal still in use today with this sort of pork meat; second, according to Martial the best *lucanica* seems to come from the Picene area, the territory which borders the land of Norcia across the Sibillini Mountain Range.

And the *lucanica* is also well accepted even as a delectable gift or present. Martial tells us (Book IV, 46) of a certain lawyer called Sabellus, who thinks he is the «happiest of the attorneys» («*inter causidicos beatiorem*» in Latin) because during the festivities of Saturnalia he received from his clients a number of delicious quality food as most appreciated gifts, including «*lucanica* sausages as well as Faliscan» («... *et Lucanica ventre cum Falisco*» in Latin).

Fig. 16 - The *lucanica*, once more, from Martial's *Epigrams* (printed edition dating to 1644, Amsterdam), pages 129 and 130

Were those sausage a food for the rich only? Not at all. As we said, they were take-away, ready-to-eat food for people's consumption at street corners. And we find tasteful traces of them even on the public walls of the ancient Roman town of Herculaneum, buried beneath the ashes and lapilli of a volcano, Mount Vesuvius.

Excavations have brought to light an ancient drawing, one of the many graffiti left by the populace on the walls of the buildings just before the town's tragical end, in the year 79 A.D. The inscription (CIL IV, 10674,

also referenced as EDR154177) is located at the Suburban Thermae and it appears to be a sort of shopping list:

«nuts, drinks: 14 [possibly asses, small Roman coins, editor's note]
pork rinds: 3
three breads: 51
three cutlets: 12
four thyme-flavored sausages: 8»

[In the original Latin text:
«Nuc biber XIII
Singa III
Panem III LI
Orrellas III XII
Thymatla III VIII»].

So people in the streets of Herculaneum used to buy food supplies or even street food: this included bread, something to drink and tasty, spicy sausages.

Street food. Food on sale at the many inns and taverns — 'cauponae' in Latin — that were scattered across the public roads of Roman towns. And sausages were a most appreciated fare.

Let's pay a visit to another celebrated Roman town, Pompeii. After entering the archaeological site through the main gate, proceed along Via Marina up to the Forum, then turn left towards Via di Mercurio and the Regio VI: just opposite to the gorgeous house of the Tragic Poet you will find insula no. 10, a large apartment block including various houses and two 'cauponae'. One of them (no. 1), lying on the north-westernmost corner of the 'insula', contains a number of small wall frescos, which depict typical tavern scenes.

On the southern wall of the rear room, the second fresco from the right shows a two-thousand-year-old scene we will have the chance to see in real life for centuries and centuries to come: merry people sitting at a small bar's table, enjoying their food and drinks, surmounted by a rod from which a number of appealing hams and sausages are happily hanging.

Unfortunately it seems that the lower portion of the fresco got severely damaged under the bombing of Pompeii unleashed by the Allied forces in

August and September 1943, with the adjoining House of the Faun being heavily hit.

Fig. 17 - Hams and sausages hanging from a a rod over the heads of a tavern's customers, from Pompeii, Regio VI, insula no. 10, property no. 1 (VI.10.1)

Luckily enough we still have older pictures, taken before the bombing took place, showing a black-and-white vision of the lower section of the image, with the drinking customers at their best.

Fig. 18 - The same fresco contained at Pompeii VI.10.1, a picture taken prior to the 1943 bombing

What can we say before this very portrait of a true, vibrant life? We can sense the continuity of experiences, the uninterrupted succession of men and women who, across different epochs, have been sitting under such a vineyard of cured meat, sipping their wine and enjoying sheep's-milk cheese and salami. Men and women belonging to the ordinary people, workers, soldiers, pretty ladies, all enjoying a sweet moment of quietness, relaxation and refreshment In Roman times just like today.

But — we must never forget — we also have examples of utterly different moments enjoyed by the affluent people only. So, as a conclusion to this chapter, we can't overlook the luscious, ludicrous, immoderate banquet scene described by Gaius Petronius Arbiter in his *Satyricon*, a first-century satirical novel.

In Chapter XLIX, the wealthy host, Trimalchio, has a large tray with a giant hog brought at the very center of the dining table. All the guests begin to wonder at the considerable size of the cooked animal, which seems to be far too excessive. And it's at this point that Trimalchio goes into a fury and shouts: «What? What? This hog hasn't been gutted, has it? No, it hasn't, by Herculest! Call that cook! Call that cook in here immediately!» (in the original Latin text: «Quid? quid? Porcus hic non est exenteratus? Non me-hercules est. Voca, voca cocum in medio»).

As the cook comes, he is angrily, publicly and exaggeratedly scolded by his master, until he is commanded to proceed right away with the evisceration. And here is what magically happens, to the pleasure and amusement of Trimalchio's amazed guests:

«The cook put on his tunic, snatched up a carving knife with a trembling hand, and slashed the hog's belly in several places. Immediately sausages of various sorts, widening the apertures by virtue of their own weight, began to tumble out».

Fig. 19 - Sausages at Trimalchio's lavish banquet, from Gaius Petronius Arbiter's *Satyricon* (as edited by Pieter Burman, Amsterdam, 1743), p. 326-329

[In the original Latin text: «Recepta cocus tunica cultrum arripuit, porcique ventrem hinc atque illinc timida manu secuit. Nec mora, ex plagis, ponderis inclinatione crescentibus, tomacula cum botulis effusa sunt»].

Here sausages are kings of the feast: they flow, they cascade as precious items over the dining table, before the very eyes of merry banqueting Romans. When the Empire ruled the world.

This is a most impressive, most lavish way to celebrate cured meat, which has just started its long, illustrious story across the centuries to come.

Fig. 20 - Today's lucanica of Picerno, Basilicata (Lucania)

2.4 The Lombards and the pigs

We have seen that in Roman times salted pork meat was produced and distributed in Rome and other towns.

But what happened to pigs during the centuries of the High Middle Ages, after the fall of the Western Roman Empire?

Starting from the sixth century A.D., the Lombards began to dominate over many portions of Italy, with Norcia (Nursia) becoming part of the Duchy of Spolegium.

According to scholars, the breeding of pigs keeps its significant relevance in the overall economy of the territories ruled by the Lombards. And an interesting token of this relevance is provided by the famous *Edictum*

Rothari, a codification of Lombard laws issued by King Rothari in 643 A.D. for application in the territories subject to the new domination.

Let's open the bruised, mistreated folia of manuscript no. 730 preserved at the Stiftsbibliothek of the Abbey of Saint Gall, Switzerland: a most precious seventh-century manuscript which contains the most ancient copy of the *Edictum Rothari*, a copy which unfortunately underwent a stunning disruption process during the fifteenth century, when foolish librarians had the brilliant idea to use its unique folia as convenient bindings for other ancient manuscripts.

Fig. 21 - The first page of the *Edictum Rothari* containing the first, second and third provisions (manuscript no. 730 preserved at the Stiftsbibliothek of the Abbey of Saint Gall, Switzerland, seventh century), folium 1

The *Edictum* is a collection of laws, made up by 388 chapters each regulating an aspect of the life under Lombard rule. Of course, the list begins with a single, hardest provision against any attempts to overturn the

royal institution: «If a man plots or counsels [with someone] against the king's life, his life shall be endangered and his possessions confiscated» (in the original Latin text: «Si quis hominum contra animam regis cogitaverit aut consiliaverit, animae suae incurrat periculum et res eius infiscentur»).

The list continues with the inclusion of a series of legal provisions concerning military espionage, murder, attacks to horsemen, people shooting arrows haphazardly, riots, injuries to the jaws, nose, ears and other parts of the body, killing of babies in women's wombs, and so on.

However, amid this collection of multifarious provisions, a special position is recognised to pigs and pig breeding, a sign of the importance of pork's meat in the life of Lombards in Italy.

Provisions no. 135, and the subsequent ones, are very clear:

«The killing of a shepherd — If someone kills someone else's swineherd, in the case the latter is a leader and has under him two, three or more young apprentices, he shall pay a settlement of 50 solidi. As for the lower-rank swineherds, if someone kills [one], he shall pay a settlement of 25 solidi».

Fig. 22 - The provisions on swineherds, from the *Edictum Rothari* (manuscript no. 730 preserved at the Stiftsbibliothek of the Abbey of Saint Gall, Switzerland, seventh century), folia 27 and 28

[In the original Latin text: «De pastore occiso — Si quis porcarium alienum occiserit, magestrum tamen illum, qui sub se discipulos habit duo aut tres aut amplius, conponat solidos quinquaginta. De inferiores autem porcarios, si quis occiderit, conponat solidos viginti et quinque»].

What's the relevance of this? The point is that if you kill an experienced swineherd, a skilled professional for the management of herds of pigs, you will have to pay a fine of fifty solidi: a dizzying amount, if we consider that the solidus was a coin made of more than 4 grams of pure gold, extensively used across the late Roman empire. Instead, if you kill a farmer («servus massarius» — provision no. 132) or a cowherd («bovulus» — provision no. 133), you can get away with it by paying less than half that amount: twenty solidi will be enough to avoid further penalties.

And that's not all. The *Edictum Rothari* is full of other provisions that — again — state the importance of pig breeding. For instance, provision no. 249 tells us that herds of pigs could be used as securities, with a direct involvement of the king, and were as important as horses:

«Herds of horses or pigs — If someone takes away a pledged herd of horses or pigs without an order from the king, the one who is the culprit shall be killed or pay a settlement of 900 solidi, half to the king and half to the one to whom he has taken them away as the pledge».

Fig. 23 - The provision on the stealing of pledged herds of pigs, from the *Edictum Rothari* (manuscript no. 730 preserved at the Stiftsbibliothek of the Abbey of Saint Gall, Switzerland, seventh century), folium

62a

[In the original Latin text: «De grege aequarum seu porcorum. Si quis grege aequarum seu porcorum sine iussionem regis pigneris nomine abstulerit, ille prior aut moriatur aut conponat solidos nongentos, medietatem regi et medietatem cui pignus abstulerit»].

And we find provisions concerning pig's pasture (no. 349), boars (no. 351), swineherd beating (no. 352 and 353), foreclosure of herds of pigs (no. 371). Manifestly pork meat was so important for the life of Lombards that their king wanted to make sure that the breeding of pigs be strictly regulated in their legal system.

But the story of pigs does not end with Lombards. New rulers will dominate the Italian peninsula in the subsequent centuries; yet, pork meat and cured pork meat will remain central in the diet of people belonging to all social classes.

2.5 Swines of the Middle Ages

It is beyond the scope of the present paper to trace the detailed story of this type of food — pork meat — across the Middle Ages; however, it is intriguing to follow, at least partially, this tasty story by showing a series of illuminated manuscripts and frescoes in which the butcher's shop and activities are presented by means of the artistic language of miniatures and paintings.

Fig. 24 - The pannage (pasturage) of pigs in forests (manuscript Royal 2 B. VII *Queen Mary Psalter*, preserved at the British Library, London, fourteenth century), f81

So did Middle Age people still pasture their pigs in forests where plenty of acorns could be found, as Varro recommended? Definitely so, as it is shown in manuscript Royal 2 B. VII, also known as *Queen Mary Psalter*, dating to the fourteenth century, with happy swineherds feeding their animals with the most flavored products of the wood.

And did medieval men slaughter pigs and process their meat at the winter solstice, as illustrated by Columella in his *De re rustica*? Yes, and that's what we find in a most famous image of a 'cinta senese' pig (the famous belted pig of Siena) being pushed by a peasant towards the town of Siena, presented in the *Allegory of Good and Bad Government*, a large fresco painted by Ambrogio Lorenzetti in 1339 on the walls of the Salon of the Council of the Nine in the Palazzo Pubblico of the said town.

Fig. 25 - A peasant conducts a pig to Siena (Ambrogio Lorenzetti's *Allegory of Good and Bad Government*, fresco, Salon of the Council of the Nine, Palazzo Pubblico of Siena, 1339)

Manifestly the pig is being brought to the town for slaughtering and meat processing; and in Padua, at the Palazzo della Ragione, whose immense hall is integrally decorated with a series of fifteenth-century frescoes, of astrological subject, we find the subsequent step: within the month of December, we see a butcher working on an eviscerated pig, his wife ready to collect the drained blood to be used for the preparation of 'sanguinacci' and other specialties.

Fig. 26 - Pig processing in December, fresco on the wall of the large hall on the first floor of the Palazzo della Ragione, Padua

To see in detail how to cut the pig's body into quarters, you can refer to an astonishing manuscript: the *Tacuinum sanitatis*, a handbook which contains a collection of hundreds of miniatures, each expressing the healing properties of a plant or food. A few of those medieval handbooks, designed for the delight of aristocratic audiences, are still surviving. A most beautiful instance is represented by manuscript Cod. Ser. n. 2644, of Italian origin and dating to the end of the fourteenth century, preserved at the Österreichische Nationalbibliothek in Wien. From it we draw the following wondrous miniature of a butcher's laboratory, showing a lively, industrious setting animated by many workers, each intent on a specific task.

Fig. 27 - Processing of pig's quarters and meat (manuscript Cod. Ser. n. 2644, preserved at the Österreichische Nationalbibliothek, fourteenth century), folium 74v

And what happened next? To have a glimpse of what followed, let's jump to a small hamlet, Ceri, sitting on a hill between the Etruscan town of Cerveteri and the Lake of Bracciano, not far from Rome: here, in the ancient, decorated church of the Madonna of Ceri, we find a fresco dating to the thirteenth century which depicts the processing of pork meat, in all its phases and possible choices. A pig is being roasted on a burning fire, maybe during the preparation of the most tasty 'porchetta'; hams and sausages hang from a suspended rod, just as it happened in Pompeii more than a thousand years earlier; a mortar and a pestle are visible on the left side of the image, ready for meat mincing or crushing.

Fig. 28 - Processing of a pig in a fresco on the wall of the church of the Madonna of Ceri, a small village outside Rome (thirteenth century)

And how did they prepare sausages in the Middle Ages? The answer is given to us by Flemish manuscript Douce 5 preserved at the Bodleian Library in Oxford, where we can see that preparation methods are not dissimilar from the ones used today.

Fig. 29 - Sausage making and pig preparation (manuscript Douce 5 preserved at the Bodleian Library in Oxford, fourteenth century), folium 7r

Finally we get to the most delicious moment: the pure, delectable enjoyment of eating an entire ham, as it is shown in a fifteenth-century French miniature (in which the guy is eating and drinking to excess — while allegorically riding a big-sized pig — thus falling into the sin of gluttony).

Fig. 30 - Man enjoying a ham (manuscript M.1001 *Book of hours*, preserved at The Morgan Library & Museum, New York, fifteenth century), f94r

This is the story of pork meat starting from the Romans and across the centuries of the Middle Ages.

We ran through the works written by Apicius, Varro, Columella, Cato the Censor, Marcus Tullius Cicero, Martialis, Petronius Arbiter, the graffiti and frescoes from Herculaneum and Pompeii, and the Lombards, King Rothari and his Edict, and a multitude of illuminated manuscripts dating to the Middle Ages, each showing an aspect of pork meat processing and the delight it procured to the men and women of those distant times.

But now time has come to move to the Apennine chain and the Sibillini Mountain Range, where the ancient town of Norcia lies.

We are now about to tell another amazing story: the astounding story of the 'Norcini', the men coming from Norcia, in Rome, with their unequalled craft concerning the processing of pork meat.

A close, ancient connection and craft, as we will see in the next chapters.

3. Norcia and cured pork meat

3.1 Norcia in antiquity: pig breeding... and turnips

In the previous paragraphs, we saw that Latin author Columella, in his first-century *De re rustica*, wrote that «woods are utterly convenient [for pig breeding], especially those accommodating oaks, corks, beech trees, holm oaks...». And Varro, a century before the Christian era, noted that «those animals [pigs] feed particularly on acorns, then fava beans, barley, and any other sort of wheat; through this food not only they grow fatter, but their meat also acquires a more enjoyable taste».

So was Roman Norcia — Nursia — an ideal place for pig breeding? Of course, it was.

This small settlement set at the foot of the Sibillini Mountain Range, at an altitude of nearly 2,000 feet, lies at the far end of an elongated plateau, surrounded on all sides by wooded elevations, the kingdom of wild boars and deer and wolves: there, domesticated pigs could easily be raised by farmers and guarded by herdsman while they roamed around through the forested hills in search of flavored food, freely handed over to them by a prodigal Nature.

Fig. 31 - A contemporary vision of the wooded mountains which encircle Norcia and its plateau

We can imagine that the extremely fine quality of the nourishment on which they fed rendered the meat of the pigs raised in Norcia a sublime experience for the aristocratic connoisseurs of food in ancient Rome. Oaks and hazelnut trees surrendered their most precious essence to the flesh of the wandering animals, which acted as collectors and distillers of a supreme taste, to be appreciated amid marble columns, cups of wine and honey, and charming slave dancers — a bit picturesque, but true!

Unfortunately we don't have any documented source dating to the Roman epoch that may confirm the scenario we have been illustrating in the previous lines.

In the classical sources, we have a significant number of references which mention the ancient town of Nursia (a complete list is contained in the paper *Norcia nelle fonti antiche e tardoantiche: sintesi cronologica* by Romano Cordella, published on the online journal *Ager Veleias*, 2024). However, the only references to a food specialty coming from ancient Nursia is not linked to pigs, but to... turnips!

Did you know that Pliny the Elder, in his *Naturalis historia* (Book XVIII, Chapter XXXIV, and again Book XIX, Chapter XXV), celebrated the toothsome-ness of the turnips from Norcia?

«The colder the weather the sweeter they [turnips] are, and the larger, it is generally thought; heat makes them turn into leaves. The finest turnip of all is that grown in the district of Nursia: it is valued at as much as one sesterce per pound, and, in times of scarcity, two even. [...] At Rome, the highest rank is given to the turnips of Amiternum and those of Nursia».

quo tuosius prope... ditatem globari. Tertiam specie siluestre appellauere in longitudine radice penumete raphani similitudine & tolo aguloso scabroq; succo acri. Qui circa messem exceptus oculos purgat medeturq; caligini admixto lacte mulier. Frigore dulciora fieri existimant & grandiora tepore in folia exeunt palma in nufino agro nascitur. Taxatio in libras sexterti singuli & in penuria bini proxima in algido natis. Napi uero amitenu: quoz eade fere natura gaudent & que frigidis ferunt & ante kl. martias in iugero sextarii quarto diligetiores quito fulco napum feri iubet. Rapa quarto utroq; stercoreto. Rapa lectiora fieri si palca seminetur. Serere nudu uolunt precante sibi et

table. Neq; ut cleoneum prelogum. In totum quide quoz tenuiora folia. Ipsi quoz dulciores quoz scabra & angulosa & horrida amariore. Est preterea genus siluestre cuius folia sunt cruce familia: palma Romae a miternis datur ide Nursinis Tertia nostratibus. Cetera de fatu eorum in rapis dicta sint.

Fig. 32 - The delicious turnips of Nursia from Pliny the Elder's *Naturalis historia* (from the first printed edition, Venice, 1469), p. 363 and 390

[In the original Latin text: «Frigore dulciora fieri existimantur et grandiora. tepore in folia exeunt. Palma in Nursino agro nascentibus. Taxatio in libras sesterti singuli et in penuria bini. [...] Palma Romae Amiterninis datur, ide Nursinis Terra»].

So in Roman times it was the sweet turnip from Norcia that was praised. We don't find a single word on pigs and pork meat.

And Pliny's mention is not casual. Other Latin authors celebrate the same product from Norcia, and it is always turnips, as we find in Martial (*Epigrams*, Book XIII, 20):

«Turnips — These the land of Amiternum nurtures in its fertile gardens; the round rapes of Nursia you will be able to eat at less cost».

[In the original Latin text: «Napi — Hos Amiternus ager felicibus educat hortis: Nursinas poteris parcius esse pilas»].

Fig. 33 - Turnips from Norcia as quoted in Martial's *Epigrams* (printed edition dating to 1644, Amsterdam), p. 421

As we can see, Nursia and Amiternum (a Sabine town set in the region of Abruzzi) were competing with each other to win the title of best turnip producer of Roman times.

And we also have radish, a relative of the turnip (Columella, *De re rustica*, X, 421):

«... The radish, which Norcia grows in its celebrated territory, and the one from the fields in Amiternum, called 'bunion'».

[In the original Latin text: «... Gongylis, illustri mittit quam Nursia campo, quaeque Amiterninis defertur bunias arvis...»].

Quin & Tardipedi sacris iam rite solutis
Nube noua scritur, cœli pendentibus undis
Congilis illustri mittit quam Nursia campo,
Quæq; Amiterninis defertur bunias aruis.
Sed iam maturis nos flagitat anxius uuis
Euhius, excultosq; iubet claudamus ut hortos.

Fig. 34 - Nursia's radish as found in a printed edition of Lucius Junius Moderatus Columella's *De re rustica* (London, 1548), Book X, verse 421, p. 356

Thus in antiquity, at least in the first century A.D., Norcia was renowned for its turnips and radishes. Latin authors have left no words on pigs being raised in ancient Nursia.

Fig. 35 - Turnips (left) and radishes (right)

However, even though we cannot retrace any specific connection between Norcia and pig breeding in Roman and even Lombard times, sure enough Norcia was a good place for raising pigs, with its wooded mountains, its oaks, its acorn and — last but not least — its turnips, which could also be used as pasturage for swines.

Despite the lack of relevant documentation on the role of Norcia in this kind of activity we can presume that the small settlement placed at the foot of the Sibillini Mountain Range was, to say the least, one of the many centres for the raising of pigs and possibly the curing of their meat, too,

owing to the presence of a most suitable forested territory, the perfect ventilation from the neighboring mountains for cured meat processing, and the proximity to the great food market of Rome, a capital city counting more than one million residents in Roman times.

Therefore we can imagine that, just as in many other territories during the ages of the Romans and Lombards (Norcia was part of the Duchy of Spolegium, a Lombard territory, so pig breeding in the area was subject to the rules stated in the *Edictum Rothari*), many farmers in Norcia used to raise pigs; and the meat of those pigs was no lower-quality meat, as the domesticated animals were being raised by feeding them with the acorns in the forests and the renowned turnips grown in the local fields.

Fig. 36 - A large three-century-old oak in Nottoria, a hamlet set not far from Norcia: a picture which provides an impressive image of what the territory offered in ancient Roman times

However, still Norcia was not being celebrated for this specific type of food.

But in the Late Middle Ages some clues will begin to show up, telling us that something was about to change, as we will see in the next paragraph.

3.2 Norcia in the Middle Ages: the pigs' business

In the fourteenth century, Norcia was a small commune, a partially-independent local entity, governed by wealthy families holding official posts but set under the control of the Pope, who approved the local charters and appointed some of the magistrates to the main administrative offices. According to estimates proposed by scholars (see Federico Lattanzio, *Il Comune di Norcia e i suoi rapporti con il governo pontificio nel secolo XV*, Ph.D. thesis, Florence, 2013, p. 47 and 48), the population of Norcia possibly totalled a few thousand people, with a significant loss of human lives caused by the large earthquake which occurred in the area in 1328.

It is in this period that we begin to find information about the increasing importance of pig raising in Norcia.

Fig. 37 - The opening page of the *Statutorum Nursie*, printed in Perugia in 1526

Let's consider the illustrious volumes of the *Charters of Norcia* (*Statutorum Nursiae*), printed in the year 1526 but whose provisions date back to the fourteenth-fifteenth century (Romano Cordella, *Statuti di Norcia: testo volgare a stampa del 1526*, Perugia, 2011, p. XLIV-XLV).

While classical Latin sources say nothing about pigs in ancient Nursia, now we start finding that domesticated pigs are mentioned many times and subject to a lot of specific regulation, a signal that pig raising is alive and kicking in medieval Norcia, at least for local consumption.

Book I of the Charters contains a number of rules which regulate the trading of pork meat and the activity of butchers, including those who process this quality of meat.

Because, in Norcia, actually there was a considerable pig market, to be held during the month of September, as explicitly stated by provision CCXI:

«Of the market of the pigs — Then we state and command that the Consuls of the land of Norcia in charge during the month of September must call for the market of the pigs...».

[In the original Italian text: «Della piazza delli porci — Item statuimo et ordinamo che li S.C. [Signori Consuli] di la terra de Norsia li quali seranno per li tempi dello mese di settembre siano tenuti et debiano far bandire la piazza delli porci...»].

For each traded animal within the market the municipality was paid a specific fee. The pigs were brought at the fair by butchers and farmers coming from Norcia and even from outer territories («ipsi venditori de porci se intendano tanto nursini et districtuali quanto foresteri che menassero porci alla dicta terra de norsia per vendere»); the local traders were even encouraged to come, as they were not compelled to pay the basic fee unless they completed the sale of their animals.

According to provision no. CCXII the money earned by the municipality and arising from the fee paid by the butchers was to be safely stored «in the stronghold of the fortified walls of the land of Norcia» («li denari dello prezo che se faranno dallo vendere dla piazza delli porci della terra de Norsia se debiano mettere [...] nello revellino delli barbacani delle mura

della terra di Norcia») to the public honor, strength and utility of Norcia («per utilità honore et perpetua forteza de epsa terra de Norsia»), and for future use.

We understand, when we read the words from the Charters, that the pig's fair was a big affair for Norcia: it must have been huge, and a lot of money must have been deposited «in the stronghold of the fortified walls» each year, if the clause stresses the point that the Consuls had better to «appoint a trustworthy person, of full reliability, in whose hands the said money must be safely trusted» («elegere uno dipositario quale sia idonea et fidata persona in mano del quale debiano venir tucti li sopra dicti denari»).

Fig. 38 - Provisions CCXI and CCXII from the *Statutorum Nursie* (Perugia, 1526), f95v

And the traffic of domesticated pigs — going in and out the land of Norcia — is really significant. Pigs are explicitly mentioned in the table of the tariffs to be applied by custom officers at the relevant check points (Book III, provision no. CXXXIII):

- pigs (priced 1 guilder): 1 soldo and a half (meaning 6 denari)
- pigs (priced between a guilder and half guilder): 9 denari
- pigs (priced less than half guilder): 4 denari
- pigs purchased in Norcia and going out: 3 soldi, but they pay nothing if they had got in to be sold in Norcia, and did not find a buyer

Luckily enough, many exemptions applied, for instance to «animals led out by the inhabitants of Norcia and farmers to be sold at fairs» (in Italian «animali che i nursini et contadini se cavassoro per mandarli ad vendere alla fiera»).

Fig. 39 - Provision CXXXIII, Book III from the *Statutorum Nursie* (Perugia, 1526), folia 100v and 111r

But a question still floats in our minds: did butchers operate in medieval Norcia? And did they actually process pork meat? Yes indeed.

To begin with, the body of the local laws includes a general provision (no. CLI) on the total freedom granted to those who intended to work in the butchery business: «Everybody be authorised to do butchery in the land of Norcia» (in the original Italian language: «che sia licito ad ognuno fare lo macello in nella terra de Norsia»). In fact, to this art is associated a critical public interest, «so as to have plenty of meat of all types in the said land and in its territory» («ad ciò che se habia copia de carne de omne generatione in nella dicta terra et suo districtu»).

Thus, starting at least from the fourteenth-fifteenth century, butchers and butchery were considered in Norcia as a pivotal element of the local economy. And this will make up the fundamental platform from which the local production of high-quality pork meat will subsequently expand, in the following centuries, to the lucrative market of Rome.

If butchery is to be widely carried out in Norcia, limitations must be introduced to avoid misapplications and inappropriate operations. It is provision no. CLX that provides a basic prescription for the safeguard of public health and hygiene, by indicating that the art of butchery cannot be practiced within the town walls:

«We state and command that no butcher shall slaughter or sell meat of sow or boar [...] if not by the gates of the land of Norcia, and in those places everyone be authorised to prepare and sell such meat with no penalty nor infringement».

[In the original Italian text: «Statuimo et ordinamo, che niuno macellaro possa ne debia occidere o vendere carne de scrofa ne carne de verre [...] Excepto et reservato alle porte della terra de Norsia, che i nelli detti loci ad omne persona sia licito epse carni fare et vendere senza pena et banno»].

Another clause that intends to deal with sanitary issues is provision no. CLII, which prevents butchers from «taking dead flesh of castrone or pig or other animal from another butcher to resell it» («niuno macellaro possa pigliare carne morta de castrone o de porco o de altro animale da uno altro macellaro per revendere epse carne»), so as to avoid the trade of rotten meat in a historical period in which no fridges were available.

Provision no. CLVIII confronts with a typical misbehaviour of butchers in the course of the sale process: «we state and command that no butcher of the land of Norcia, its countryside and district, nor foreigner shall weigh, together with other meat, shanks, heads, thighs, heads of pigs, castrated and other animals, as they shall sell them separately at half the price of pork meat» (in the original Italian language: «statuimo et ordinamo che niuno macellaro della terra de Norsia suo contado et districtu o foresteri possa pesare insieme con altre carni ogne, teste, gambe, teste de porci, castrati et altri animali ma le debia vendere seperate et darele per la mità delllo prezzo se vendesse le carni porcine»). This also applied to «lungs, heart and

spleen» («pulmone, core et milza»), with exception of the same parts when cut from a pig («excepto non fosse secato de porco»), clearly a delicacy that was to be sold at full price.

Fig. 40 - Provisions CLI, CLX, CLVIII and CLII, Book I, from the *Statutum Nursie* (Perugia, 1526) folia 28b, 30r, 29v, 29r

So there are pigs in Norcia during the fourteenth/fifteenth century, the period in which the Charters were in place? Yes, they are there. And they are even annoying, as we find in some other provisions present in the Charters.

If you remember, pigs in Norcia feed on savoury acorns, which you can find by the many oaks that make up the woods and forests in the neighbouring territory.

But — when looking for acorns — pigs can turn into veritable war machines, ravaging any cultivated land they stumble upon, if the swineherd is not careful enough in directing their enthusiasm. So the *Statuti* try to cope with the problem (Book V, provisions no. VIII and IX):

«If any pig or sow is be found in the ['groco'? possibly a cultivated field] belonging to someone else [...] in case of any damages their owner shall be punished by a fine of twenty soldi for each pig or sow and for any occurrence, and the owner [...] shall restore the damage [...]. We command that no one send his pigs or sows [...] to the foot of any oak from the second half of September to the second half of November. [...] And it is forbidden to collect the acorns from the oaks belonging to others, under a fine of twenty soldi».

[In the original Italian language: «Se alcuno porco o scrofa serrà trovato nello groco de alcuno [...] per qualunque modo darà danno sia punito lu patrone de ipso pena de vinti soldi per ciascun porco o scrofa et ciascuna fiata et lu patrone [...] sia tenuto mendare lu danno [...]. Ordinamo che niuno mecta porci o scrofe [...] apede de alcuna cerqua o cerro della mità del mese de septembre fino alla mità del mese di novembre. [...] Et a niuno sia licito de cogliere le ianne delle cerque o cerri de altri ad pena de vinti soldi»].

Fig. 41 - Provisions VIII and IX, Book V, from the *Statutorum Nursie* (Perugia, 1526), f118r

So the herds of pigs must not go around and feed on the acorns of others. And, as a curiosity, here we find a first sign of a provision devised to protect the typical, most-famous golden treasure of Norcia: the black

truffle, which still today is being collected from the ground near the oaks after the month of September; pigs must be kept away from the foot of the trees lest they eat the whole treasure up.

Here we are. In these late-medieval centuries Norcia is already a good place to raise good (tasty) pigs, as possibly happened in antiquity, too, even though in classical Latin works we only read about turnips and radishes.

What was the type of pigs that was being raised in Norcia at the time? We can see a 'photograph' of it on the decorated walls of the ancient Church of Santa Maria Assunta, in the small hamlet of Vallo di Nera, not far from Norcia. There a fifteenth-century fresco shows the illustrious 'cinta senese', or belted pig from Siena, a breed that we also saw in a previous paragraph as depicted by Ambrogio Lorenzetti in the Palazzo Pubblico of Siena:

Fig. 42 - 'Cinta senese' pig depicted on a fresco in the Church of Santa Maria Assunta, Vallo di Nera (fifteenth century)

As we illustrated in our previous essay *The Precian Surgical School: an astounding European-wide success originated from a small Apennine hamlet* (2026), this same pig is also present in other frescoed images located at various churches of the neighboring Valle Castoriana, such as St. Antonio at Ancarano and St. Giovanni at Piedivalle of Preci.

Fig. 43 - 'Cinta senese' pig, Church of St. Antonio, Ancarano of Norcia (left), and Church of St. Giovanni, Piedivalle of Preci (right), from *Suino nero cinghiato - Storia del recupero e della reintroduzione di un'antica popolazione suina in Valnerina*, in *I quaderni della biodiversità*, no. 4 (Perugia, 2020), p. 32 and 41

This type of pig will be extensively raised in Norcia across the centuries to come, too. A most interesting witness who reported on this specific aspect is François-Jacques Deseine: in 1699 the French writer published a veritable travellers' guide to Italy (*Nouveau voyage d'Italie*), in which he describes his impressions concerning the town of Norcia:

Fig. 44 - The excerpt on Norcia and its black pigs from François-Jacques Deseine's *Nouveau voyage d'Italie* (Lyon, 1699), *Nouveau voyage*, p. 40

«... In the territory of Norcia they raise an amazing quantity of pigs, and nearly all of them are black...».

[In the original French text: «... On nourrit dans le territoire de Norcia une prodigieuse quantité de cochons qui sont noirs presque tous...»].

And a multitude of 'black' pigs will be also retrieved in Norcia a century and a half later, in the book *Topografia statistica dello Stato Pontificio* (1859)

«In the territory [...] which is not so fertile, there are many woods with acorns, so there are raised huge cattle of black animals, of which a great trade is made, and also of a most excellent salted pork meat; and many 'Norcini' of the populace are renowned for their dexterity in carrying out castration on pigs».

[In the original Italian text: «Nel territorio [...] che dà un mediocre raccolto, essendovi molti boschi di ghiande, vi si allevano copiose mandre d'animali neri, de' quali si fa grande traffico, ed anche di salata porcina di molta eccellenza, come rinomati sono ben molti Norcini della plebe, in castrare destramente porcelli»].

fabbriche di tele di lino, di canapa. Nel territorio della superficie di rubbia 14146 che dà un mediocre raccolto, essendovi molti boschi di ghiande, vi si allevano copiose mandre d'animali neri, de' quali si fa grande traffico, ed anche di salata porcina di molta eccellenza, come rinomati sono ben molti Norcini della plebe, in castrare destramente porcelli. V'è poi in città un settimanale Mercato assai pingue, e 10 annue

Fig. 45 - Black pigs in Norcia from Adone Palmieri's *Topografia statistica dello Stato Pontificio - Parte Quinta, provincie di Spoleti e Camerino* (Roma, 1859), p. 52

Now, back to the end of the Middle Ages, we can say that the era of turnips is over, and pigs in Norcia are kings of the food sector (as they will be, according to Deseine, also in the seventeenth century). Or, to say the least, they are a significant part of the town's lively economy, which includes butchery as it is effectively described by F. Lattanzio (p. 51) basing on a study on the list of eight 'Arts', or guilds, present in town during the fifteenth century:

«[...] We can get a rough idea of the manufacturing activities that marked the social and economical life of the town in which St. Benedict was born during the fifteenth century. [...] The eight guilds were] those of butchers, carpenters and stonecutters, tailors, blacksmiths, makers of woollen products, shoemakers, traders and soldiers, judges, physicians and notaries public (macellorum, lignaminum et lapidum, sutorum, fabrorum, lane, calzolaiorum, mercatorum e militum, iudicum, medicorum et notariorum), with the last four categories forming a single group. Apart from the last two, that were mainly social guilds, we can easily infer that [...] only two of those activities were the main pillars of the local economy and commercial trade in fifteenth-century Norcia: butchery and the production of woollen fabric».

Lattanzio (p. 54) confirms that «it is possible to assume that butchery and meat trading was in late-medieval Norcia, as well as sixteenth-century Norcia, a most important portion of its economy». However, we don't agree with him when he says that «on the contrary, it doesn't come out, in this same period, an already strong focus in the field of pig raising [...] which possibly emerged, gradually, in the course of the subsequent centuries, starting from the seventeenth-eighteenth century»: in the light of what we said in the present paragraph and the next ones, we repute that Norcia's specialisation on pigs was already shaped up in the fifteenth century, and became apparent in Rome during the next century.

And that wasn't only a matter of pigs: because fifteenth-century Norcia was already over the top as to what concerns the production of delicious salted pork meat. And toothsome hams.

3.3 *The renowned, most-flavory hams of Norcia*

In the previous paragraph we said that, as to salted pork meat, fifteenth-century Norcia knew how to do the job. But how can we prove this claim?

Actually we are able to retrieve a specific, targeted mention about the superiority of Norcia with relation to hams directly in a work dating to 1542: it is not the fifteenth century, we are some fifty years later; but we must consider that fame needs time to build up.

With the odd title *In praise of cheese, written by Mr. Stentato (Formaggiata di Sere Stentato)*, this curious booklet is a humorous treatise over the quality and delectability of the cheese made, at the time, in Piacenza, in northern Italy. It is a work written by Giulio Landi, a man of letter born from a noble family originating in the same town.

When describing the local milk and salt used in the preparation of cheese, he says that that same quality salt from Piacenza is also used in the preparation of sausages in the same town, to be considered as the best ones in Italy, but — according to the author himself — with a few exceptions:

«So good is the salt from Piacenza that its goodness is attested by the cervelats, bolognas, black puddings, 'zambudelli' et sausages, and any other sort of salami, which here in Piacenza are manufactured by our women; and they are delicate to the utmost, and of excellent flavour, as they are certainly the best Salami that are made in the whole of Italy — with the honorable exceptions of the cured loin from Naples and the hams from Norcia»

[In the original Italian text: «Tanto è di eccellente qualità il sale piacentino di che ne fanno fede i cervelati, le mortadelle, i sanguinacci, i Zambudelli, et le salsiccie, et ogni altra sorte di salame; che qui da noi le donne fanno: il quale è dilicatissimo, et di ottimo gusto, et certo sono i migliori Salami, che in Italia si faccino, salvando perhò l'honore delle somate di Napoli, et i persciutti di norsia»].

Fig. 46 - A sixteenth-century reference to the hams produced in Norcia from Giulio Landi's *Formaggiata di Sere Stentato* (Piacenza, 1542) p. 7

So in the first half of the sixteenth century Norcia was already renowned, at least in Rome where Giulio Landi had been living for many years, for the unrivalled quality of its hams. And this is a confirmation of the fact that its renown concerning cured pork meat had started building up decades and decades earlier, to say the least, and most probably as far back as the fifteenth century.

Now, let's consider in more depth the above reference to the toothsome hams made in Norcia, contained in a humorous book written in 1542.

Can we perceive, in our present days, all the mighty power of this odd reference to Norcia, included in a work totally dedicated to the quality of the food products processed in Piacenza?

The hams from Norcia must have been so good and so utterly appreciated in Rome (a city in which Giulio Landi had been living many years) that he could not omit to include a mention about that small mountainous settlement, lost amid the Apennines: because too strong was the running fame of its hams, and this renown could not be neglected, even in a work marked by a hue of literary fun, written in praise of Piacenza!

Of course, in Italy Norcia was not alone. The processing of salted pork meat was a craft that many other towns and regions knew well, each with

their specific methods and recipes. For instance, we may quote from *The excellence and triumph of the pig* (*L'eccellenza et trionfo del porco*), another extravagant work dating to 1594, written by Salustio Miranda, a nickname of writer and performer Giulio Cesare Croce; in it the author praises the quality of the sausages produced in Bologna, Ferrara and Cremona. We might also remember the cured pork meat typical of Piacenza and Naples, as mentioned in the said *Formaggiata di Sere Stentato*.

Che dirò io sopra le Mortadelle, Salami, Salciz-
zoni, Salcicie, Ceruellati, Sanguinazzi, Ciambu-
delli, e tante altre cose, che si cauano della carne di
questo animale, le quali tutte sono preciose, & rare, &
massime le Mortadelle, & i Salami, i quali sono cibi
da Prencipi, & da Signori; e di questo la Città di Bo-
logna porta il vanto, per farle con tutte le preminen-
ze, ch'elle uanno. Et anchora Ferrara è eccellentissi-
ma, & se ne mandano ogn'anno à diuersi Signori: e
personaggi d'importanza, & sono tenuti in grandis-
sima stima per tutte le Città, come per la Lombardia
quelle di Cremona.

Fig. 47 - Sausages from various Italian towns as mentioned in Giulio Cesare Croce's *L'eccellenza et trionfo del porco* (Ferrara, 1594), p. 16

But all those sausages were manufactured too far from Rome. And, for Rome and the Romans, cured pork meat will begin to mean Norcia. Norcia with its crafted skills; Norcia with its luscious hams; Norcia with its experienced 'Norcini'.

As early as the fifteenth century, a number of people from Norcia started to move from Norcia to Rome: those people will give birth to the long-lasting figure of the 'Norcino'.

And the 'Norcini' will conquer Rome, with a peaceful invasion of salted pork meat. As we will see in the next chapters.

4. The fourteenth century: Florence first

4.1 Porters and butchers from Norcia in Florence

The present essay is centered on the history of the presence of the people from Norcia, the so-called 'Norcini', in late-medieval and modern Rome, up to our present days.

Nonetheless, before we start discussing the presence of the 'Norcini' in Rome, we must first divert our steps from the town of the Popes and take the road to fourteenth-century Florence.

Why Florence? Because Florence, in the fourteenth century, was a rich, important city, whose economy was flourishing under the push of primary banking activities, controlled by a number of affluent families, and a prominent role in the industrial production of wool fabrics. By contrast, in the same century, as we will see in the following chapter, Rome was still a dilapidated town, sitting on its ancient ruins, ravaged by the internal struggles among the local barons, and with the Popes settled in Avignon, France.

While Rome still did not offer significant job opportunities, medieval Florence already needed workers. Lots of them. And, since the fourteenth century, the town attracted many immigrants, from other places around Italy.

Why? Because Florence had a primary role in the manufacturing of wool fabrics, the so-called 'pannilana'. Its high-quality woollen cloth was universally known, and its production was appreciated and purchased by customers all around Europe. During the centuries of the Middle Ages, Florence was the veritable European capital of textile manufacturing.

With a population of around 100,000 inhabitants, some 30,000 people were employed in the many phases of the production of 'pannilana': the wool, purchased by the experienced Florentine traders at the fairs held in the French region of Champagne and in Flemish towns like Ypres, was initially brought to Florence; there, after the passage through the local customs, this basic commodity underwent a number of processing steps, including quality selection, washing and battering, carding and combing, spinning

and twisting, and weaving. Then the newly-produced textiles were fullled to increase their density and strength, and finally dyed with splendid, gorgeous natural colors. Ready for shipment and sale all around Europe.

Fig. 48 - Manufacturing of clothes (manuscript Cod. Ser. n. 2644, preserved at the Österreichische Nationalbibliothek, fourteenth century), f105r and f106r

So lots of low-level, unskilled workers were needed to perform the related heavy-duty tasks intertwined with the multi-phased manufacturing process: these included the transport of all the half-processed and fully-processed packs of cloth from the customs and then from one processing site to another, which were scattered amid the various town districts. This was a task for a multitude of porters and bearers, who swarmed across the streets loaded with their burdens; a job that was illustrated by Placido Landini in his *Storia della venerabile arciconfraternita della Misericordia dalla sua origine fino ai giorni nostri* (1871):

«[Already from the thirteenth century] the inhabitants of Florence [were] engaged in the trade and sale, and the manufacturing of woollen cloth, which out of their special, extraordinary quality were appreciated and asked for everywhere. [...] So there was the need to have many porters, who were in charge to move the woollen fabrics back and forth between the warehouses and the manufacturing shops».

[In the original Italian text: «[Già dal tredicesimo secolo] i Fiorentini [erano] occupati e intenti al traffico e alla mercatura, impannavano lane, che per la loro speciale e squisita bontà erano repute e richieste per tutto

il mondo. [...] Era bisogno per conseguenza che vi si trovassero molti facchini, i quali i panni e le lane portassero e riportassero ai magazzini e alle botteghe»].

This was the reason for which, already in the fourteenth century, we find many 'Norcini' in Florence: they were unskilled workers, whose main job was the transport of heavy loads. In Italian, 'facchini'. At the same time, they used to bring with them their skilled know-how, that concerning pork meat and its tasty processing.

In Florence, there were so many of them that we find a witness to their early fourteenth-century presence in a learned work written in 1853 by Luigi Passerini Orsini de' Rilli, a knowledgeable scholar and the Director of the Archivio di Stato of Florence. In his well-informed essay (*Storia degli stabilimenti di beneficenza e d'istruzione elementare gratuita della città di Firenze*), he presents the people from Norcia in Florence, in their dual role as both porters and experienced butchers:

Fig. 49 - The 'Norcini' in Florence, from Luigi Passerini Orsini de' Rilli's *Storia degli stabilimenti di beneficenza e d'istruzione elementare gratuita della città di Firenze* (Florence, 1853), p. 104

«The porters from Norcia, also commonly known as Bearers, formed a pious guild in 1317 and determined to establish a small Hospital for the accommodation of the elderly poor, providing assistance to their infirmities, and with a preferential access granted to the members of the guild, and for their fellow-countrymen from Norcia who annually used to come to Florence to salt and process pork meat».

[In the original Italian text: «I portatori di Norcia, detti più volgarmente Facchini, unitisi in pia associazione nel 1317, deliberarono di fondare uno Spedaletto destinato a ricoverare dei poveri vecchi, assisterli nelle loro infermità, con dritto di preferenza agli ascritti nell'Arte, ed a que' loro compatriotti di Norcia che in ciascun anno si portavano a Firenze a salare ed acconciare le carni di porco»].

So, while in the very same period Rome was living an age of poverty, destitution and underdevelopment, Florence was already attracting a large number of 'Norcini' workers from the small town set at the foot of the Sibillini Mountain Range, offering to them various types of job opportunities (including surgery, as we will see below) and a chance to earn their living, especially during the winter seasons when the land of Norcia was submerged by heavy snowfalls and substantially frozen.

The community of 'Norcini' in Florence was so significant that in the first quarter of the fourteenth century they felt the need to set up their own association, with a view to providing mutual support and help to their fellow-countrymen who used to come to the Tuscan town on both a temporary or permanent basis.

Of this ancient brotherhood we still have the illustrious emblem, carved in stone: the name of the association, written around the outer edge, was «Guild of the Porters of St. John the Beheaded of Norcia» (in Italian, «Compagnia di San Giovanni Decollato dei Portatori di Norcia»), as the brotherhood was dedicated to the patron saint of Florence, St. John the Baptist, who is shown with his head severed by a guard of Herod Antipas.

Fig. 50 - Emblem of the Guild of the Porters of St. John the Beheaded of Norcia in Florence (carved stone, sixteenth century), preserved at the Museo di San Marco, Florence

This emblem, whose actual name is 'small stone' ('pietrino' in Italian) was to be found — as it was a usual custom in Florence — on the external wall of a building that was the property of the association, in a downtown district set at the intersection of Via San Gallo and Via dei Camporeggi. A house was there, which the porters from Norcia had bought and were using as a 'hospital' (for accommodation and assistance) to the benefit of their fellow-citizens who worked in Florence: it was the ancient Hospital of St. John the Beheaded of the people of Norcia (in Italian, 'Ospedale di San Giovanni Decollato dei Norcini').

According to Luciano Artusi and Antonio Patruno (*Gli antichi ospedali di Firenze*, Firenze, 2000, p. 111), «the industrious 'Norcini' determined in 1317 to establish in Florence a hospital, also including a small church, “to the benefit and shelter of the Poor of the Nation of Norcia, especially when they are ill”. To this purpose the guild members set up “(...) a house in the town of Florence in the district of San Lorenzo, in the area which is called Camporeggi”» (in Italian, «Gli intraprendenti norcini deliberarono nel 1317 di fondare in Firenze uno spedale con oratorio annesso "a necessità e rifugio de' Poveri della Nazione di Norcia particolarmente quando sieno

infermi". A tal fine i confratelli vollero erigere "(...) una casa nella città di Firenze nel popolo di Santo Lorenzo, nella contrada che si chiama Camporeggi"».

As we already illustrated in our previous essay *The Precian Surgical School: an astounding European-wide success originated from a small Apennine hamlet* (2026), medieval hospitals are not to be intended in modern terms. They were places where people could be accommodated, assisted and fed, especially when travelling or ill; and the 'Norcini', as a local community in Florence, used to make long seasonal trips to and from Norcia, with extended stays in the Tuscan town, so they felt the need to establish some sort of local assistance to their fellow-citizens: a proud way to mark their presence in Florence, as hospitals needed funding and in this way the community visibly manifested its cohesion, financial solidity and ability to sustain the expenses of a local institution.

Fig. 51 - The Hospital of St. John of the porters of Norcia, from Giovanni Lami's *Sanctae ecclesiae Florentinae monumenta* (1758), Vol. II, p. 1358 and 1364

According to an eighteenth-century scholar, Giovanni Lami, who in his *Sanctae ecclesiae Florentinae monumenta* (1758) reported the text of a manuscripted last will and testament of a certain Bartolo di Cino Benvenuti, in 1361 Bartolo bequeathed «to the Hospital of St. John, known as the Hospital of the Porters, six pairs of bed sheets, each worth six pounds» (in Italian, «allo Spedale di S. Giovanni, che si chiama lo Spedale de' Portatori, sei paia di lenzuola della detta stima [di lire sei] ciascun paio»). And Lami adds that «above the entrance gate an inscription reads: 'This is the Hospital of St. John of the Porters from Norcia'» («Supra Portam scriptum est: 'Questo è lo Spedale di S. Ioanni de' Portatori da Norcia'»): a proud declaration marked in stone by the 'Norcini' of Florence.

Is this hospital still extant? Artusi and Patruno (p. 113) further specify that the house was «around Via San Gallo 68, where now is the High School of Arts 'Leon Battista Alberti', and it was mainly devoted to the accommodation, as we already reported, “(...) of those who happen to come from Norcia to salt the meat of porks and make sausages and other food products, and while being in Florence have gotten ill”» (in Italian, «all'incirca al n. 68 dove ora ha sede il Liceo Artistico Statale Leon Battista Alberti, specialmente per accogliere, come già noto, “(...) coloro che vengono di Norcia a salar carne di maiale, per salsiccia et altro, e che stando per tal causa in Firenze si sono ammalati”»).

Fig. 52 - The building of the High School of Arts at Via San Gallo 68 in Florence (left), where was possibly located the ancient Hospital of St. John the Beheaded of the people of Norcia

Subsequently, as recounted by Luigi Passerini Orsini de' Rilli, in the second half of the sixteenth century, the Hospital was forced to relocate, and the Porters bought another house not far from there, between Via delle Ruote and Via di Santa Reparata. Eventually, in the eighteenth century the hospital was assigned to a different charitable association and the Guild of the Porters was dismantled by order of the government, possibly because it was not active anymore.

So in the fourteenth century the 'Norcini' were in Florence as porters and butchers: they had their own guild and were well-stocked enough to afford the purchase of a house and the management of a small hospital for the poor and the ill.

But were they the only 'Norcini' who were present in Florence during the fourteenth century? Not at all, because the migration from the land of Norcia, beside porters and butchers, was bringing to Tuscany another sort of 'Norcini' as well: the Precian surgeons, as we will see in the next paragraph.

4.2 Precian surgeons in fourteenth-century Florence

Migration calls migration, so it is no surprise to find out, as we already illustrated in our previous essay on the Precian Surgical School, that Florence, a town where immigrants from Norcia began to work as butchers and porters as early as the fourteenth century, was also the destination of an initial, successful migration of further 'Norcini', in their specific role as Precian surgeons: «from the registries of the Guild of Physicians in Florence», we wrote in *The Precian Surgical School* (2026), «we can see that something was already happening as early as the second half of the fourteenth century: the land of Norcia was beginning to produce a number of surgeons, and especially proficient in internal surgery (stones, hernia), who were being exported towards a major town of central Italy [Florence], in which at the time power was in the hands of trade and arts».

Through the studies carried out by experienced researchers such as Katherine Park and David Gentilcore, it could be ascertained that «between

1368 and 1444, Florence's Guild of Physicians, Apothecaries, and Grocers enrolled twenty-six practitioners from Norcia and its territories».

cities. In Florence in 1406, two hernia surgeons, Maestro Antonio and Maestro Francesco of Norcia were granted an extremely rare lifetime tax exemption. Some twenty years later, in the city's *catasto* or tax register of 1427, nine such specialists were listed; out of thirty-seven male heads of household identified as a *medicus* (doctor) of some sort or other, five of them, all of the same family, were hernia doctors (*medici de' crepati*) from Norcia. Between 1386 and 1444, Florence's Guild of Physicians, Apothecaries, and Grocers enrolled twenty-six practitioners from Norcia and its territories.¹³⁹ Similarly, in the thirty years from 1540 to 1570,

Fig. 53 - 'Norcini' surgeons in fifteenth-century Florence, from David Gentilcore's *Medical charlatanism in early modern Italy* (Oxford, 2006), p. 182 and 183

«Clear. Massive. Almost unexpected», we wrote. But, as a matter of fact, this astounding presence of Precian surgeons in Florence, in a period when still nobody seemed to know nothing about them outside their original homeland in Norcia, is not so unexpected.

In the light of our further insight on the characteristics of the early migration flow from Norcia to Florence in the fourteenth century, the presence of the Precians in Tuscany is now easily accounted for: they came to Florence as a side effect of the main migration of butchers and unskilled workers from the town of St. Benedict. It is clear that the throng of people coming from Norcia, on both a temporary and a permanent basis, to work as porters and process pork meat, brought to Florence the odd, curious news about some fellow-countrymen of them that were skilled practical surgeons, so proficient that they could even perform lithotomy and cataract surgery successfully.

The low-skilled 'Norcini', already present in numbers in town since the beginning of the fourteenth century, must have praised and exalted the

crafty hands of the Precians to the people in Florence, and so convincingly that some of them, greatly suffering for the stones or fearing blindness out of a cataract, must have asked for one or more Precians to come and treat them.

And, following the first successful operations, the Precian surgeons were in: their presence began to be eagerly requested in Florence, especially by the most affluent inhabitants, as it was becoming clear that those people from Norcia weren't telling lies, and their fellow-citizens were truly proficient in surgery, and in an unexpected way.

So Florence became the very first area outside Norcia in which, as early as the fourteenth century, the Precian Surgical School could establish its roots. And this occurred out of the good publicity about the Precians disseminated in the Tuscan town by the many migrant workers of Norcia who already used to be present in the town itself.

This was the beginning of a surgical presence that will last centuries: from Maestro Antonio and Maestro Francesco of Norcia, who in 1404 were granted an extremely rare lifetime tax exemption, to the hernia doctors ('medici de' crepati') from Norcia registered in the 'catasto' of Florence, dating to 1427, and up to Girolamo Accoramboni and Antonio Benevoli from Preci, the former second chief of castration and ophthalmologist at the illustrious Hospital of St. Maria Nuova in eighteenth-century Florence, and the latter a professor of surgery and lector at the same hospital.

The 'Norcini' as surgeons were mainly originating from Preci, in the Valle Castoriana, set in the territory of Norcia. But where were all those butchers and porters in Florence from? A clue to their specific area of provenance is given to us by some additional information, which we will illustrate in the following paragraph. And we will see that they, too, seem to have come to Florence starting from the Valle Castoriana.

4.3 'Norcini' from the Valle Castoriana to fourteenth-century Florence

It seems that the early migration from Norcia to Florence, dating to the fourteenth century, might have taken place especially from a specific area

of the homeland of St. Benedict: the Valle Castoriana, the secluded valley from which the medieval Precian surgeons were born.

Why do we set forth such a suggestion? Because it appears that a close link existed between Florence and two small castles belonging to Norcia and set on the hills that border the Valle Castoriana itself: Abeto and Todiano, lying a few miles from Preci and its surgeons.

Fig. 54 - Todiano and Abeto, two small hamlets lying in the Valle Castoriana, not far from Preci

Actually it appears that a significant migration from the two tiny hamlets fuelled the historical presence, in Florence, of the people originating from the area of Norcia.

This is attested by the joint presence, in both Abeto and Todiano, even though in more recent times, of a special charitable association of local people: the 'Opera Pia di San Giovanni Decollato in Abeto e Todiano', also called 'Università dei facchini norcini di Preci', dating to the nineteenth century. In English, this means Charitable community of St. John the Beheaded of the Porters from Norcia in Preci: the very same words that have been marking the identity of the ancient Guild of the Porters of St. John the Beheaded of Norcia in Florence.

According to recent studies (Soprintendenza Archivistica dell'Umbria, *Le istituzioni pubbliche di assistenza e beneficenza dell'Umbria*, 1990, p. 354 and 355), this local association was born in a much later age, as its first known Charters date back to 1886; nonetheless, in the same Charters it is specified that the 'Opera Pia di San Giovanni Decollato in Abeto e Todiano' «finds its own roots in the Company of the porters at the customs of

Florence, and in the statement issued by the Grand Duke of Tuscany, Leopold I, on February 7 1786» (in Italian, «trae la sua origine dalla Società dei facchini nella dogana di Firenze, e dal rescritto del granduca di Toscana Leopoldo I in data 7 febbraio 1786»). In fact, as the mentioned study also recollects, «the migrants from Abeto and Todiano had long established in Florence a guild of workers at the customs, with a hospital dedicated to the people from Norcia, to the additional purpose of granting subsidies to the poor back in their own native land».

Fig. 55 - The 'Opera Pia di San Giovanni Decollato in Abeto e Todiano' from *Le istituzioni pubbliche di assistenza e beneficenza dell'Umbria* (Rome, 1990), a volume edited by the Soprintendenza Archivistica dell'Umbria, p. 354

What did Leopold I state in his decree dated February 7 1786? We do not know for certain; however, as it is reported by local scholar Ansano Fabbi (*Artisti fiorentini nel territorio di Norcia*, in *Rivista d'Arte*, Florence, 1959, Vol. XXXIV, p. 112), it possibly contained a donation in favor of the people of Abeto and Todiano, even though Fabbi mistakingly writes that «during the eighteenth century the Grand Duke, as a reward for the help given in Florence by the people originating from Abeto and Todiano as to the plague in town, donated to the University or Guild of the porters of the Customs some buildings at Via San Gallo, so that they could establish the 'Opera Pia'

of St. John the Beheaded»: a great confusion with events that happened in actual reality during the fourteenth century (the plague in Florence, the building at Via San Gallo, the establishment of a guild dedicated to St. John the Beheaded).

Thus, in late-nineteenth-century Abeto and Todiano there existed a local charitable association which proudly stated its own illustrious lineage from the 'Norcini' porters in Florence, whose guild had been abolished by the Tuscan government a century earlier.

According to the Charters dating to 1886, the scope of the association was «to support the poor born in Abeto and Todiano through the available income, by doing the following: 1) supply a dowry for two unmarried women [...] originating from the two hamlets [...]; 2) establish two schools for small children in the two hamlets; 3) provide subsidies to poor who are unable to work and ill people, both at their own house and in the hospital; 4) fund civil works to the benefit of the community and the improvement of roads» (in Italian, «sovvenire con le proprie rendite la classe povera per i naturali ed originali di Abeto e Todiano provvedendo: 1) a una dotazione a due zitelle povere [...] originali delle due frazioni [...]; 2) all'impianto di due scuole-asilo nelle due frazioni; 3) a sussidi ai poveri inabili al lavoro e infermi poveri, sia a domicilio che ricoverati in ospedale; 4) a sovvenzionare opere di pubblica utilità e di viabilità»).

But in the twentieth century there was no more space nor scope for the 'Opere Pie', the local charitable associations now totally superseded by public medical and assistance services. So the 'Opera Pia di San Giovanni Decollato in Abeto e Todiano' just followed the same destiny of its ancient predecessor in Florence: it was abolished, too, in 1982, because it was not operational anymore.

Nonetheless, the thin line which connected fourteenth-century Florence and today's Valle Castoriana, in the land of Norcia, was unbreakable. And it will remain visible, still in our contemporary age, in an unexpected domain: visual art and ancient Italian paintings, as we will show in the next paragraph.

Fig. 56 - Abeto (above) and Todiano (below) as they appear today

4.4 From Florence to Norcia, the amazing journey of Renaissance art

Researchers have long noted the incongruous presence of works of arts from Tuscany «in the so-called 'Tuscan island', the mountainous area sitting between Spolegium and L'Aquila, where once were the borders between the ancient Duchy of Spolegium and the Kingdom of Naples, and where until not many years ago many paintings on wooden tables dating to the fifteenth and sixteenth century could be seen, and also wooden statues made by masters from Florence» (Elvio Lunghi, *Scambi reciproci tra i pittori nelle terre di confine: alcuni esempi*, in *Le dinamiche del confine fra Romagna, Toscana e Umbria - Società locali, circolazione di uomini e merci, scambi culturali (secoli XIII-XVI)*, Documenti e Studi della Deputazione di Storia Patria per le Province di Romagna, Vol. XLIV, Bologna, 2022, p. 239).

What was happening in the land of Norcia? Why masterworks created by painters and sculptors in Florence had been transferred to this remote area, so as they are still present in isolated churches and local museums?

Because, as Lunghi notes, in this territory we can detect «the apparently-inexplicable presence, in a land that used to have strong links with Rome, of a number of works painted by Florentine masters — Matteo Rosselli, Jacopo Confortini, Matteo Bonechi — tra Abeto, Poggio di Croce and Todiano»; and two other scholars, Giorgio Falcidia and Bruno Toscano, in their article *Attività artistica, storia del territorio*, in *Pittura del Seicento e del Settecento: Ricerche in Umbria*, Vol. 1 (Treviso, 1976, p. 34), wrote that it could be found «in Abeto works by the 'Master of the Madonna Straus', Nero di Bicci, Piero di Cosimo; in Todiano, by Filippino Lippi; in Preci, by Mariotti di Cristofano; in Ancarano [between Norcia and Preci, editor's note] a statue by Simone Ferrucci».

Abeto, Todiano, Poggio di Croce, Preci, Ancarano: the very area from which the ancient Guild of the Porters of St. John the Beheaded of Norcia, established in Florence in the fourteenth century, was from; and also the area of origin of the Precian surgeons, who were in Florence, too, starting from the very same period.

It is clear, as correctly remarked by Falcidia and Toscano, that «the origin of this occurrence was not to be retraced in the personal taste of some affluent patrons: instead, it was the effect of a centuries-long, established

economical relationship that the capital town of Tuscany had in place with extended local communities in this area».

As we already know, Elvio Lunghi notes that «all this happened because there were seasonal workers who relinquished the mountainous hamlet of the Valnerina, where the snow covered everything and all activities were on hold, and moved to Florence in search of a job as porters at the customs». And — we add — there were also butchers and surgeons from Norcia and Preci who established their residence there permanently, earning a considerable wealth in the Tuscan town.

So what happened with those works of art? Lunghi provides a reasonable answer, shedding light on the whole issue: «When they needed a painting or a statue for the churches of their native villages, it is in Florence that those temporary migrants made their purchases, maybe even picking less-innovative, more-traditional works, which better fitted the taste of those parishes lost amid the mountains. As a matter of fact we are in front of the activities carried out by one or more local brotherhoods, that is religious associations whose members were the villages' residents, which, when purchasing a sacred image, did not turn to a painter from Spolegium or Norcia, and took advantage of their temporary stay in Florence».

Again, it is not a matter of temporary workers only, because we saw that in fourteenth-century Florence there were permanent residents from Norcia who were able to invest much more money than a mere porter in art commissions.

So, that is the reason for the presence, in the small hamlet of Todiano, of a masterwork called *Our Lady of Mercy* ('*Madonna della Mercede*' in Italian), by Filippino Lippi, who lived in Florence in the second half of the fifteenth century. His tempera on table, which represents a charming Mary breastfeeding the Child, sided by St. Montano and St. Bartholomew, was once preserved at the tiny Church of St. Montano, lying just outside the village, then moved to the local parish church dedicated to St. Bartholomew, and stored today at the Diocesan Museum in Spolegium.

Fig. 57 - Flippino Lippi's *Our Lady of the Mercy with St. Montano and St. Bartholomew* (tempera on table, around 1485), preserved at the Diocesan Museum of Spolegium

And this is also the reason for the presence, in Abeto, of another masterpiece made by a painter from Florence who lived between the fourteenth century and the fifteenth, the so-called 'Master of Our Lady Straus' (in Italian, 'Maestro della Madonna Straus'). His imposing altarpiece, including three wooden panels now preserved at the Diocesan Museum of Spolegium and the Vatican Museums, was once located at the Church of Santa Maria and then at the Church of San Martino, both in Abeto. The central panel shows Our Lady enthroned with the Child and two angels, while the two lateral panels present Santa Paola Romana and her daughter St. Julia Eustochium.

Fig. 58 - Central panel of the *Tryptich of the Master of Our Lady Straus* (end of fourteenth / beginning of fifteenth century), preserved at the Diocesan Museum of Spolegium

Fig. 59 - Lateral panels of the *Tryptich of the Master of Our Lady Straus*, (end of fourteenth / beginning of fifteenth century), preserved at the Vatican Museums

And that's also the reason for the presence, in Poggio di Croce (a small Castel from which various Precian surgeons were born), of a gorgeous work by Giovanni del Biondo, a painter active in Florence in the second half of the fourteenth century, dating to around 1385, proudly preserved, still today, in the small Church of Santa Maria Annunziata: the *Annunciation of Our Lady*, a superior masterwork of tenderness and elegance.

Fig. 60 - Giovanni del Biondo's *Annunciation of Our Lady* (around 1385), preserved at the Church of Santa Maria Annunziata, Poggio di Croce (Preci)

Abeto, Todiano, Poggio di Croce and Florence. The Valle Castoriana and the neighboring, secluded valleys, in the land of Norcia, and Tuscany. A close relationship made of men, travels, jobs, religious piety and magnificent works of art.

It is a beautiful story. Nonetheless, the legacy of all this will not be as nice as we might imagine. Eventually, the memory of the role of the 'Norcini'

porters in the local economy of Florence got lost; the hospital in the central district was utterly forgotten; the Precian surgeons' proficiency totally vanished amid the mists of the history of medicine.

And the only recollection still remaining in Florence about those ancient people from Norcia who had been living there for centuries will be quite depreciative, if not totally derogative.

They will be just remembered as the 'mare mules of Norcia' (le 'mule norcine'). As we will see in the next paragraph.

4.5 Derogative descriptions of the 'Norcini' as porters

We are in Florence, as early as the second decade of the fourteenth century. And people from Norcia use to annually reach the Tuscan town to work in the sector of pork meat processing. They also use to carry out heavy tasks on demand, carrying burdens and loads (including the carcasses of pigs) around the city, as an additional source of income. In Italian, they are called 'facchini', or porters. In the wake of this initial, low-skilled migration flow, a number of surgeons from Preci starts to be known and appreciated in Florence, so that an additional community of proficient people from Norcia begins to settle in town, too. This close, centuries-long relationship will bring a series of works of art from Florence to the area of Preci: magnificent paintings which are still found, today, in those remote valleys laying in the territory of Norcia.

But, if we just move to the late seventeenth century, we find that, in the mind of the people in Florence, the 'Norcini' are just considered, and remembered, as filthy, almost disreputable workers, performing dirty jobs around the streets of their illustrious, shining Tuscan town.

Here is how the 'Norcini' are presented in a mock-heroic epic poem, *Il Malmantile racquistato*, a satirical work written in Florence by Perlone Zipoli (a fictitious name for Lorenzo Lippi, a painter and a poet) during the second half of the seventeenth century. His verses, full of incomprehensible references to Florence, its districts, its people, its dialect, are so hard to

understand that a subsequent edition was published accompanied by a huge number of explanatory footnotes.

Lorenzo Lippi, a true, shrewd inhabitant of Florence, did not spare the 'Norcini' from his biting wits, when he mentions them in Chapter VI, Stanza 61 of his poem, while describing a vision of a sinner sentenced to Hell:

«[A devil] Thrusts him down by a push
In certain waters so black and loathsome,
That he emerges again, in a way that jars look much cleaner
Or even dirtier than a 'Norcino', mare mule of swines».

[In the original Italian text: «...[Un diavol]
Con una spinta a basso poi lo getta
In cert'acque bituminose e lorde,
Ch'e' n'esce poi, ch'io ne disgrado gli orci,
O peggio d'un Norcin, mula de' porci»].

61. Un'altro ad un balcon balla e corvetta,
Che un diavol colla sferza a cento corde,
Che un grand'occhio di bue cialcuna ha in vetta,
Prima gli dà certe picchiate forde:
Con una spinta a basso poi lo getta
In cert'acque bituminose e lorde,
Ch' e' n' esce poi, ch'io ne disgrado gli orci,
O peggio d'un Norcin, mula de' porci.

Fig. 61 - 'Norcini' as quoted by Lorenzo Lippi in his *Il Malmantile racquistato* (edition printed in Venice in 1748), Chapter 6, Stanza 61, p. 469

Why does Lorenzo Lippi from Florence write such a derogatory remark on the 'Norcini', here considered as foul and revolting men?

The striking explanation is provided in the accompanying footnote edited by Paolo Minucci, a man of letters and Lippi's close friend:

«'NORCINO', MARE MULE OF SWINES. Those are the people who, in Florence, kill the pigs and, when dead, carry them over their very shoulders to the butchers' shops; they are mainly from the town of Norcia, so they are called 'Mare mules of Norcia', meaning 'Porters of Norcia'; and they are always covered with pig's grease, utterly filthy and disgustingly stained with blood».

[In the original Italian text: «NORCIN, MULA DE' PORCI. Coloro, che in Firenze ammazzano i porci, e così morti gli portano sopr'alle spalle alle botteghe de' macellari, sono per lo più del paese di Norcia, e però gli chiama *Mule Norcine*, cioè *Portatori da Norcia*: e costoro son sempre tutti unti di grasso di porco, lordissimi e schifi di sangue»].

NORCIN, MULA DE' PORCI. Coloro, che in Firenze ammazzano i porci, e così morti gli portano sopr' alle spalle alle botteghe de' macellari, sono per lo più del paese di Norcia, e però gli chiama *Mule Norcine*, cioè *Portatori da Norcia*: e costoro son sempre tutti unti di grasso di porco, lordissimi e schifi di sangue. *Min.*

Fig. 62 - Footnote on the 'Norcini' in Lorenzo Lippi's *Il Malmantile racquistato* (edition printed in Venice in 1748), Chapter 6, Stanza 61, p. 470

Even though Lorenzo Lippi is certainly a good representative of a typical habit of the supercilious inhabitants of the aristocratic town of Florence of looking at other people with scorn and a caustic sense of humor (as it still occurs in our present days), his disdain for the 'Norcini' appears to be truly excessive; however, Norcia was just a small town lost amid the Apennines, and possibly Lippi never experienced the pain caused by a stone in the bladder or the blindness arising from eye cataracts, otherwise his

perception of the 'Norcini' and Precians would certainly have been different.

But that was the reality in Florence: the 'Norcini' were just poor immigrants, performing their filthy jobs, so no consideration was due to them in the mindset of the haughty people of the elegant Tuscan town.

And here is how the 'Norcini' appeared while carrying their disgusting burden in the streets. This image is drawn from *Di Bologna le arti per via* (*The arts in the streets of Bologna*), a collection of drawings published by Giuseppe Maria Mitelli in 1660: the image refers to a porter (not specifically from Norcia) working in Bologna, but his aspect and attitude, his face and body concealed under the loathsome weight of a slaughtered pig, are certainly the same of our 'facchini' from Norcia who used to unsteadily tread, in such an attire, the noble streets of Florence.

Fig. 63 - The porter of carcasses of swines, from Giuseppe Maria Mitelli's *Di Bologna l'arti per via* (Rome, 1660), Tab. XXVIII

And the contempt for this poor worker is so tangible that Mitelli does not omit to include, at the bottom of his drawing, a few merry lines, which play

with illustrious reminiscences of Hercules, the hero who carried the carcass of the defeated Nemean lion over his shoulders, and Adonis, who according to myth was killed by a wild boar:

«Victorious Hercules brought on his powerful body
the corpse of the nasty lion, now killed.
I myself, by carrying a dead swine over my shoulders,
intend to vindicate the murderer of Adonis».

[In the original Italian text:
«Trionfò su l'gran fianco Ercole avvinto
Lo spoglio de l'ucciso empio leone.
Io, portando su l'dorso un porco estinto,
Vuò trionfar de l'uccisor d'Adone»].

Such were the porters from Norcia in Florence: the object of scorn and derision; nonetheless, their story is brave and illustrious, and we diverted our narrative from our main Roman path because we felt the need to recognize and celebrate this Tuscan branch of the historical migration from Norcia.

But it's now time, for us, to turn from Florence to Rome. Because the fifteenth century is about to begin, and the presence of the 'Norcini', in the town of the Popes, is gaining momentum in the wake of a new period of growth and development being experienced by the capital of the Papal States.

So let's shift again to the main focus of our essay: the historical presence of the 'Norcini' in the former capital of an Empire. Let's move to Rome, and meet the 'Norcini' there. In the fifteenth century.

5. Rome, a capital town and a market for the Papal States

5.1 Rome rebuilt: the fifteenth-century evolving scenario and the need for food

What was happening in Rome in the fifteenth century? To understand how things were going, let's start from a century earlier.

In the previous century, the fourteenth, Rome had been enduring a number of distressing hardships: the transfer of the papacy to the French town of Avignon (1309 - 1377) had impoverished the city; further disarray was caused by the subsequent Western Schism (1378 - 1417), with competing, conflicting Popes sitting at the same time in Rome and Avignon; the prolonged struggle between the people and the local aristocratic families, with the attempt effected by Cola di Rienzo to establish a popular government in town, had originated decades of conflicts and turmoil; finally, the Black Death pandemic hit Italy and Rome in 1348, demanding its appalling toll of lives.

When humanist Pier Paolo Vergerio arrived in Rome in 1398, he reported in a letter the poor, miserable conditions of the former capital of an empire: «The portion of the town lying on the hills is deserted; the lower part and that near the river [Tiber] is inhabited, and on the large foundations of the ancient collapsed buildings now stand the new, flimsy houses» («Pars montana deserta est; plana tamen et quae est ad flumen proxima colitur, ubi collapsis veteribus aedificiis novae nunc ac fragiles casae grandibus insident fundamentis») — from L. Smith, *Epistolario di Pier Paolo Vergerio in Fonti per la storia d'Italia*, no. 74, 1934, p. 217).

At that time the attractiveness of Rome, in terms of availability of higher-level careers (i.e. open positions in the papal administration), and chances to earn a living in the town by selling goods or finding any sort of job, were markedly scarce. Population was reduced to a few tenths of thousands people. It is a period in which immigration was limited, and we have no documented references concerning the settlement in Rome of immigrants coming from Norcia.

As we saw in the preceding chapter, the situation in Florence was utterly different: a primary European manufacturing center for the 'pannilana', a

mighty financial system, the Tuscan town, in that same fourteenth century, was flourishing and thriving with life and businesses; so much so that a significant migration from Norcia was already there, with its porters and its Precian surgeons.

Things in Rome began to change with the advent of Pope Martin V in 1417. He promoted the restoration of the institutions, monuments and artistic life of Rome, following more than a century of decline. The town was now back on track, with a Jubilee being celebrated on 1423 and the launch of a number of large construction works, at the Lateran and in the area of the Vatican.

Now Rome is again a destination of choice for pilgrims and artists. A new influx of money is generated by the incoming visitors and the rearrangement of the fiscal policies and revenues originated by the Italian territories subject to the Pope.

Renaissance in Rome had just begun, and it will continue with enlightened, learned Popes like Eugene IV, Nicholas V, Pius II, and others.

Fig. 64 - A vista of fifteenth-century Rome, from Hartmann Schedel's *Liber Chronicarum*, or *Nuremberg Chronicle* (Nuremberg, 1493), folium LVIII

Here is Rome in the fifteenth century: a town that is emerging from a long period of decline, and is now entering a new phase of growth, increase in population and considerable wealth for many families having

responsibilities in the government of the Church and in the public administration.

This is the town to which people from Norcia, according our assumption, began to migrate in search of new job opportunities, or even — for the members of wealthy families — as the result of an appointment to a distinguished position within the papal administration in the capital city.

Before dealing with the characteristics of this migration process, let's try to illuminate the peculiar features and aspects that marked fifteenth- and sixteenth-century Rome, in terms of society, population and food supplies. We will find that all such aspects will present close connections with the quality and nature of the presence of the 'Norcini' in Rome.

5.2 The critical management of food supplies in fifteenth-century Rome

The supplies of food for the growing town were turning into a critical issue for the Popes, a «primary requirement linked to reasons of general politics, if not of public security»: in this framework, during the fifteenth century measures were established «to funnel the whole agricultural production [towards Rome] so as to meet the demand for food of the Roman population» by «putting in place significant assets and energies to channel in the direction of Rome food products purchased in various territories of Italy» (P. Brezzi, *Il sistema agrario nel territorio romano alla fine del Medio Evo*, in *Studi Romani*, XXV, 2, Rome, 1977, p. 153-154).

Because Rome was hungry. And the populace wanted food.

During the fifteenth century, the stability of the supplies was often under strain: «hence the repeated shortages and endless complaints raised by the people with a perpetual threat of uprising» (C. De Cupis, *Le vicende dell'agricoltura e della pastorizia nell'Agro Romano — L'Annona di Roma*, Rome, 1911, p. 92), and with the generation of «political and military unrest which, ensuing from the Pope's temporary absence from the capital city and owing to the weakness of the central administration, made it difficult to ensure the supply of foodstuff» (P. Brezzi, p. 154). Throughout

the century repeated episodes of famine hit the town, and specifically its weaker, more destitute residents (P. Brezzi, p. 154 and 160).

A main problem was that the Roman Campagna — the extended plain lying near Rome, for centuries the property of barons belonging to aristocratic families that had been increasing their power and wealth during the Middle Ages — was now undergoing a general process of «decrease in population and transformation into grazing fields for cattle» (P. Brezzi, p. 157). The Campagna was now in a state of «total dereliction [...] with the last remnants of agricultural care having gone lost [...] with a general desertion of farmers which caused the sterility of the soil, once so fertile and productive» (C. De Cupis, p. 91).

The issue was so critical that on March 1, 1476 Pope Sixtus IV issued a bulla (*Inducit nos humanitatis*) in which he noted that «too often the neighboring land set in the vicinity of our mother city produces only scarce grain and fodder [...] as the cultivable lands] are left fallow and used as grazing areas for animals» (in the original Latin text: «omnis regio nostre alme Urbi finitima frequenter habuit steriles frumenti et bladorum proventus [...] potius sinuntur incolti ut sint in pascua animalibus brutis»). In the bulla, the Pope granted farmers the right to plough and cultivate portions of the fields even though they belonged to private landlords and ecclesiastical institutions.

The opposition by the barons to this sort of decrees was, of course, strenuous. That meant that eventually the Popes could only «ascertain that it was impossible to supply food to Rome by counting on the products that used to come from the neighbouring countryside, and they were forced to address other provinces of the Papal States, especially the Patrimony of Saint Peter, the Marches and the Romagna», especially for grain (P. Brezzi, p. 155).

Across the centuries, the critical issue concerning the funnelling of food from the various provinces of the Papal States towards Rome was solved by the Popes through the enforcement of a strictly-regulated supply chain.

CODEX DIPLOMATICUS
DOMINII TEMPORALIS S. SEDIS.

RECUEIL DE DOCUMENTS

POUR SERVIR À L'HISTOIRE DU GOUVERNEMENT TEMPOREL

DES ÉTATS DU SAINT-SIÈGE

EXTRAITS DES ARCHIVES DU VATICAN

AUGUSTIN THEINER

PRIEUR DE L'ORATOIRE, PRÉVÔT DES ARCHIVES SÉCRÈTES DU VATICAN, ETC., ETC.

TOME TROISIÈME

1389—1793.

ROME

IMPRIMERIE DU VATICAN

1862.

CCCCXIV.

Bulla, qua conceditur, ut ad frumentum uberius comparandum omnibus sub certis conditionibus liceat agros etiam alienos arare et colere in districtu Urbis, quamvis ab eorum dominis licentiam non obtinuerint etc.

Bull. divers. cod. membran. fol. 145.

SIXTUS EPISCOPUS etc. Ad perpetuam rei memoriam. Inducit nos humanitatis cum omnibus ho-

62*

492

SIXTUS PP. IV. A1

minibus communicatio, ut omnium consiliorum ea ducamus potiora et pre ceteris capiamus, que sustentationi et victui hominum magis conducere videantur. Ideo attendentes, quod a pluribus annis citra omnis regio nostre alme Urbi finitima frequenter habuit steriles frumenti et bladorum proventus cum gravi populorum in ea degentium iactura et afflictione, considerantesque id preter et ultra celi naturalem cursum et dispositionem patissime etiam provenire ex raritate culture agrorum, qui propter aliquam forte maiorem utilitatem inde provenientem eorum dn̄is potius sinuntur inculti, ut sint in pascua animalibus brutis, quam colantur aut coli sinantur in alimentum et sustentationem hominum, et volentes, prout n̄o incumbit officio, tanto errori obviare ac predictis populis, quorum incommodo paterna nos caritas commonet et sollicitat, de opportuno remedio providere, auctoritate apostolica harum serie statuimus et ordinamus, quod deinceps perpetuis futuris temporibus liceat omnibus et singulis agros arare et colere volentibus in predictae nostre Urbis territorio, et Patrimonii beati Petri in Tuscia ac Campanie et Maritimae provinciis rumpere et arare ac colere, alias debitis et consue-

Fig. 65 - Sixtus IV's bulla *Inducit nos humanitatis*, from *Codex Diplomaticus Domini Temporalis S. Sedis*, edited by Augustin Theiner, Vol. III, Rome, 1862), CCCCXIV, p. 491 and 492

As to grain, since the middle of the fifteenth century the office of the 'Annona' was in charge to «direct to the Roman market the food commodities purchased across different areas of Italy, with the arrangement of a centralised system of provision and distribution of grain at controlled prices» (P. Brezzi, p. 154). This implied that «the export of food from Rome was forbidden [...]; the quantity of grain produced was to be communicated to the authority; the whole production, apart from what was needed for local consumption, was to be transferred to Rome; grain was to be distributed to bakers at regulated prices» (P. Brezzi, p. 155).

A similar approach was applied to the supply process of meat, lard and oil. From that same fifteenth century, the 'Dogana della Grascia' controlled the whole chain: «at the grazing lands an initial, quantitative selection of the cattle was carried out through an enforced requisition of the animals to be

destined to the city's food market. During the transfer to the market of Rome and its slaughterhouses, the cattle was protected by specific privileges [... with the] exemption from custom fees [...]. Once in town, the cattle was brought at the Foro Boario, used as a market. There the animals were sold to butchers and subject to taxation» (Marina D'Amelia, *La crisi di un mercato protetto: approvvigionamenti e consumo della carne a Roma nel XVIII secolo*, in *Mélanges de l'Ecole française de Rome. Moyen-Age, Temps modernes*, Vol. 87, no. 2, 1975, p. 496).

So the stability of food supplies, in the fifteenth-century, was an issue that the Papal government was forced to tackle by enforcing strict regulations and procedures.

And what about pigs and pork meat? How could the 'Dogana della Grascia' cope with the issues concerning the supply of this specific sort of food? Were there enough pigs in Rome to satisfy the local demand? Or, could the Campagna Romana be a convenient source for such animals?

The answer to both questions was no. As we will see in the next paragraph.

5.3 Pig supplies in fifteenth-century Rome

So what about domesticated pigs, to be used as food supply? They were an important element, among many others, in the process of granting the provision of sustenance to the capital city. They were fully subject to the process controlled by the 'Dogana della Grascia' starting from the fifteenth century, but we find in the sources indications of their importance already a century earlier.

In the *Liber Statutorum Urbis*, the Charters of the city of Rome, dating back to 1363, a specific provision, relating to the food that must not be distracted from the general supplies (*De grascia non extrahenda* — CXLVII,) states that «pigs [...] cannot be led out through the Customs from this district [of Rome]» («porci vero et castrati cum dohana extrahi de dicto districtu [Urbis] non possint»). They were too important, just as all the food that already was in the city, and for no reason they were to be taken away, beyond the borders of the urban district. They were so important that, in the

same provision, it is recommended that «all Senators, when taking on their position, shall make a public announcement in Rome that anybody who owns pigs [...] must have them registered at the House of Capitolium within a specific term» («quilibet Senator in principio sui regiminis bandiri facere per Urbem quod omnes habentes castratos vel porcos teneantur illos facere scribi in Camera Urbis infra terminum», in Latin).

Fig. 66 - Provision CXLVII on pigs from Book II of the *Liber Statutorum Urbis* (manuscript Cred. XV, t. 45 preserved in the Archive of the Camera Capitolina, Rome, copy dating to around 1430 of the original fourteenth-century Charters), folia 29, 49 and 50

Pigs were brought to Rome from the territories of the Papal States under the control of the 'Grascia'; nonetheless, there was a certain number of pigs in Rome itself, as we can read in the description of a curious occurrence reported by Antonio di Pietro dello Schiavo, a fifteenth-century, middle-class inhabitant of Rome who wrote a diary full of news and events, including the following incident occurred during the military confrontation between Pope Alexander V and King Ladislaus of Naples:

«Saturday 16 of the said month [November 1409] A butcher of the district of Parione [in Rome] [...had?] a hundred pigs; the said butcher, after having released the pigs, said to his companions or relatives: 'let them drink'; and so they let them immediately. When the pigs reached the river [Tiber], one of the pigs entered the waters, and all the remaining pigs followed it; the whole herd drifted towards Castel Sant'Angelo, so in the end they were all seized by those who were inside the castle».

[In the original Latin text: «Die Sabbati 16. dicti mensis [...] Macellarius de Regione Parionis centum porcos, qui dicti porci post solutionem dixit

dictus Macellarius suis sociis vel familiaribus: 'Fate abeverare questi porci'; et ita fuit factum statim. Quando fuerunt prope flumen unus intravit flumen, et omnes alii fuerunt secuti dictum porcum, et omnes iverunt versus Castrum Sancti Angeli, et sic illi de Castro Sancti Angeli capuerunt dictos porcos»].

Fig. 67 - The episode of the pigs reported by Antonio di Pietro dello Schiavo in his *Diarium romanum*, from Ludovico Antonio Muratori's *Rerum italicarum scriptores*, Vol. XXIV (Milan, 1738) p. 1008

And, in addition to that, there was a specific provision in the *Liber Statutorum Urbis* to prevent pigs from going around in the streets of Rome:

«Of leading pigs by the hand — All inhabitants of Rome must keep pigs by the hand [...] pigs must be retained in fenced areas so that they don't go unrestrained through the city...».

[In the original Latin text: «De retinentibus porcum ad manus — Quicumque cuius romanus retinuerit aliquem porcum ad manum [...] retineat ipsum porcum et retinere debeat reclusum sic que per urbem non vadat...»].

Fig. 68 - Provision CCXXV on pigs from Book II of the *Liber Statutorum Urbis* (manuscript Cred. XV, t. 45 preserved in the Archive of the Camera Capitolina, Rome, copy dating to around 1430 of the original fourteenth-century Charters), f55v

So there were pigs in Rome, but the fundamental supply was provided from the outside through the process managed by the 'Dogana della Grascia'.

But where did the 'Grascia' take those pigs from? Did the nearby Roman Campagna offer, in the fifteenth century, enough pigs to ensure a convenient supply of pork meat to the people of Rome?

Not at all. Domesticated pigs — a species that does not migrate seasonally, as sheep instead used to do during the annual transhumance — were mainly raised at the local productive units typical of the Roman Campagna: the farmsteads (in Italian: 'casali'), with their rural buildings and the adjoining land. But the fifteenth-century 'casali' were undergoing a heavy decline, which accompanied the general process of abandonment which was marking the whole Campagna: farmers tended to leave the fields to settle in Rome or in hamlets on the nearby hilltops, because «the presence of malaria and the brutality of brigands and barons did not encourage a business that was proving to be unfruitful» (P. Brezzi, p. 161-162).

Actually, the veritably fruitful business was nomadic pastoralism, from lowlands to highlands in summer and vice versa in winter: «In the course of the fifteenth century, raising and herding of livestock became the main economic activity carried out in the Campagna Romana [... in the presence of a concurrent] depopulation of the land and its transformation into grazing grounds». And many shepherds used to come «from the Apennine regions, and passed the winter in the plains [of the Roman Campagna]; afterwards they came back to their mountains, heading to the summer grazing grounds» (P. Brezzi, p. 161-163).

That was the situation of Rome in the fifteenth century: an increasing population; emerging social groups marked by an expanding wealth and

more demanding food requirements; a difficult, heavily-regulated management of food supplies; the absence of grain production in the neighboring Roman Campagna, mainly devoted to the pasture of transhumant cattle; limited raising of domestic animals at farmsteads, which were undergoing a growing crisis and an extending deprivation. And there were no enough pigs, in Rome and in the adjacent territories, to meet the demand of Rome for pork meat.

So the city had to address other, differentiated sources with the aim of purchasing the food that its hungry inhabitants needed on a day-by-day basis.

And — as to pigs, pork meat and salted sausages — Norcia was there to satisfy their demand.

Norcia and its extensive pig raising activities. Norcia and its salted pork meat. Norcia, not far from Rome.

So we think that all the gears were now in place. A professional market supply was about to meet a compelling market demand. Norcia was about to meet Rome. Already in the fifteenth century — specifically, in the second half of it.

But how was the food trade arranged in Rome? What sort of economical structure was in place in the capital city of the Papal States? And how could the new immigrants from Norcia insinuate in an existing market, where a number of players were already positioned and fully operational?

Let's have a look at the mixed population and complex, regulated structure of the market of food, goods and services in late-medieval and early-modern Rome. And we will understand how the 'Norcini' succeeded in entering the specific trade segment concerning pigs and salted pork meat in Rome.

5.4 The multifaceted population of Rome: the national brotherhoods

We must now briefly pause to consider the truly peculiar nature of the society of Rome as it was emerging from the Middle Ages.

What was Rome during those centuries?

To begin with, the town — featuring 50.000 residents in the sixteenth century, rapidly growing to 100.000 before the end of the same century — was a particular pole of attraction, owing to its unique role as the focal point of the whole Christianity. And this attraction did not concern only pilgrims, who were coming and going on a temporary basis; it also had important effects on the social, ethnic and cultural composition of the people who permanently lived in Rome.

As effectively noted by Antonio Martini in his essay *Arts, crafts and faith in papal Rome (Arti mestieri e fede nella Roma dei Papi*, Bologna, 1965, p. 38), «the universality of the catholic Church attracted towards Rome, in the Middle Ages too, several foreigners, who arrived in the city for different reasons, namely spiritual and even political or commercial. This uninterrupted inflow fostered the incorporation into the urban population of some of those foreigners, who, decade after decade, built up their own colonies coalesced by the ties originating from their common homelands».

So as people from other Italian towns or even foreign countries gathered in Rome to reside in the capital city of the Papal States, they tended to associate in brotherhoods marked by a common origin. This peculiar process conferred to the Roman society — marked by the presence of a Pope with absolute powers and dominant aristocratic families, the barons — a peculiarly loose, disjoint character, featuring many different social groups that did not use to work together to pursue any common goal, be it political or economical (A. Martini, p. 38):

«An effect of the blend of nationalities was the lack of cohesion amid the active population: certainly the very different origins did not foster the establishment of a common feeling, a requirement for the formation of a popular body with political aspirations».

That's why in Rome a number of brotherhoods appeared between the sixteenth and seventeenth century, bringing together people who lived in town for the most diverse reasons, but all sharing the same origin, be it from an Italian town or a European country: Florentines, Frenchmen, Portugueses, Germans, people from Siena, Genoa, Naples, the Marches, and then Spain, Sicily and many others set up their own associations, as it is effectively displayed in a seventeenth-century book written by Carlo Bartolomeo Piazza.

TRATTATO VIII.
Delle Confraternite Nazionali.

D i S. Giovanni de' Fiorentini, detta della Pietà.	Cap. 1.
Di s. Luigi, de' Francesi.	Cap. 2.
Di s. Antonio, de' Portoghesi.	Cap. 3.
Di s. Girolamo, de' Schiauoni.	Cap. 4.
Dell' Anima, de' Teutonici.	Cap. 5.
Di s. Caterina, de' Senesi.	Cap. 6.
De' Ss. Bartolomeo, & Aleffandro, de' Bergamaschi.	Cap. 7.
Di s. Gio: Battista, de' Genovesi.	Cap. 8.
Dello Spirito Santo, de' Napolitani.	Cap. 9.
Di s. Giovanni Euangelista, de' Bolognesi.	Cap. 10.
Della Santa Casa, de' Marcheggiani.	Cap. 11.
De' Ss. Faostino, e Giouita, de' Bresciani.	Cap. 12.
Della Resurrezzione, de' Spagnuoli.	Cap. 13.
Della Madonna di Costantinopoli; de' Siciliani, e Maltesi.	Cap. 14.
Di s. Venanzio, de' Camerinesi.	Cap. 15.
Della Madonna di Monferrato; de' gli Aragonesi, Maiorchini &c.	Cap. 16.
Di s. Caterina, e Nicolò; de' Lorenesi.	Cap. 17.
Di Santa Croce, de' Lucchesi.	Cap. 18.
Della Purificazione; de' Tranfalpini.	Cap. 19.
* Delle Santissime Spine; de' Calciani.	Cap. 20.
Di Sant' Iuo; de' Brittoni.	Cap. 21.

Fig. 69 - The national brotherhoods in Rome as listed by Carlo Bartolomeo Piazza in his *Eusevologio romano delle Opere Pie di Roma* (Rome, 1698), p. XXVIII

What was the scope of brotherhoods? They gathered all the people who lived in Rome and shared a same origin, often belonging to illustrious, wealthy families; they raised the money which was needed to build their new churches, which will become the place where to meet and celebrate the Christian festivities and the day of their patron saint; they helped each other, and especially their fellow-countrymen in need, also providing with a dowry the poor girls of their nation living in poverty in Rome. They assisted, too, the pilgrims coming to Rome from their hometown or home

country, arranging their stay in the town at national hostels; in some cases, they even ran hospitals, to be intended as places where the poor and the ill were piously helped, fed and accommodated.

But it was not only a matter of charity. Each brotherhood had its own patron at the papal court, most often a high-rank prelate or even a Cardinal. They celebrated their own power and influence each year, often by a public procession moving along the streets of downtown Rome, with a full display of torches and standards, all the brothers clothed in their robes that recalled the tunics used by monks and friars.

We will see that the people from Norcia will set up their own brotherhood, too, thus marking the relevance of their presence in the town of the Popes.

However, brotherhoods are not the only social arrangement we find in Rome from the fifteenth century onwards. In town there is a further grouping, with a much stronger economical influence, and a regulated control on the trade of all sorts of goods, including food.

These are the Universities of arts and crafts, or Guilds. Let's go and meet them, before we address the issue of how the 'Norcini' could effectively penetrate into this complex, variegated scenario.

5.5 The Roman guilds and the regulation of trade in town

We must now consider a further aggregation process that marked Rome during the late-medieval and early-modern period.

As we saw earlier, the population of Rome was the result of an incessant motion of people coming and going to and from the city, for religious, political and artistic reasons, especially starting from the fifteenth century, when the Popes began to restore the magnificence of Rome following a long period of conflicts and disruption.

In this framework, the economy of Rome was mainly devoted to the service of the large numbers of people who visited the city, be they pilgrims, members of diplomatic missions or workers employed in the large

construction activities being carried out in town: «the incoming and outcoming foreigners fostered the development of specific businesses, including managers of hotels and taverns, bakers, shoemakers, physicians, barbers, etc., who granted accommodation and comfort for the travellers» (A. Martini, p. 38). So the vast majority of the economic activities were connected to the import and distribution of goods, and the delivery of services, to local clients and customers, with no export activities outside the walls of Rome (we must also remember, as effectively noted by A. Martini, that there was a «lack of markets in the neighborhood, because, as it is known, at that time Rome was isolated from the rest of Italy owing to the presence of the unhealthy expanse of the Roman Campagna» — p. 38).

A non-exhaustive list of arts and crafts that were active in seventeenth-century Rome is given by Carlo Bartolomeo Piazza in his book *Eusevologio romano delle Opere Pie di Roma*: from bakers to painters, from shoemakers to coachmen, from blacksmiths to stonecutters, the fascination of papal Rome lives again in the many crafts that contributed, across the centuries, to the picturesque splendour of this magnificent city.

TRATTATO IX.		
<i>Delle Confraternità dell'Arti.</i>		
D ella Madonna di Loreto; de' Fornari.	Cap. 1.	
De' Cuochi.	Cap. 2.	
De' Mercanti, & Artegiani.	Cap. 3.	
De' Barbieri, e Stufaroli.	Cap. 4.	
De' Sartori, e Calzettari.	Cap. 5.	
De' Calzolari.	Cap. 6.	
Di s. Elisabetta; de' Fornari.	Cap. 7.	
De' Speciali.	Cap. 8.	
Di s. Luca; de' Pittori.	Cap. 9.	
	De'	
		XXIX
De' Parafrancieri.		Cap. 10.
De' Muratori.		Cap. 11.
De' Sellari.		Cap. 12.
De' gli Orefici, & Argentieri.		Cap. 13.
De' Librari.		Cap. 14.
De' Statuarij, e Scarpellini.		Cap. 15.
De' Copertari, & Arte della Lana.		Cap. 16.
De' Vignaroli.		Cap. 17.
De' Tefitori.		Cap. 18.
De' Eredenzieri.		Cap. 19.
De' Cocchieri.		Cap. 20.
De' Macellari.		Cap. 21.
De' Piazzaruoli, Fruttaroli, &c.		Cap. 22.
De' Curiali.		Cap. 23.
De' Materazzari.		Cap. 24.
De' Ferrari, Ghiauari, &c.		Cap. 25.
De' Bombardieri.		Cap. 26.
De' Copisti.		Cap. 27.
De' Caudatarij.		Cap. 28.
De' Garzoni de' Calzolari.		Cap. 29.
De' Vaccinari.		Cap. 30.
De' Mercari, Profumieri, &c.		Cap. 31.
Corollario delle Vniuersità dell'Arti.		Cap. 32.

Fig. 70 - The universities or brotherhoods of arts in Rome as listed by Carlo Bartolomeo Piazza in his *Eusevologio romano delle Opere Pie di Roma* (Rome, 1698), p. XXVIII and XXIX

Another list, also pertaining to the beginning of the seventeenth century and ranked according to the annual fee to be paid to the local authorities, is presented by Antonio Martini in his book *Arti mestieri e fede nella Roma dei Papi*: sellers of cloths and clothes, grocers, tailors, fishmongers,

carpenters, makers of dishware, sellers of wine, herbs, oil, wood, books, manufacturers of candles and soap, millers, barbers and many others make up a long, multifarious list of workers and professionals who served both residents and visitors in papal Rome.

CATEGORIA	TASSA IN SCUDI	CATEGORIA	TASSA IN SCUDI
Osti e bettole	325,—	Mercanti di legna	25,—
Merciari, mercanti di drappi, banderari, berrettari, guanta- ri, profumieri e velettari	200,—	Mercanti di corami cordovani e sola	25,—
Fornari, ciambellari, tagliolinari	150,—	Mercanti di salumi	25,—
Mercanti di panni di fondaco..	120,—	Librari e cartolari.....	20,—
Pescivendoli	117,—	Mercanti di legnami grossi	20,—
Pizzicaroli	104,—	Pollaroli	19,50
Sartori, pelamantelli, giubbona- ri, camiciari, calzettari	100,—	Sellari, cassari e brigliozzari ..	19,50
Fornari e arti dipendenti	100,—	Camere locande.....	19,50
Macellari e arti dipendenti.....	97,50	Candelottari	19,50
Mercanti di vini a Ripa	97,50	Rigattieri, bambaciari e mate- razzari	16,—
Falegnami e arti dipendenti ..	80,—	Vermicellari	13,—
Vascellari, bicchierari e fornaciari	65,—	Speziali	13,—
Fruttaroli e merangolari	52,—	Coronari e medagliari	13,—
Vaccinari	52,—	Norcini, uccellatori	13,—
Droghieri	52,—	Coramari e battilori	13,—
Mercanti di olio e saponari....	52,—	Muratori e imbiancatori	13,—
Calzolari d'arte sottile.....	50,—	Funari e linaroli	13,—
Calzolari d'arte grossa e ciabat- tini	50,—	Cocchieri e vetturini.....	13,—
Mercanti di lana	50,—	Orzaroli	10,—
Arte bianche	40,—	Barilari	6,50
Mercanti di panni romaneschi e copertari	39,—	Pasticceri	6,50
Ortolani ed erbaroli	32,50	Scarpellini	6,50
Magazzinieri di vino.....	25,—	Molinari	6,50
		Barbieri	6,50
		Tessitori di panni di lino e di lana	6,50
		Ricamatori.....	4,—

Fig. 71 - Business activities in Rome in the year 1600, from Antonio Martini's *Arti mestieri e fede nella Roma dei Papi* (Bologna, 1965), p. 41

In the Italian towns of the Middle Ages, the growing presence of new categories of people able to generate their own revenues through their work changed the established social landscape, traditionally dominated by local aristocracies and including masses of low-income rural workers. The new economically-relevant social groups tended to associate in guilds, which ensured a coordinated protection of their interests and better represented their aspirations in the urban political arena.

A similar process happened in Rome, though with a significant delay connected with the peculiar situation experienced by the city, in which the Popes and the barons occupied the whole political space, leaving no opportunity for popular classes to emerge. And we must consider that even during the new phase of restoration and development that occurred starting from the fifteenth century the evolution of the political scenario in Rome

turned to be different with respect to what happened in other Italian towns: here the papal court and the powerful aristocratic families never allowed the local guilds to gain any political role.

So, as we will see later, the associated bodies of crafts and arts of Rome will mainly devote their time and efforts to the consolidation of their positioning in their own captive trades, quarrelling with each other to win for themselves additional market spaces and new clearances for selling additional products originally assigned to other guilds.

Starting from the fifteenth century, we begin to find in Rome dozens and dozens of guilds, known as 'Confraternite' (brotherhoods) or 'Università' (universities, or general associations). As an illustrative list we mention those grouping together the 'ortolani' (greengrocers), 'pollaroli' (sellers of chicken meat), 'pizzicaroli' (grocers), 'pescatori' (fishermen), 'pescivendoli' (fishmongers), 'librari' (booksellers), 'artebianche, orzaroli e nevaroli' (practitioners of 'white arts', including sellers of flour and snow), 'sellari' (makers of saddles and harnesses), 'vaccinari' (makers of leather goods), 'barbieri' (barbers), 'fruttaroli' (fruit sellers), 'muratori' (construction workers), 'sarti' (tailors), 'saponari e ogliarari' (soap makers), 'vascellari' (makers of dishware), 'candelottari' (makers of candles), 'orafi e argentieri' (goldsmiths and silversmiths), 'macellari' (butchers). A full list can be retrieved in the well-informed essay *Arti mestieri e fede nella Roma dei Papi* by Antonio Martini, from which we already quoted.

And we will see that the 'Norcini', too, will have their own guild, side by side with the others.

Each guild was authorised by the Popes to conduct one or more businesses and was provided with its own management level, formed by consuls, chamberlains ('camerlenghi') and other officials.

How many of them are relevant within the purpose of our research? Only two are significant to us (actually three, if we also include the 'Norcini'): the ones that were formally authorised to deal with pigs and pork meat.

We are referring to the Butchers ('macellari') and the Grocers ('pizzicaroli'). And we will deal with their guilds in more detail in the next paragraph.

5.6 Before the 'Norcini' came: the Guilds of 'Macellari' (Butchers) and 'Pizzicaroli' (Grocers)

In sixteenth-century Rome, two important guilds were involved in the management of pork-based food: they were the Butchers and the Grocers.

First, there were Butchers ('Macellari'), with their guild, one of the most ancient of all Roman guilds. Their Charters, written in Latin in the fifteenth century and then rewritten in Italian in 1536, were intended to regulate a complicated market, in which the animals — as we already mentioned in a previous paragraph — were subject to requisition at farms in the Roman Campagna and other papal provinces, and forcibly brought to Rome to be sold at lower, regulated prices in order to quench the hunger for food of the population of the capital city, notoriously prone to rioting in case of provision shortfalls and market turmoil.

Fig. 72 - 'Campo Vaccino' at the Roman Forum as it appeared in the first half of the seventeenth century, a detail from a drawing by Stefano della Bella, preserved at the Gabinetto Disegni e Stampe of the Istituto Centrale della Grafica in Rome (Fondo Corsini, scatola 51bis, S-FC117364)

The correct handling of such a heavily-controlled market wasn't easy at all. The butchers, too, were subject to strict rules, so as to avoid inappropriate behaviours that could endanger the critical, regular flow of the procurement, distribution and processing of meat in Rome, resulting in unwanted meat shortages amid the town's inhabitants.

For instance, as per Chapter XX of their Charters, the Butchers were absolutely prohibited from buying the animals directly in the countryside, in an attempt to avoid the auctions and market negotiations to be publicly held at the 'Campo Vaccino', the large esplanade which since the Middle Ages covered the ruins of the Roman Forum, that was still buried underneath.

The 'Campo Vaccino' (also indicated in the Charters as 'Foro Boario' or 'Campo Tarquinio') extended from the Church of Santa Maria Nova, also known as Santa Francesca Romana, to the slopes of the Capitoline Hill. There, and only there, a market was held in selected days, «until the toll of the bell of Santa Maria Nova at sunset» (in Italian «al sono della campana de Sancta Maria Nova ad Ave Maria»), as stated by Chapter LV. And Fridays were explicitly dedicated to the trade of pigs (Chapter LIV):

«No butcher, for himself or by sending others on his behalf, ever dare go on Thursdays to the gates or to any other place to buy pigs, nor castrated animals, sheep and goats except on Fridays at the Campo Tarquinio».

[In the original Italian text: «Nissun macellaro per se, o per altri in suo nome ardisca ne presuma al giovedì di andare ad alcuna porta o vero altrove ad comperare porci, o castrati pecore ne capre se non il Venerdì in Campo Tarquino»].

So butchers were fully licensed to slaughter pigs and sell fresh pork meat in Rome, a work they could only carry out in authorised abattoirs so as to avoid that butchery be performed in filthy, unhealthy premises: a perilous business resulting in the sale of «contaminated meat, a most dangerous occurrence for public safety» (in Italian, «carne di bestiame infecta, cosa perniciosissima alla repubblica»), as expressed in Chapter LVIII.

Fig. 73 - Clauses on pigs from the *Statuta Artis Macellariorum de Urbe* (manuscript Cred. XI, t. 87 preserved in the Archive of the Camera Capitolina, Rome), folium 17

Nonetheless, sure enough they did not have the specific knowledge to correctly manage the procedure for making sausages, salami, and other salted pork meat products; neither had they the suitable premises where to process salted pork meat, a craft which requires the performance of very specific treatments and time enough to obtain the right level of seasoning for hams and sausages.

So this part of the work was mainly carried out, in Rome, by the 'Pizzicaroli' with their dedicated, powerful guild.

The Guild of the Grocers ('Pizzicaroli'), whose Charters were first approved in 1568, was one of the most thriving in Rome, as we can see from the significant annual tax that its members were compelled to pay to the local authorities (see Antonio Martini, *Arti mestieri e fede nella Roma dei Papi*, p. 41). They occupied an extended territory in the overall market of consumer goods in papal Rome, as clearly defined in Chapter XXXVI of their Charters. In the long list of foodstuff and other goods they assign to themselves for exclusive sale in town, they explicitly reference their own monopolistic position in the trade of salted pork meat, which is mentioned as the very first item:

«Then we state and command that all the listed stuff and goods, that is Pork Meat, salted of any sort, like Bacon, Lard, Soppressata, and Sausages of all sorts, Pork and Buffalo tongues, Cheese of all sorts, [...], Oil, Candles, and

Soap of all sorts, Anchovies, Tuna fish, [...] Fish and Salmon, Eels, and Mulletts [...] and on a general basis all sorts of cured meat, [...] Vinegar, [...] Macaroni and Vermicelli, [...] Beans, Barley, [...] Fava beans, and Wheat to be used as feed for the Poultry, [...] all and each of the said stuff and goods, they are intended to be, and must be, by legal statement, called and recognised as Stuff and Goods pertaining to the Art and University of the Grocers of Rome... ».

[In the original Italian text: «Item statuimo, et ordiniamo, che tutte e singole infrascritte robbe, e mercanzie, cioè Carne di Porco salata d'ogni sorte, come Ventresche, Lardo, Strutto, e Sogna, Sopprassate, e Salsiccioni di tutte le sorti, Lingue di Porco, e di Bufala, Cascio di tutte le sorti, [...], Oglio, Candele, e Sapone di tutte le sorti, Alice, Tonnina, [...] Pesce e Salomone, Anguille, e Cefali [...] e generalmente d'ogni sorte di Salumi, [...] Aceto, [...] Maccaroni, e Vermicelli, [...], Legumi, Orzo, [...] Fave, e Grano per dare ai Polli, [...] tutte, e singole cose, e mercanzie predette, s'intendono, esser debbiano, e siano con effetto nuncupate, chiamate, e dette Robbe, e Mercanzie dell'Arte, et Università de Pizzicaroli di Roma, et ad essa Università, et Arte spettante, e pertinente... »].

Fig. 74 - Foodstuff and goods pertaining to the Grocers, from the *Statuti dell'Università, ed Arte de Pizzicaroli di Roma* (manuscript Cred. XI, t. 48 preserved in the Archive of the Camera Capitolina, Rome), p. 52

Was that all? Not in the least. There was an additional clause (Chapter XXXIX) which added to all the listed, exclusive items a long series of further elements on a non-exclusive basis, making the 'pizzicaroli' the guild with the most extended managed market area, even in spite of other competing guilds:

«Of the items that the 'Pizzicaroli' can hold and sell with no limitation at all — Then we state and command that the said University and Art of the Grocers of Rome, and each man belonging to the said University and Art, is permitted to legally hold and sell, at will, all the following Goods, that is Thread, Cord, Laces, Needles and Pins of any kind, dry Almonds, and Raisin of any sort, [...] Onions, Shallots, Pumpkins, Cucumbers, Melons, and in general any sort of vegetables, without any acknowledgement whatsoever to any other Consulship or Art, as to the relevant earnings, nor any need for Papers or Licenses, or imposition whatsoever coming from any other Art or Consulship over the said items, or trading Goods».

Delle robbe che possono tenere,
e vendere li Pizzicaroli senza
soggezione alcuna.

Cap. XXXIX.
Item statuimo, et ordiniamo, che
sia lecito all'Università, et Arte
predetta de Pizzicaroli di Roma,
et a tutti, et singoli Uomini del-
la predetta Università, et Arte
di poter tenere, e vendere a loro
beneplacito tutte le infra scritte
mercanzie, à vero frutti secchi,
e robbe d'orto, ovvero ortaglie,

Fig. 75 - Additional items to be traded freely by the Grocers, from the *Statuti dell'Università, ed Arte de Pizzicaroli di Roma* (manuscript Cred. XI, t. 48 preserved in the Archive of the Camera Capitolina, Rome), p. 57

[In the original Italian text: «Delle robbe che possono tenere e vendere li Pizzicaroli senza soggezione alcuna — Item statuimo et ordiniamo, che sia lecito all'Università, et Arte predetta de Pizzicaroli di Roma et a tutti, e singoli Uomini della predetta Università, et Arte di poter tenere, e vendere

a loro beneplacito tutte le infrascritte Mercanzie, ò vero frutti secchi, e Robbe d'orto, overo Ortaglie, et etiam Mercanzie, cioè Filo, Spago, Stringhe, Agucchie, e Spillette d'ogni sorte, Amandole secche, overo Uve passe d'ogni sorte, [...] Cipolle, Scalogne, Cocuzze, Cetrioli, Meloni, e generalmente ogni, e qualunque sorte e genere de Fogliame, e Ortaglie, senza riconoscimento ad alcun altro Consolato, overo Arte, quanto all'Introito, ò Carte, overo Patenti, ò imposizione, ò qualsivoglia altra cosa, che v'imponesse da qualsivoglia altra Arte, overo Consolato su le predette cose, overo Mercanzie»].

So the 'pizzicaroli' were fully authorised to sell, amid a plethora of items, salted pork meat, including sausages and soppressata and salami and any other sort of salted and seasoned product.

But what about fresh pork meat? Could they also invade the home market of Butchers, with the presumption typical of their Guild?

Yes, they could. And they had to pay nothing to the Guild of Butchers, as we can read in Chapter LXIX of their Charters:

Fig. 76 - Pig slaughtering freely carried out by the Grocers, from the *Statuti dell'Università, ed Arte de Pizzicaroli di Roma* (manuscript Cred. XI, t. 48 preserved in the Archive of the Camera Capitolina, Rome), p. 93

«That no Tax be paid to the Butchers [by the Grocers] on the slaughtering of pigs — Then that no Grocer be required nor obliged to pay any fee nor Tax to the Art of Butchers on the annual slaughter of pigs carried out by the said Grocers at their own shops and grocery stores».

[In the original Italian text: «Che non si paghi Tassa del Macello de Porci a Macellari — Item che nessun Pizzicarolo sia tenuto ne obbligato a pagare sorte alcuna di gravezza, ne Tassa all'Arte de Macellari per il Macello che annualmente li detti Pizzicaroli fanno dei Porci a le loro Botteghe e Pizzicherie»].

This version of the Charters dates back to the eighteenth century, yet we know that this momentous right was conferred to the Grocers at least two centuries earlier.

How can we tell that? We actually find an explicit reference to this privilege in the so-called *Rubricellone* of the Archive of the Camera Capitolina in Rome, an extraordinary catalogue of all the documents preserved in this historical archive compiled by archivist Francesco Maria Magni at the mid of the eighteenth century: a highly meritorious work which provides extensive references to many official documents of papal Rome that would be almost impossible to retrieve otherwise — unless physical accesses are made to the ancient volumes stored at the Camera Capitolina, looking serendipitously for clues amid a colossal, unmanageable quantity of paperwork.

In volume IV of the *Rubricellone*, under the heading «Grocers of Rome», we retrieve a reference to a papal decree issued in 1539 stating the following:

«Decree of the Council that the Grocers must never slaughter pigs nor salt their meat if not after Christmas, for the reasons there indicated».

[In the original Italian text: «Decreto di Consiglio che li Pizzicaroli non potessero Macellare Porci in niuno tempo, ne insalare se non dopo Natale per le Raggioni ivi addotte»].

Thus the 'pizzicaroli' of Rome, with their marked ability to win for themselves specific market positions originally assigned to other guilds, could freely slaughter pigs and process their meat since the sixteenth century, or even before.

So such was Rome in the sixteenth century: the holy, celebrated see of the Popes, to which the people from Norcia began to migrate possibly starting from the fifteenth century, when Rome itself was entering a new period of growth and development.

But what were the characteristics of this migration process? Why people from Norcia began to move to Rome? And what roles did they play within the Roman society? We will address these peculiar topics in the next chapters.

6. Norcia and Rome: the role of the 'Norcini' in the town of the Popes

6.1 The investigation of a centuries-long process: issues and methodologies

Rome: the Popes; the populace; the need for food supplies; a regulated market; the Butchers, the Grocers and their Guilds.

Then, we have the 'Norcini': people from Norcia who, across the centuries, have taken the role of main experts in town as to pork meat, especially with reference to salted pork meat. Throughout the centuries, we will find many documents that will attest to both the presence in Rome of the 'Norcini' and their particular role in the same city, up to our contemporary times.

Nonetheless, we must admit that a historiographical problem does actually shows up: we will see that, while it is easy to retrieve information on the growing presence in Rome of people from Norcia starting from the late fifteenth century and onwards, it is no easy task to recover the same information as to their role in the arts of butchery and meat processing during the earliest centuries, namely the fifteenth and the sixteenth.

In other words, we know that the 'Norcini' begin to be present in Rome from as early as the fifteenth century, the result of an increasing flow of migrants moving from Norcia to the town of the Popes; yet we cannot easily show that their initial presence was also marked by a specific craft, an art which concerned their special ability in butchery and the making of sausages, hams and salami.

Still, we know for certain that such was their popular renown in Rome, and a lasting one, too: so much so that many butchery and grocery shops in town are called, even today, 'norcinerie'. That is, the shops of the 'Norcini'.

So, before we address in full the tricky issue of investigating the earliest centuries of the presence of the 'Norcini' in Rome, we will present their long lasting renown as butchers. We will read the words written centuries ago by professional experts of the Papal States; we will peruse the many old books that have provided mentions of the art of the 'Norcini' in Rome and other towns of central Italy; we will briefly describe the contemporary fame of the people from Norcia amid contemporary Roman residents.

Fig. 79 - A contemporary 'norcineria' (butcher's shop) in Via di Bravetta, a road set in a western district of Rome not far from the Vatican

We will illuminate the celebrated name of the 'Norcini' living by St. Peter's dome and the Colosseum. Only afterwards, we will try to shed light on their initial presence in Rome, dating to the late fifteenth century.

And let's start from the words written, during the eighteenth century, by an expert in the field: Demetrio Andretti.

6.2 The 'Norcini': a eighteenth-century professional witness

The most explicit, comprehensive reference to Norcia, the 'Norcini' in the capital of the Papal States and their specific expertise on pork meat is given

by a text which dates to the middle of the eighteenth century; it describes in detail the historical role of the Roman 'Norcini' with words which leave no space to uncertainty.

The author of the *Trattato sopra il Presidentato della Grascia di Roma* was a professional expert in the field: for many years, around 1750, Demetrio Andretti (or Andretti) had served as chief magistrate of the 'Grascia', the powerful institution that was in charge for the critical supply of meat and oil in Rome. Starting from the sixteenth century onwards, the body had been handling, in the countryside, the requisition of cattle to be sent to the capital city for slaughtering, meat processing and controlled distribution to the Roman market, as well as the collection of relevant custom duties.

Andretti's huge essay is contained in two manuscripted volumes (no. 69 and 70) preserved at the Archivio di Stato of Rome, and we can read the illuminating excerpt he wrote on the 'Norcini' in the article *L'arte norcina dall'Umbria a Roma — L'impatto, storico, sociale ed economico* by Giuseppe Cruciani, included in the book *I norcini e Roma — L'arte della norcineria dall'Umbria alla Dominante* (Rome, 2013) edited by Elio di Michele (p. 35-36).

The following is the history of the 'Norcini' in Rome according to Andretti:

«In old times, the slaughtering of the Black Animals [meaning the pigs, editor's note], as to what concerns fresh Meat, was carried out by the Guild of Butchers, and, as to what concerns Salted meat, those were processed by the Guild of Norcini, who from season to season used to come to this purpose from the Mountains to Rome».

[In the original Italian text: «Anticamente la macellazione degli Animali Neri per quello concernevano le Carni fresche, questa si faceva dall'Arte dei Macellari, e rispetto alle Salate queste si facevano dall'Arte de Norcini, quali a tal'oggetto di staggione in staggione calavano dalle Montagne à Roma»].

Here we are. Since centuries, says Andretti, people used to travel from the mountains of Norcia to the capital city of the Papal States bringing with them their specialised craft concerning how to salt and season pork meat, for the preparation of toothsome products. That was an art they had been

nurturing in their hometown, using the delicious meat of pigs — the «Black Animals» mentioned by Andretti, which we saw were raised in Norcia in medieval and modern times — pasturing by the oaks which grew in the untouched woods and fed on tasty acorns: the products of their know-how were sausages which had been maturing at the fresh, reinvigorating winds blowing from the elevated peaks of the Apennines. According to Andretti, the supply for the Romans was prepared directly in Rome, by seasoning the pork meat through the application of the craft they knew so well. Their food products were for the poor and the rich, and always of the highest, most palatable quality.

L'ARTE NORCINA DALL'UMBRIA A ROMA

miliari. Demetrio Andretti, Governatore della Dogana, nel suo *Trattato sopra il Presidentato della Grascia*, oltre due secoli e mezzo orsono (nel 1758), informava come tra le Corporazioni dei Pizzicaroli e dei Norcini macellai frequentemente ci fossero degli attriti di natura economica. L'oggetto del contendere era stato per secoli il comune interesse per il maiale dalla vendita del quale gli uni ricavano una parte cospicua dei propri introiti, gli altri l'unica fonte di reddito. Così registra l'Andretti:

Anticamente la macellazione degli Animali Neri per quello concernevano le Carni fresche, questa si faceva dall'Arte de' Macellari, e rispetto alle Salate queste si facevano dall'Arte de' Norcini, quali a tal'oggetto di stagione in stagione calavano dalle Montagne à Roma, ma in progresso di tempo l'Arte de' Pizzicaroli richiese quella sudetta dei Macellari ai quali in vigore dei loro Statuti confermati da diversi Pontefici è solo permessa la macellazione, di volergli dare il permesso di poter anche essi Pizzicaroli far la macellazione dei Porci, conforme gli fu accordata col pagamento di un annuo tributo alla Chiesa dei Macellari dai quali poi fu anche abbandonata affatto una tal macellazione restando li Norcini, ed in luogo dei Macellari li Pizzicaroli, questi però non bastandogli l'ottenuto permesso di macellare li Porci e di farne le Salate, ma per voler esser soli à tal mercimonio di Carni hanno cercato, e tuttavia cercano ogni strada possibile per discacciare da Roma li Norcini, cioè quelli che in sua stagione come dissi si portano à Roma ad aprirne Bottega, senza niente considerare ingannati dal luoco, che li primi che hanno introdotta in Roma l'arte di salare le Carni Porcine sono stati li Norcini, e che senza di questi neppure essi Pizzicaroli potrebbero ad uso di arte farne il lavoriero, dovendosi necessariamente valersi dei Norcini, che di anno in anno vengono a lavorargli dette Carni. Questo intento de' Pizzicaroli gli è in parte riuscito valendosi in particolare delli contratti delle compre dei Salami, che dalli Norcini si vendono alli Pizzicaroli à Pasqua di Resurrezione, mentre l'Arte dei Norcini in tempo della Stagione Porcina vende soltanto un poco di Lombetto, e di Salciccie, et il restante procura di salare, in specie col fare dei Salami quali poi à Pasqua di Resurrezione per poter far ritorno alla sua Patria e Famiglia procura di farne contratto di ...
...detti alli Pizzicaroli e questi servendosi dell'occasione eli offeriscono temui

Fig. 80 - An excerpt from Demetrio Andretti's *Trattato sopra il Presidentato della Grascia di Roma* as presented in the article *L'arte norcina dall'Umbria a Roma — L'impatto, storico, sociale ed economico* by Giuseppe Cruciani, included in the book *I norcini e Roma — L'arte della norcineria dall'Umbria alla Dominante* edited by Elio di Michele (Rome, 2013), p. 35

Because, Andretti writes — clearly and once for all — that «the first to introduce in Rome the art of salting Pork Meat were the Norcini» (in Italian «li primi che hanno introdotta in Roma l'arte di salare le Carni Porcine sono stati li Norcini»).

With Demetrio Andretti, we plunge right away into the focal point of our research: even though in Rome pigs were certainly raised and slaughtered and processed since Roman times, the 'Norcini' from Norcia were the ones who perfectly knew the delicate, tricky craft of salting pork meat: the ones who brought this craft onto the dining tables of Rome. For the members of the papal aristocracy and the Roman populace.

But how did the 'Norcini' used to work in Rome? Andretti says that they used to migrate seasonally from Norcia to Rome: «[The Norcini] when the season is right, as I said, travel to Rome to open their Shops» (in Italian «quelli che in sua staggione come dissi si portano a Roma ad aprirne Bottega»).

This is a framework which is also confirmed by later sources, even up to the twentieth century. Especially in winters, a specialised migration of crafted workers and assistants, proficient in pig slaughtering and the processing and seasoning of salted pork meat, used to flock to Rome, where the market was waiting for their services.

So Demetrio Andretti provides us with a reliable starting point from where to begin our investigation on the 'Norcini' in Rome: they were butchers, they were grocers, they brought in town the art of salting pork meat.

But what was the relationship with the existing Roman guilds, especially those of the Butchers and the Grocers? Andretti writes a few significant words on the matter:

«Without them [the 'Norcini', editor's note], the Grocers [in Rome] would never be able to skillfully process that sort of meat; so they necessarily need to avail themselves of the Norcini, who year after year come to Rome and work the said meat».

[In the original Italian text: «Senza di questi neppure essi Pizzicaroli potrebbero ad uso di arte farne il lavoriero, dovendosi necessariamente valersi dei Norcini, che di anno in anno vengono a lavorargli dette Carni»].

portano à Roma ad aprirne Bottega, senza niente considerare ingannati dal lucro, che li primi che hanno introdotta in Roma l'arte di salare le Carni Porcine sono stati li Norcini, e che senza di questi neppure essi Pizzicaroli potrebbero ad uso di arte farne il lavoriero, dovendosi necessariamente valersi dei Norcini, che di anno in anno vengono a lavorargli dette Carni. Questo intento de' Pizzicaroli gli è in parte riuscito valendosi in particolare delli con-

Fig. 81 - The excerpt on 'Norcini' and 'Pizzicaroli' (grocers) from Demetrio Andretti's *Trattato sopra il Presidentato della Grascia di Roma* as presented in the article *L'arte norcina dall'Umbria a Roma — L'impatto, storico, sociale ed economico* by Giuseppe Cruciani, included in the book *I norcini e Roma — L'arte della norcineria dall'Umbria alla Dominante* edited by Elio di Michele (Rome, 2013), p. 35

So it seems that the 'Norcini' worked for the Roman Grocers and their Guild. But is that confirmed by any other sources? And what about the Butchers? How could they accept those 'Norcini' as straight competitors as butchers operating on their same market, even though they were limiting themselves to the processing of pork meat?

Andretti provides further details on this issue:

«In the course of time the Art of Grocers asked the Art of Butchers — which under their Charters, confirmed by various Popes, were granted the right to carry out butchery on an exclusive basis — to be given the license to slaughter pigs. This right was granted to them, under the payment of an annual tax to be conferred to the Church of the Butchers. Later, the Butchers themselves just gave up the pig slaughtering business: so this activity was only carried out by the Norcini and, rather than the Butchers, by the Grocers».

[In the original Italian text: «In progresso di tempo l'Arte de Pizzicaroli richiese quella sudetta dei Macellari ai quali in vigore dei loro Statuti confermati da diversi Pontefici è solo permessa la macellazione, di volergli dare il permesso di poter anche essi Pizzicaroli far la macellazione dei Porci, conforme gli fu accordata col pagamento di un annuo tributo alla Chiesa dei Macellari dai quali poi fu anche abbandonata affatto una tal macellazione restando li Norcini, ed in luogo dei Macellari li Pizzicaroli»].

Andretti confirms that the Grocers had obtained for themselves the right to slaughter pigs, an activity originally reserved to the Butchers, as we already illustrated in a previous paragraph. But the important consideration here is that the people of Norcia in Rome, too, as time went by, won for

themselves a remarkable business positioning in the area of the slaughtering of pigs and the processing of their meat, sharing the Roman market with the powerful Guild of the Grocers and eventually leaving the Butchers out of this particular sector.

Certainly enough, the work written by Demetrio Andretti, a professional in the food sector of Rome, is to be considered as a veritable treasure trove of valuable information on the history of the 'Norcini' in Rome. And we will base all our subsequent analysis on the framework bountifully provided by him.

However, many questions are still open and need further insight.

For instance, Andretti does not provide any information on the early phase of the presence of the 'Norcini' in Rome, which, as we will see, is to be situated in the late fifteenth century.

Furthermore, according to some sources the 'Norcini', in the course of the centuries, would have eventually won for themselves the exclusivity on the treatment of pork meat in Rome, including not only salted products but also fresh meat: an assertion that has been enjoying a widespread circulation and fortune until our present days, but certainly with no confirmation at all in the words written by Demetrio Andretti.

So is that true? Could the 'Norcini' from Norcia, in their uncomfortable role as newcomers, ever defeat all the powerful, existing guilds in Rome and gain full control over the exclusive rights on the processing of pig's meat?

It sounds strange to our ears: lucrative markets are never abandoned to new players without fighting a stern, pitiless war. Centuries ago just like today.

Nonetheless, let's analyse this issue, by starting from the very scholar who first propagated the above assertion: French historian Emmanuel Pierre Rodocanachi.

6.3 A monopoly on pork meat controlled by the 'Norcini' in Rome?

Emmanuel Pierre Rodocanachi, one of the major nineteenth-century experts in the history of papal Rome, holds that the 'Norcini' actually enjoyed a straight monopoly on the supply of pigs in Rome.

According to Rodocanachi, this monopoly was formalized in certain decrees issued by the authorities in Rome throughout the time, as he reports in his study *Les corporations ouvrières à Rome depuis la chute de l'Empire Romain* (Paris, 1894, Vol. 1, p. 189):

«Since ancient times, as said in the Charters, the inhabitants of two small towns, Norcia and Cascia, lying at the borders of Latium and Umbria, had an exclusivity over the provision to Rome of game and pigs. [...] The Umbrian traders created a monopoly to their advantage and a papal decision was needed to abolish it. The Roman butchers were, on this specific subject, dependent on the 'norcini'; and the papal decrees concerning butchery, which are numerous, are intended for the 'norcini' rather than for the butchers».

Fig. 82 - The 'Norcini' in Emmanuel Pierre Rodocanachi's *Les corporations ouvrières à Rome depuis la chute de l'Empire Romain* (Paris, 1894), Vol. 1, p. 187 and 189

[In the original French text: «Depuis des temps très anciens, ce sont les statuts qui le disent, les habitants des deux petites villes de Norcia et de Cascia, situées aux confins du Latium et de l'Ombrie, avaient le monopole de l'approvisionnement de Rome en gibier et en porcs. [...] Les marchands ombriens avaient créé un monopole à leur profit et il fallut une décision pontificale pour l'abolir. Les charcutiers étaient, sur ce point, leurs tributaires et les ordonnances papales relatives à la charcuterie, qui sont nombreuses, s'appliquent à eux plus qu'aux charcutiers»].

So, according to Rodocanachi, the 'Norcini' were the sole and exclusive suppliers of pig's meat in Rome. They even superseded the Butchers and their influential guild. A total success, utterly amazing, for people who were new to Rome and its market.

It is apparent that there are significant discrepancies in the descriptions of the status held by the 'Norcini' in Rome as presented by Andretti and Rodocanachi: the former hints to a business on pigs shared with the Guild of Grocers, while the latter envisages the existence of a thorough monopoly allegedly held by the 'Norcini' and concerning pigs, the butchery of fresh pork meat and salted pork meat.

However, a few lines later Rodocanachi seems to contradict his previous statements: in fact, he adds that the 'Norcini', before setting up their own guild (an occurrence that will happen only in 1677, as we will see in a subsequent paragraph), «they were under the control of the butchers» («jusqu'alors, ils étaient restés soumis aux bouchers», in French).

So did they hold a monopoly on the pigs' market? Or, alternatively, were they subject to the Guild of Butchers? The two pieces of information don't seem to get along together. Furthermore, Rodocanachi does not mention the Grocers at all.

Is Rodocanachi right about a supposed market exclusivity on pigs held by the 'Norcini' in Rome? Or maybe Rodocanachi just misinterpreted the information he was able to retrieve in the ancient archives of the city of Rome?

Let's analyse the statement written by Rodocanachi in further detail.

A source quoted by Rodocanachi and containing, according to him, a confirmation of the existence of the said monopoly is a document preserved at the Italian State Archives («*Atti di Domenico Righi*, protocol, 1616, fol. 208»); unfortunately this document is currently unpublished, so for the time being we cannot check its actual content.

Luckily enough, he also provides further information: when he mentions the control exerted by the Butchers over the 'Norcini', Rodocanachi includes a footnote with an accurate reference to some additional sixteenth-century documents preserved at the Camera Capitolina of Rome.

It will be in those documents that we will find the relevant clues that will help us clarify the whole matter.

We will see that we will start talking of the 'salcicciari': in English, the 'makers of sausages', possibly the earliest mention of the presence of our crafty 'Norcini' in Rome, during the early sixteenth century.

And we will also find out that the 'Norcini', though excellent butchers and experts in pork meat salting, did not hold a monopoly on this business in Rome: they shared this lucrative market with the Grocers, and were also active in other food markets (game, truffles, fish) and lower-level job areas (handymen, manual workers). And — as we extensively illustrated in our previous essay *The Precian Surgical School: an astounding European-wide success originated from a small Apennine hamlet* (2026) — during that same sixteenth century they will begin to appear in Rome as experienced surgeons: the so-called 'Precians', from the small hamlet of Preci, near Norcia, also known as 'Norcini' surgeons.

So let's now go back to the earliest phase of the presence of the 'Norcini' in Rome, and try to illuminate this initial period, for which documents are scarce: yet, we will find that reasonable scenarios can be built basing on the available information.

We will get back to the fifteenth century. When the 'Norcini' were coming to Rome.

7. The 'Norcini' in Rome: history of a migration

7.1 *The fifteenth century: from Norcia to Rome*

7.1.1 *A new migration flow begins*

As we saw in the preceding chapter, in fourteenth-century Florence we already have lots of people from Norcia: a number of appreciated surgeons, possibly coming from the area of Preci; the craftsmen who seasonally come to town to process the salty pork meat; and a class of lower-level workers, who earn their wages by carrying out simple, heavy tasks: the porters, or 'facchini' of Norcia.

But there is a time during which the people from Norcia also began to move to Rome, the capital city of the Papal States, in search of job opportunities of the most varied sorts, and bringing with them their craft concerning how to process pork meat to create toothsome sausages.

In our opinion, this time is the fifteenth century. This is the century of an early migration of 'Norcini' from their homeland to Rome, the capital city that was experiencing a new period of growth, population increase and general expansion. It is in this very period — the fifteenth century — that Norcia also experienced a growth in population, getting back to a number of inhabitants possibly summing up to five thousand people (see Federico Lattanzio, *Il Comune di Norcia e i suoi rapporti con il governo pontificio nel secolo XV*, Ph.D. thesis, Florence, 2013, p. 48), in a context of lively animation of the whole local society, attending to a number of expanding business and trades, with links to Florence, Rome, the Marches, the Kingdom of Naples and other Italian territories (F. Lattanzio, p. 51-63).

So let's now begin our analysis of this long migration process by considering the first, documented transfer of illustrious people from Norcia to Rome during the fifteenth century.

7.1.2 Prominent people from Norcia in fifteenth-century Rome

In the course of the Middle Ages in Norcia, as in other communal towns and settlements, a class of higher-rank individuals and families had gradually emerged: they were the owners of cattle, vast portions of lands, real estate and manufacturing plants (like mills, etc.); and so they acted as accumulation points for significant riches and wealth, which in turn allowed further acquisitions of properties and made it possible to invest in one's own career within both the local government and the papal central bureaucracy.

It is mainly starting from the second half of the fifteenth century that we find a number of prominent officials, born in Norcia, who held important posts within the papal administration in Rome: their names are Giovanni Nicola Barattani (captain of the town), Giovanni Ranieri (senator), Pietro Tebaldeschi ('comes palatinus' of the Holy Palace of the Lateran, senator), Carlo of Norcia (senator), Giacomo Silvestrini (senator), Johannes de Nursia (notary at the papal court), Andrea de Tartaglia (captain of the Holy Apostolic Palaces), as referenced by F. Lattanzio (p. 83-86, 99, 102).

So in this very period Rome began to appoint a quota of public servants drawing them from the ranks of the local elite in Norcia. We are talking of people who held important positions within the public administration of Rome and at the papal court. People from Norcia who had the chance and skills to carry out their brilliant careers by the river Tiber, in the course of the fifteenth century.

And there was also a celebrated professional who, being born in Norcia, was providing his skilled services to a Pope: Benedetto Reguardati, a member of one of the most distinguished families of Norcia (he brought the same family name as the mother of St. Benedict and St. Scholastica), was, for a certain time, the physician of Pope Pius II Piccolomini, even though he never resided permanently in Rome. We already mentioned him, in more detail, in our previous essay *The Precian Surgical School: an astounding European-wide success originated from a small Apennine hamlet* (2026, p. 175-178).

We don't have further documented evidence concerning any other migrations from Norcia to Rome, namely that of the 'Norcini' as butchers.

Nonetheless, we can suppose that during this very same period, the overall flow of people moving from Norcia to Rome was positively gaining momentum, with an increasing number of workers, merchants, and professionals of some sort who were settling in the town of the Popes: a settlement process that was experiencing a significant growth and was already attracting high-level officials originating from the town of St. Benedict.

We must keep in mind one main factor: in fifteenth-century Norcia certainly there were prominent individuals and families; yet, there were also many people who could not survive with the work and resources available locally. They needed to migrate in search of work, and the nearest places, the closest natural destinations were, of course, Florence and Rome.

This need for migration has not been changing much in the subsequent centuries. We can retrieve a moving description of the hardships that affected the poor families in the countryside of Norcia in a book written many centuries later by a man of our contemporary times: Oscar Battaglia, a Monsignor and an eminent professor of Biblical Studies, who was born in 1930 in Todiano, a small castle in the territory of Norcia, from which, as we saw earlier, many porters present in Florence used to come in past centuries.

In his *Book of memories (Il libro delle memorie, Rieti, 2024, p. 30 and 31)* he remembers his own departure to Rome when he was only nine, with the prospect to work in a grocery shop:

«Life amid the mountains [of Norcia, editor's note] was scant of economical resources. The fields were not fertile enough, and many families were forced to borrow money, or even faced plain starvation. Child labour was commonly practiced in such an environment of widespread deprivation, in which children, following a shortened cycle at the primary school, had to contribute to the family budget, either through work in the fields or sheep farming or even through a work provided to them by others. [...] I gladly agreed to leave Norcia for Rome, where my mother's brothers had a shop and needed an errand boy...».

In the first half of the twentieth century, just like five, six centuries earlier, the need for an additional income was a dramatic urge for the poor families of Norcia; people used to migrate to Florence already in the fourteenth century, and — when fifteenth-century Rome began to experience a most-welcome stabilisation process — they also used to migrate to the capital city of the Papal States, the other most reasonable choice to make.

However, this sort migration — certain and documented as to Florence, but only probable and undocumented when it comes to Rome — was no rapid, manifest, patent process. In fact, we don't find any references to workers and professionals coming from Norcia and established in Rome until the second half of the sixteenth century: this means that this second migration flow, which eventually built up a significant presence of people from Norcia in the capital of the Papal States, was steady and long-lasting, and was registered in the written sources at a later stage, owing to its subsequent blatant, conspicuous occurrence.

But why are we so convinced that the 'Norcini' actually began their migration to Rome as early as the second half of the fifteenth century, perhaps also driven or encouraged by their fellow-citizens already holding important post in the papal administration?

We think so because Rome was turning into a lucrative market for the supply of food from the neighboring territories. Including Norcia and its pork meat. So Rome actually needed their craft. As we will outline in the next paragraphs.

7.1.3 The appearance of the 'salcicciari' (makers of sausages): here come the 'Norcini' in Rome?

In a previous paragraph, we have been reading the words written by French scholar Emmanuel Pierre Rodocanachi in his nineteenth-century study *Les corporations ouvrières à Rome depuis la chute de l'Empire Romain*. In a precious footnote included in the chapter dedicated to the brotherhood of the people from Norcia and Cascia in Rome (we will talk about it in full detail later), Rodocanachi provides a most interesting clue, which he found in the meanders of the Archive of the Camera Capitolina.

In the said footnote, he refers to three ancient documents dating back to the early sixteenth century and relating, according to him, to the relationship between the 'Norcini' and the butchers: a precious piece of information, as the referred papers should tell us a lot about the early presence in Rome of people from Norcia marked by an expertise in butchery and cured pork meat.

Statuts. Quoique liés par tant d'intérêts semblables et par le souvenir de leur patrie commune, les marchands de Norcia et de Cascia ne songèrent à s'unir en corporation que vers la fin du dix-septième siècle¹; jusqu'alors, ils étaient restés soumis aux bouchers². Leurs statuts, composés seulement de vingt articles, furent rédigés par les principaux d'entre eux et approuvés par l'assemblée le 15 juin 1677; le pape Innocent XI les ratifia par la bulle « *Exponi Nobis nuper*

2. *Archiv. Stor. Not. Capitolino*, cred. I, vol. xxxvi, p. 42, et vol. xv, p. 40, an. 1515.

Fig. 83 - The footnote on the 'Norcini' from Emmanuel Pierre Rodocanachi's *Les corporations ouvrières à Rome depuis la chute de l'Empire Romain* (Paris, 1894), Vol. 1, p. 190

In the present paper, we are able to fully show the content of all three documents, giving us the chance to shed a new light on the history of the 'Norcini' in Rome.

The French scholar retrieved a mention to the three listed documents in the *Rubricellone* of the Archive of the Camera Capitolina in Rome, the great catalogue of all documents contained therein. It was compiled three centuries ago by archivist Francesco Maria Magni. And we are also able to show the specific chapter of the *Rubricellone* from which Rodocanachi drew its references from: it's in volume IV of the *Rubricellone*, under the heading «Butchers of Rome». The third item, one of the most ancient as it concerns documentation dating back to 1515, reads as follows:

«Decree of the Council [of the Camera Capitolina, editor's note] stating that the 'makers of sausages' can process pork Meat, and other types of meat, provided that the sausages are only made of Pork Meat, and that the pigs are not flayed nor burnt and their skin is not stripped off with Water; in any case those 'makers of sausages' must report to the Consuls of the Butchers».

[In the original Italian text: «Decreto di Consiglio, che li Salcicciari potessero fare la Carne porcina, e altre Carni, purché le Salsiccie fossero di Carne di Porco, e che li Porci non si scorticassero, né si abbruciassero e spellassero con l'Acqua, e che detti Salcicciari niente di meno dovessero star sotto de Consoli de Macellari»].

Fig. 84 - The 'Salcicciari' as mentioned in the *Rubricellone generale di tutte le materie esistenti nell'Archivio Segreto dell'Eccellentissima Camera di Campidoglio* (Archive of the Camera Capitolina, Rome), Vol. IV, p. IV and 3203

We must note that the text we just read from the *Rubricellone* is only a summary of the original document, so we need to retrieve the wording of the original decree written in 1515; furthermore, the *Rubricellone* says that there are two more decrees of similar content («altro Decreto simile»), and the three are exactly marked by the same catalogue positions as reported by Rodocanachi in his footnote.

Let's take the first one, which, according to Rodocanachi and the *Rubricellone*, is stored in cupboard no. 1, Vol. XXXVI of the many tomes contained in the same ancient, illustrious 'credenzone', containing a series of decrees issued by the Camera Capitolina of Rome between 1515 and 1557.

Here it is, we find it at page 12:

«And in the same day, month, indiction, Year and Pontificate [referring to October 7 1515 of the pontificate of Pope Leo X, as reported in the previous page, editor's note], it was decided in the same session of the Council that the 'makers of sausages' can process pork meat, and all other types of meat, provided that the sausages are only made of pork meat, and

that the pigs are not flayed nor burnt and their skin is not stripped off with water; in any case those 'makers of sausages' must owe obedience to the Consuls of the Butchers».

[In the original Latin text: «Et eodem die, mense, indictione, Anno, et Pontificatu conclusum in eodem consilio fuit que salcicciarii possint facere carnes porcinas, et omnes alias carnes, dummodo salciccia sint ex porci carne, et que porci non excoriantur, seu comburentur, et aqua pelantur, et que dicti salcicciarii nihilominus sint sub obedientia consulum macellariorum»].

Fig. 85 - Decree on the 'salcicciarii', from Cred. I, t. XXXVI preserved in the Archive of the Camera Capitolina, Rome), p. 12

As the original decree is very short, this is just the same text, in Latin, as the summary we found in the *Rubricellone*, in which it appears in its Italian translation.

And what about the second and third decrees? They are both stored in the 'credenzone' I, Vol. XIV and XV and they are mere copies, with minor changes, of the previous decree as they both date to the same October 7 1515:

Fig. 86 - The second and third decrees on the 'salcicciarii', from Cred. I, t. XIV (p. 18) and XV (f. 10r) preserved in the Archive of the Camera Capitolina, Rome

So what are the clues we can infer on the 'Norcini' from this decree issued in Rome in 1515?

Possibly, we may infer that here we are: perhaps, at the beginning of the sixteenth century, the 'Norcini' are actually appearing in Rome, though initially with the generic denomination of 'makers of sausages'.

How can we support this momentous guess? Let's try to investigate the whole matter in further detail.

Our starting point is that, in the year 1515, we find in Rome the 'salcicciari': men who prepare sausages by using pork meat. But who exactly were they?

They were not Butchers; they were not Grocers; they were not included in the regulated system of business and trade in Rome. At the time, they didn't have their own guild: they are not listed in the guild catalogues edited by Piazza and Rodocanachi, and no trace of any charters referring to them is to be found at the archive of the Camera Capitolina.

They seem to be some sort of independent players. But where do they come from?

Sure enough, they cannot practice their art freely: the Camera Capitolina, possibly urged by the Butchers themselves, on October 7 1515 stated that the 'makers of sausages' had to operate under the control of the Guild of Butchers. In addition to that, in Rome they were not permitted to slaughter pigs on their own: this was a job assigned to the Guild of Butchers only, and the 'salcicciari' must not dare invade their specific market.

It appears that the Camera Capitolina was called to settle some kind of controversy, or litigation: there were new players in Rome, they were making and selling pork products, namely sausages, in spite of the exclusive rights assigned to Butchers and Grocers.

So who were they? Were they our 'Norcini', the people from Norcia who had started migrating to Rome to sell their crafted pork meat?

This is the vision we propose in the present essay: we conjecture that, amid the 'salcicciari' that had started working in Rome from the second half of

the fifteenth century following the increase in food demand within the capital city, there might have been many people coming from Norcia. Possibly also from other places around Rome, but we think that many of them might have been a first, early wave of 'Norcini': a growing migration, which ultimately will lead, in the subsequent centuries, to the manifest presence in Rome of lots of people from Norcia, so much so that they will subsequently establish their own brotherhood and guild.

And, by the way, this is also what French historian Emmanuel Pierre Rodocanachi actually believed: he plainly included the above decrees — relating to the 'salcicciari', the makers of sausages — into the chapter he wrote on the 'Norcini'! For him, there was no difference between those early 'salcicciari' and the 'Norcini' of the later brotherhood and guild.

Certainly, we cannot assume that all the 'salcicciari' were 'Norcini'; nonetheless, it is most probable that many of the 'salcicciari' who were present in Rome at the beginning of the sixteenth century, and possibly since the second half of the fifteenth, were actually coming from Norcia to practice the art and craft in which they excelled: they were the initial ranks of a multitude of people that will subsequently become part of the urban space in the town of the Popes.

How can we support this sort of conjecture? Unfortunately no specific documentation is available on the 'Norcini' as butchers with relation to this very early period; nonetheless we can try to retrace, basing on common sense, the possible steps of the first 'Norcini' in Rome.

We will see that their early presence in Rome must have been marked by a series of issues, problems and market opportunities. Just like it seems to have occurred to our 'salcicciari'.

7.2 Retracing the early presence of the 'Norcini' in Rome: a reconstruction

7.2.1 The reasons behind the migration

Let's now try to put ourselves in the shoes of the first 'Norcini' in Rome, whose presence there — we suppose — might have materialised as early as the second half of the fifteenth century (while in Florence they were already present since the fourteenth century).

We do not have, in our hands, any direct sources that may tell us how things actually went; however, people migrations towards new social and economical environments have always been marked by a series of common issues, throughout the centuries and still in our present days. So we may just try to reconstruct what might have happened at the time, keeping an eye on what occurred for certain not many decades later (i.e. an established, recognised presence of the 'Norcini' in Rome), as it can be inferred from the later sources.

According to our assumption, supported by the historical data, the fifteenth century has been a century of change for both Norcia and Rome as to their relation about people migrating from the former to the latter, with the first appearance of the 'Norcini' and their settlement in the capital city of the Papal States. This process was the result of two intertwined demands, arising respectively from Rome and Norcia: two demands — crafted food on one side, work on the other — that found their mutual fulfilment with fully reciprocal convenience.

Fig. 87 - A vision on Rome in 1485 from a lost engraving of Francesco Rosselli, a painting dating to 1538 preserved at the Museo della Città, Palazzo San Sebastiano (Mantua, Italy)

So let's jump back to the second half of the fifteenth century, when Rome, under the push of enlightened Popes — Martin V, Eugene IV, Nicholas V and Pius II — was recovering its political stability and was entering a new phase of social and economical growth, with a marked increase in population, now heading towards 50,000 residents in town.

At the same time, Norcia was experiencing a period of economical development, with the establishment of growing relationships and trade connections with its neighbouring territories, including the Marches, the Kingdom of Naples and, of course, Florence and Rome. Public servants drawn from many local illustrious families were assigned to relevant administrative posts in the capital city.

In the fifteenth century the small town lying by the Sibillini Mountain Range was getting richer. But wealth was not for everybody. Many families, mainly employed in subsistence farming, were facing plain starvation in a land whose soil was not fertile enough to ensure their sustenance; winters were harsh and snowy, and for many months the available food was scarce, and farming almost impossible.

Fig. 88 - Castelluccio, a small hamlet in the neighborhood of Norcia, portrayed in a picture taken by British photographer Peter Paul Mackey between 1890 and 1905, but this vision would have been almost the same hundreds of years earlier

Therefore people needed to migrate. They already used to migrate to Florence, especially from the area of Preci and the Valle Castoriana. And Rome was there, too, less than a hundred miles away: a capital city, now living a phase of significant expansion, populated by tens of thousands of people, who needed services and — above all — food supplies. When seen from Norcia, Rome meant jobs, and the chance to earn a living so as to grant the sustenance of one's own family (just like Florence starting from a century earlier).

Thus, people began to move from Norcia to Rome. As they were already doing with respect to Florence.

On the basis of the economical considerations mentioned above, we can suppose that this migration flow to Rome could only start, at least over significant numbers of people, not before the second half of the fifteenth century (let's remember that during the previous century, the fourteenth, Rome had experienced a period of general deprivation and prolonged conflicts, with a reduced population and limited job opportunities for any would-be migrant workers, so that people preferred to leave for Florence).

In Rome, which was no primary manufacturing center as Florence was, there was no strong need for porters. Thus, the main skill that the people from Norcia could offer to the Roman market was butchery (actually, proficient, tasty, toothsome pig's butchery), together with other low-level abilities offered as handymen and jacks-of-all-trades. While, as for the Precian surgeons, which were already being appreciated and recognised in Florence in the wake of the earlier migration of 'Norcini' towards the Tuscan town, we still do not find a documented presence in Rome: the fame and initial success of the Precians seems to travel with the migrant from Norcia, and in this early phase the 'Norcini' in Rome are just beginning their historical course.

So this early, fifteenth-century migration from Norcia to Rome must have been initially marked by a seasonal character, typical of pig's butchery and matching the winter need for work experienced in snow-covered, frozen Norcia, with the 'Norcini' travelling to the city in winters and coming back to Norcia at Easters, as noted by Demetrio Andretti. Yet some of them possibly also began to open their specialised shops, the so called

'norcinerie': trading posts that will populate the landscape of downtown Rome for the subsequent centuries and up to our present days.

Possibly the first attractive factors active in Rome for migrants were those same fellow-citizens, belonging to the wealthiest families of Norcia, who, in this very period, had already settled in the town of the Popes in order to take on the administrative positions assigned to them within the papal bureaucracy. When in Rome, they could easily perceive the job opportunities that the city made available to lower-level workers such as butchers or handymen; furthermore, in Norcia, a very small town, everyone knew everyone else, even if they belonged to very different social classes. So the word was easily spread: in the capital city of the Papal States chances existed to earn money by selling food or providing simple services. So, in the second half of the fifteenth century, people just began to move to Rome, seasonally or permanently, in search of sustenance for their families.

But what sort of craft were the 'Norcini' bringing with them to Rome? What products, what services did they intend to sell on the Roman market?

Fundamentally, they began to propose their own specialised craft. They began to offer to the Romans their skilled, toothsome art. The art of making salted pork meat.

7.2.2 The proposition of a skilled craftsmanship

Demetrio Andretti, the chief magistrate of the 'Grascia' in Rome, wrote that «the first to introduce in Rome the art of salting Pork Meat were the Norcini».

Andretti, an expert in the field, provides us with the confirmation that the migration of the first 'Norcini' to Rome during the late fifteenth century was marked by the presence of this particular ability: an ability they brought with them to Rome from their mountainous homeland, where they had been nurturing it for centuries and centuries, possibly as far back as Roman times and across the High Middle Ages.

They were skilled in the preparation of cured pork meat: they knew how to salt and season the meat of pigs, so as to create luscious, palatable sausages and hams and salami.

Fig. 89 - The art of 'norcineria'

They brought this art and craft to Rome. And they soon became the masters of this most-sought, most specialised activity.

But why was their professional craft in the making of salted pork meat so coveted and, in the end, so hard to retrieve?

We will answer this question by reporting the illuminating words written by Luciano Giacchè in his article *Il paradosso della 'norcineria'* (in *Studi Umbri*, Vol. 11, no. 1, Perugia, 2019):

«The reason for resorting to a 'specialist' was due to the difficulty of a working procedure for which a specific, in-depth know-how was required as to the anatomy of the animal; in addition, a proven capability and an established expertise was needed with relation to both the slaughtering phase and the subsequent processing of the meat, which was turned into a manifold range of food products that were capable of preserving themselves over the time. The slaughtering of the pig, its cutting, the

preparation of the various portions, with no waste at all — even the bones were used to manufacture soap — all the listed aspects made up the steps of an elaborated process that included a sort of ritual elements in the sequence of operations and in the actions to be performed. This rendered the 'norcino' a peculiar mix between an officiant and a surgeon».

Thus the craft handled by the 'norcini' was not limited to butchery: they also knew how to treat the various portions of the slaughtered pig; they knew how to grind and spice and salt the parts needed to manufacture a sausage or a salami or a ham; furthermore, they knew whether to cover the processed meat with salt or insert it into a casing made of a section of intestine; and, finally, they knew how to append the final product to a rod in a ventilated room for seasoning, for the exact period of time required and with the performance of all the suitable actions needed for a perfect ageing, depending on weather conditions, humidity, time of the year, etc.

Actually, this is kind of an art. It is no easy process. You must know how to perform it. You must have been trained on that. Because you cannot just concoct: with cured meat, improvisation is not allowed.

In Norcia they knew how to do the job. They had woods and oaks and acorns; they had pigs; they had herbs and spices to flavour the meat; they had their mountains and the right weather and the cold winds that facilitated a perfect seasoning process. So, cured pork meat was their bread and butter.

So, when they began to migrate to Rome, during the fifteenth century, they brought their craft with them. And it was a thorough success, though they had to cope with the existing market players and find deals with them. As we will see in the next paragraphs.

7.2.3 What they found in town

Let's put ourselves again in the shoes of the first 'Norcini' in Rome. They were leaving their small town behind, at least for the winter season; and they intended to settle down on a temporary basis in the capital city to sell their products and skills.

What products were they bringing with them? Possibly a quantity of salted pork foodstuff, including sausages, salami and hams, already manufactured in their small farms at home. Those products — certainly in limited quantities, as they were carrying with them only part of their family production, poor as they were — represented the high-end, top-quality materialization of their art: most fragrant sausages, made out of the meat of pigs that have been raised amid the oaks of Norcia, feeding on flavored acorns and drinking the pure waters of the grassy plains lying at the foot of the Apennines. That was a display of their excellence, not so dissimilar from the sets of shining samples presented by salesmen.

Some of them might have brought with them one or more of those pigs, with the idea of slaughtering it in Rome and prepare fresh and salted products straight in the town of the Popes, ready for sale.

But, certainly, their main objective was to offer their know-how on salted pork meat to the main local players in Rome, the ones who used to deal with pigs: the members of the Guilds of Butchers and Grocers. They were eager to be given the chance to work for them, of course upon payment of a salary.

And what did they find on their first arrival in Rome?

In the previous paragraphs we saw that trade in Rome, from the late fifteenth century onwards, was arranged in guilds and brotherhoods, who sold foodstuff and goods to the local residents under strict centralised control. When the 'Norcini' began to settle in Rome, permanently or seasonally, they found parties of men practising specific arts and crafts who were starting to get together within organised groups, which in turn were giving birth to guilds.

So, the the 'Norcini' were not beginning to practice their art in a desert or in a free-trade environment. They had to deal with the existing, powerful groups of traders, trying to find their own space within the limitations imposed by the presence of exclusive market domains, being defined in writing through the various guilds' charters.

Fig. 90 - Rome and its busy streets in *La via Rua, in fondo il Portico d'Ottavia*, a watercolour by Ettore Roesler Franz dating to 1888

They were not entering an empty space. Instead, they found — as we already know — two specific groups. Two powerful Guilds. The Butchers and the Grocers.

And certainly, as it always happens in any epoch and place, they did not like those rustic newcomers at all.

Butchery was the exclusive domain of the Guild of Butchers ('Macellari'); salted pork meat made up another closed market owned by the Guild of Grocers ('Pizzicaroli'). Both represented large communities, and they both were significantly influential in Rome.

So the newly-arrived 'Norcini' certainly could not just begin to slaughter their pigs or freely sell their toothsome sausages: they would have incurred the wrath of the existing professionals, and also exorbitant fines and

endless litigations before the papal courts, as we will see later in the present paper.

So how could the newly-arrived 'Norcini' enter this market, already assigned to other players?

Let's try to imagine how this could have happened, by also recalling what Demetrio Andretti wrote in his paper on the 'Grascia' and considering the presence in Rome of new people called 'salcicciari'.

7.2.4 Grocers, Butchers and those annoying 'salcicciari'

When increasing numbers of 'Norcini' began to establish themselves in Rome — encouraged by their aristocratic fellow-citizens already in town and employed within the papal institutions and administration, and also following the spread by word of mouth, in Norcia, of the news about the availability of growing work opportunities in Rome — they soon found out that pigs could not be slaughtered if not by the Butchers in their licensed slaughterhouses, and salted pork meat could not be sold if not by the Grocers. As we can read in the guilds' charters, heavy fines were applied to wrongdoers, and we can bet that the Roman professionals would not restrain from reporting those rustic, illegal butchers and traders to the papal constabulary.

So what could the 'Norcini' do in town?

If they really intended to work in Rome, the only way was to find an employment with the Butchers or the Grocers.

And, on common-sense grounds, it is what actually happened. Late fifteenth-century migrants from Norcia to Rome just began to work, often seasonally, with the members of the existing guilds.

But why would Butchers or Grocers wish to employ those migrants coming from a mountainous, remote countryside?

As for the Butchers, because the 'Norcini' perfectly knew how to slaughter pigs.

And, as for the Grocers, because the 'Norcini' were proficient, to say the least, in the art of processing salted pork meat. Let's recall what Demetrio Andretti wrote: «the first to introduce in Rome the art of salting Pork Meat were the Norcini» (in Italian «li primi che hanno introdotta in Roma l'arte di salare le Carni Porcine sono stati li Norcini»).

The 'Norcini' were skilled. The 'Norcini' were used to fatigue and worked in a reliable, productive way. So the 'Norcini' began to be considered as markedly useful. They helped Butchers and Grocers earn more money.

With the Grocers, the match was easily won since the very beginning: the 'Norcini' just did what the Grocers were not able to do with their same ability; so, most probably, the Grocers in Rome just began to hire those new migrants so as to prepare the most palatable sausages, salami and hams. This is totally confirmed by our expert, Demetrio Andretti, who reports that the powerful Guild of Grocers took full advantage of the services provided by the 'Norcini' to process sausages for them, as they were unable to do the work by themselves:

«Without them [the 'Norcini', editor's note], the Grocers [in Rome] would never be able to skillfully process that sort of meat; so they necessarily need to avail themselves of the Norcini, who year after year use to come to Rome and work the said meat».

portano à Roma ad aprirne Bottega, senza niente considerare ingannati dal lucro, che li primi che hanno introdotta in Roma l'arte di salare le Carni Porcine sono stati li Norcini, e che senza di questi neppure essi Pizzicaroli potrebbero ad uso di arte farne il lavoriero, dovendosi necessariamente valersi dei Norcini, che di anno in anno vengono a lavorargli dette Carni. Questo intento de' Pizzicaroli gli è in parte riuscito valendosi in particolare delli con-

Fig. 91 - The excerpt on 'Norcini' and 'Pizzicaroli' (grocers) from Demetrio Andretti's *Trattato sopra il Presidentato della Grascia di Roma* as presented in the article *L'arte norcina dall'Umbria a Roma — L'impatto, storico, sociale ed economico* by Giuseppe Cruciani, included in the book *I norcini e Roma — L'arte della norcineria dall'Umbria alla Dominante* edited by Elio di Michele (Roma, 2013), p. 35

[In the original Italian text: «Senza di questi neppure essi Pizzicaroli potrebbero ad uso di arte farne il lavoriero, dovendosi necessariamente valersi dei Norcini, che di anno in anno vengono a lavorargli dette Carni»].

Certainly enough not all the 'Norcini' were available to work as employees for Butchers and Grocers.

Many of them, especially the seasonal ones, just came to Rome to sell their products directly to the Roman populace, trying to evade all rules so as to avoid any submission to the existing market players, and earn quickly a living before going back to Norcia and their families. We can also suppose that this sort of behaviour was put in place not only by the 'Norcini' but also by many other rural people coming from different territories of the Papal States, looking for easy sales in the capital city (we find manifest references to all this in many guilds' charters and public announcements that explicitly sanctioned illegal trading carried out by farmers and shepherds outside the authorised market places in Rome).

As to pork meat, the easiest marketable products were fresh sausages ('salicce' in Italian), involving a simple, fast manufacturing phase, and readily placed amid local consumers in Rome. That's why we find, in 1515, all those 'salicciari' (makers of sausages) going unrestrained around the city, belonging to no guild at all, in spite of all local regulations and with a patent infringement of the rights specifically granted to the Guild of Butchers.

Fig. 92 - Fresh sausages flavored with different spices

In this unacceptable situation, the Butchers were forced to resort to the Camera Capitolina in order to obtain a decree concerning the regulation of the activities of those annoying 'salcicciari': from then on, they would be allowed to sell only sausages made of pork meat, and would be totally subject to the Guild of Butchers.

So in our conjecture — in full accordance with Rodocanachi's surmise — the 'salcicciari' who had popped up in a decree issued by the Council of the Camera Capitolina in 1515 were mainly including people occasionally coming from Norcia to Rome to sell simple pork products, namely sausages made of fresh meat: a kind of maverick butchers, who did not want to adhere to the system of guilds that was in place in Rome. They only wanted to market their products freely and without engaging themselves with any existing organisation in the capital city: nonetheless, after a period of loose operations, they were eventually 'caught' by the system and forced to report to the Guild of Butchers and their officially-formalised scheme, which included authorisations, licenses, duties and prohibitions, obedience to the Consuls, fees to be paid, etc.

Therefore, here we are. At the end of the fourteenth century and in the subsequent decades, we begin to find traces of the presence of a number of 'Norcini' in Rome, possibly to be identified with the 'salcicciari' in this first, early period. A few of their aristocratic fellow-citizens were already here, working in the papal administration; but the 'Norcini' as butchers, most probably, began to represent a tangible reality in downtown Rome in this very years: a limited, seasonal presence at the beginning, mainly working with the Roman Butchers as mere assistants, and with the Grocers as specific experts in the processing of salted pork meat.

But all this was about to change. The 'Norcini' in Rome were gaining momentum, as their craft was turning into an appreciated, popular art.

People liked what they were able to do with pork meat. And began to ask for more. Directly to them.

7.3 The sixteenth century: the consolidation of the presence of the people from Norcia in Rome

7.3.1 The magnificent renovation of Rome

We are now entering sixteenth-century Rome: a city which was still experiencing a notable growth process — only temporarily interrupted by the grievous occurrence of the Sack of Rome in 1527 — up to the end of the century, when its population will reach 100.000 residents.

What sort of urban environment were the 'Norcini' now living in?

The sixteenth century was the time of the 'renovatio urbis': a vision which actively pursued the restoration of the greatness and power of the capital of a former Empire, now the illustrious capital city of the Papal States.

This strategical vision was initially elaborated by Pope Julius II Della Rovere, elected in 1503. The new ruler of the Papal States intended to re-establish the full political and military control of the Holy See over all the territories which were included in the Patrimony of Saint Peter. In this framework, the might of both ancient and contemporary Rome was to be celebrated by promoting a comprehensive, munificent activity of patronage of all artistic domains, including visual arts, literature and architecture, with the development of large construction projects which were designed with the aim to change the very shape of Rome.

The Papal Basilica of Saint Peter in the Vatican was at the center of this challenging renovation programme: the old church built under the rule of Emperor Constantine the Great in the fourth century was demolished and totally re-built, on a gigantic scale, by architectural masters of the Italian Renaissance such as Donato Bramante, Raphael and Michelangelo. And Julius II did not limit to the development and transformation of the area of the Vatican: he wanted to re-draw the connections between the papal headquarters and the other districts of the city by cutting new fundamental streets like Via Giulia and Via della Lungara, with the construction of aristocratic buildings belonging to the wealthiest families of Rome along the new urban routes.

The daring plans on the restoration of the magnificence of Rome were embraced and even strengthened by Pope Leo X Medici, Julius II's successor. Under his pontificate the artistic geniuses of Raphael, Giuliano da Sangallo, Antonio da Sangallo, Jacopo Sansovino, Baldassarre Peruzzi, Giulio Romano were unleashed on the city, while the cult of ancient Roman remnants and ruins was spreading among the affluent members of the most aristocratic families. New lavish palaces were built all around downtown Rome, inspired to classical models and full of antiquities dating back to the centuries of the Roman Empire. Again, new streets were created in Rome, especially in the northern district of Via di Ripetta and Piazza del Popolo.

The bloody Sack of Rome in 1527 put momentarily on hold this whole development strategy; nonetheless, a few years later works were resumed under the papacy of Paul III Farnese, who entrusted to Michelangelo the design of Piazza del Campidoglio and the full responsibility for the ongoing project of the Basilica of St. Peter.

Finally, during the closing quarter of the sixteenth century, Pope Sixtus V Peretti will act as a most visionary planner of the new urban structure of Rome: starting from the complete reconstruction of the Palace of the Lateran, he will trace the new Via Felice and Via Sistina, literally crossing the entire city from the new apostolic building to Piazza del Popolo; he will also have the former Via Papale, from the Lateran to the Colosseum, enlarged and paved, thus creating a further route between two main locations in Rome: veritable arteries that nourished the internal life of the whole capital town of the Papal States, together with the new aqueduct of Acqua Felice (from the very name of the Pope, Felice Peretti), completed in 1586.

This is the city to which the people from Norcia, in search of work opportunities to earn their living, are continuing to move in the course of the sixteenth century: a town at the center of the world, inhabited by tens of thousands of residents where the considerable riches owned by the Pope and the many affluent families which live in the capital city are being used to carry out extensive construction works, with the renovation of infrastructures and the building of new lavish palaces.

And there's also another peculiar aspect of Rome — one we already signalled in a previous paragraph: the city is a town of foreigners, be they

pilgrims and travellers or wealthy ambassadors to the papal court, with their families and retinues. The French writer and philosopher Michel de Montaigne, who travelled to Rome in 1580, noted down a few words on this very peculiarity in his *Journal du voyage en Italie*:

«Rome is the most open cities in the world; here being a foreigner and a stranger from a different nation is not considered at all; in fact, Rome is, by its very nature, a city scattered with strangers, and all of them feel like at home. Its King encircles the entire Christendom with his authority».

[In the original French text: «[Rome] c'est la plus commune ville du monde, et ou l'etrangeté et difference de nation le considere le moins; car de sa nature c'est une ville rappiecée d'etrangers; chacun y est come chez soi. Son Prince embrasse toute la chretienté de son autorité»].

JOURNAL
DU VOYAGE

DE

MICHEL DE MONTAIGNE

EN ITALIE,

Par la Suisse & l'Allemagne en 1580 & 1581.

Avec des Notes par M. DE QUERLON.

TOME SECOND.

A R O M E ;

Et se trouve à PARIS,

Chez LE JAY, Libraire, rue Saint-Jacques,
au Grand-Corneille.

M. DCC. LXXIV.

Je disois des commodités de Rome, entr'autres, que c'est la plus commune ville du monde, & ou l'etrangeté & difference de nation le considere le moins; car de sa nature c'est une ville rappiecée d'etrangers; chacun y est come chés soi. Son Prince embrasse toute la chretienté de son autorité; sa principale jurisdiction

Fig. 93 - The cosmopolitan society of sixteenth-century Rome from Michel de Montaigne's *Journal du voyage en Italie* (Paris, 1774), Vol. II, p. 60

So, as the 'Norcini' were continuing to come to Rome during the sixteenth century, they were finding a growing marketplace, full of opportunities for people who knew how to process the meat of pigs, with the preparation of sausages and salami for both the populace and the most refined Roman

houses. Precian surgeons will be increasingly registered in the official lists of authorised practitioners. And lot of space was also available as to lower-level jobs, like manual labourers or handymen.

However, before accounting for the 'Norcini' in Rome during the sixteenth century, we must mention the illustrious names of the many eminent persons, born in Norcia, who had reached distinguished positions in Rome, at the court of the Pope or even as celebrated professionals. They were retracing the steps of their fellow-citizens who, during the previous century, had been senators and notaries and captains in the capital city, as we illustrated in a previous paragraph.

So, it is not only a matter of butchers. In Rome, there were prominent people from Norcia. Let's see who they were.

7.3.2 Prominent people from Norcia in sixteenth-century Rome

In the capital city of the 'renovatio urbis', a town that was changing its very shape with the construction of new streets and magnificent aristocratic buildings, the presence of people from Norcia was increasingly manifest. And some of them reached the summit of their professional careers right there, in Rome, at the service of the Popes.

The most remarkable instance of a totally successful progression within the Roman society and the papal court is given by Francesco Fusconi, whose figure we already illustrated in our previous essay *The Precian Surgical School: an astounding European-wide success originated from a small Apennine hamlet* (2026, p. 228-232). Born in Norcia at the end of the fifteenth century, he lived his life amid the affluent members of the aristocratic class of Rome, as the chief physician of three different Popes and doctor of choice for the most powerful Roman families.

His professional success was so complete and his fees so expensive that he became a man of exceeding wealth. In the book *Degli architri pontifici (On the papal physicians)*, written in the eighteenth century by Luigi Gaetano Marini, president and custodian of the Vatican Apostolic Library, it is reported that Fusconi was referred to by another renowned physician,

Amato Lusitano, as «medico famigeratissimo» («medical doctor of immense fame»); and that a further colleague, Paolo Giovio, a bishop, man of letter and medical doctor, mentioned him as the «pecunioso Norcia» («the person from Norcia who is rolling in money»).

Fig. 94 - The renown and personal wealth of Francesco Fusconi, from Luigi Gateano Marini's *Degli archiatri pontifici* (Rome, 1784), Vol. 1, p. 325 and 326

His personal wealth was actually so considerable as to allow him to own a whole palace at the Piazza Farnese; in it he stored an astounding collection of valuable marble statues dating to the centuries of the Roman Empire: an experience that was open to external visitors for their enjoyment and wonder. One of the most important pieces of his dispersed collection — a piece that was considered, in the fifteenth century, as one of the most charming antique statues in Rome — is now exhibited at the Vatican Museums: the 'Meleager of the Belvedere', which was purchased by Pope Clement XIV in the eighteenth century.

Fig. 95 - A beautiful Roman statue that once belonged to Francesco Fusconi: the *Meleager of the Belvedere*, dating to the second century A.D. (Vatican Museums, Rome)

Another significant example involving a Norcia-born, high-rank member of sixteenth-century's Roman society was Laerzio Cherubini. During the last quarter of this century he was a renowned lawyer at the Curia (the Tribunal) in Rome: he actually was one of the many successful people from Norcia who had made a brilliant career at the Papal court, holding the top position of 'Conservatore' in the year 1601. He was also the editor of a major collection of papal decrees (*Bullarium sive Collectio diversarum constitutionum multorum Pontif. a Gregorio Septimo usque ad S. D. N. Sixtum Quintum Pontificem Opt. Max.*, 1586). As we will later see, he will be the principal promoter of the roman brotherhood of the St. Benedict and St. Scholastica, whose members mainly were people from Norcia.

D. Laertij Cherubini de Nursia Iureconsulti.

Fig. 96 - Laerzio Cherubini's *Bullarium sive Collectio diversarum constitutionum multorum Pontif. a Gregorio Septimo usque ad S. D. N. Sixtum Quintum Pontificem Opt. Max.*, (Rome, 1586)

Fig. 97 - A detail of Michelangelo Merisi da Caravaggio's *Death of the Virgin*, 1605-1606 (Louvre Museum, Paris)

His wealth, too, was particularly remarkable. And, at the beginning of the seventeenth century, he could place a commission with the great painter Caravaggio, at the time already a celebrated artist, for a painting to be put in his family chapel at the Church of Santa Maria della Scala, in the district of Trastevere. Unfortunately, Caravaggio's work — *Death of the Virgin* — could not be exposed in the said chapel out of the popular, real-life rendering of the corpse of the Holy Mary: an artistic interpretation that was considered by many as unholy and intolerable. This outstanding masterwork, full of a sense of grievous sadness for the death of a woman who is totally human to the artist's eyes, is now exhibited at the Louvre Museum in Paris.

We also want to recall the figure of Girolamo Catena, a scholar and a man of letter, born in Norcia, who in Rome became the appreciated secretary to various cardinals and subsequently the Secretary of the Council under Pope Sixtus V. He was the author of a celebrated biographic essay on Pope Pius V, and his learned letters show his acquaintance with a number of princes and princesses of his time, including the Grand Duchess of Tuscany, the Duke of Mantua, the Prince of Massa, and others.

ultimamente per la feruitù mia verso di lei da quel tempo incominciata, che io famigliar diuenni di F. Clemete Moniliano Cardinal d'Araceli, & cōtinuata poi d'anno in anno fin qui, che hò hauuto il carico di secretario della Consulta di V.Santità. Tutto quello,

Fig. 98 - Origin and posts in Rome of Girolamo Catena from his *Vita del gloriosissimo Papa Pio Quinto*, (Rome, 1587), p. 3 and 4

And finally, as to sixteenth-century Rome, we cannot omit to mention the presence of a number of surgeons and medical practitioners, listed in the registries of the Holy See and recorded as originating from Norcia, the small castles set under its direct rule, and other settlements scattered along the valley of the Nera river: a rank of experts in specific medical practices coming from the hometown of St. Benedict and its surroundings, which we have presented in full detail in our previous essay dedicated to the 'Norcini' as Precian surgeons (*The Precian Surgical School*, 2026, p. 223-228). The list was extracted from the registry of the general prothomedicus of the Holy See, Petrus Antonius Contugius, written in 1552, as reported by Antonino Bertolotti in his article *Medicine, surgery and pharmacy in Rome in the sixteenth century* (1885):

«From 1540 [a license is granted] to Lorenzo from the countryside of Norcia, for surgery, hernial incision, bladder stones, treatment of eye diseases, i.e. cataract... From 1551 to Cristofaro Castellano of Norcia for all types of surgery... In 1554 for six months to Arcangelo Mensurato from the countryside of Norcia, surgeon, for the treatment of syphilis, urinary gravel, cataract, hernia... From 1557, a four-year license to Orazio of Piedivalle from Norcia in minor surgery... In 1561 to Paolo son of Pasquale of Norcia for castration, bladder and kidney stones, hernia, cataract... In 1561 to Giovanni the son of Pietro Moschetto from Castel Vecchio of Norcia (ulcer, cataract)... From 1562 to Giacomo Scachi from the castle of Preci in Norcia for the treatment of ulcer, fistulae, gangrene, hernia, cataract and other diseases... From 1562 to Saulo of Norcia, the son of Pascale, surgeon, for phlebotomy, hernia, stones, cataracts, etc... In 1563 Lucido di Dionigi da Norcia... In 1570 to Girolamo Chaos of Norcia for bladder stones, hernia, cataract and cleft lip...».

So, such was Rome in the sixteenth century: a capital city that was undergoing a relevant renovation process, and in which many people from Norcia had their chance to advance their own social position, up to truly significant outcomes, which rendered them so wealthy as to afford to own a masterpiece of Roman art like the *Meleager*, or even commission a new extraordinary work of art to the most celebrated painter of Rome, Caravaggio.

Fig. 99 - Surgeons from Norcia to Rome, from *Medicine, surgery and pharmacy in Rome in the sixteenth century* by Antonino Bertolotti, from *Il Buonarroti*, Series III, Vol, II, VI (p. 194, 196 and 198) and VII (Rome, 1885, p. 227, 231, 232, 233, 234 and 237)

But — while addressing the most famed, most affluent people coming from Norcia and living by the Popes — we are almost forgetting our 'Norcini' in Rome, the butchers and experts in the salting of pork meat. Where were they during the sixteenth century?

They were also there, in Rome. And their presence, too, was becoming increasingly visible, but still with mixed characters. As we will see in the next paragraph.

7.3.3 The 'Norcini' in Rome during the sixteenth century: the butchers

As we saw earlier, sixteenth-century Rome was an urban environment marked by a growing population, the funding of new public and private construction works, and the presence of an extended class of wealthy families and foreigners. Affluent people from Norcia had settled in town and were making their brilliant careers. So the attractive power of the city for people in search of new markets and job opportunities was certainly remarkable, spurring many 'Norcini' — to be intended both as butchers and less-skilled workers and traders — towards Rome.

For sure, following the first early, poorly-documented phase dating back to the fifteenth century and the beginning of the sixteenth — during which

some sort of 'salcicciari', possibly an early presence of 'Norcini', were active in the capital city of the Papal States — in the second half of the sixteenth century the 'Norcini' were indisputably there, and fully established in downtown Rome: part of them on a seasonal basis, and part with their own shops, open throughout the year.

How can we be sure of that? Because, at the end of the century, we find an incontestable proof of the fact that the 'Norcini' are there, in Rome, as butchers; and — even more far-reaching — it seems that pigs in the capital city are slaughtered only, or mainly, by them (even though this assertion on a supposed exclusivity held by the 'Norcini' will have to be scaled back).

So here is the first official reference to the 'Norcini' as butchers of pigs in Rome: a most important document within the framework of the present research.

On November, 16th 1593 Cardinal Enrico Caetani, camerlengo of the Holy Roman Church, issued an edict in which he provided a clarification on a previous decree concerning the opening of slaughtering houses in Rome. As to what related specifically to the slaughtering of pigs, he clearly commanded as follows:

«To avoid any doubt whether the 'Norcini' Butchers who slaughter Pigs are included in the said Decree — because they are not, as they are allowed to open their slaughterhouses only in a specific season, when the price is set and they have the full right to work pork meat — out of the present public Edict [...] we declare that the said slaughterhouses for pigs, which will open during the licensed season, are not included in the said Decree [...] and so we command, under the said Edicts, that they [the 'Norcini'] must not be disturbed, nor prevented from opening their slaughterhouses of the said meat»].

[In the original Italian text: «Perché non si possa dubitare se i Macellari Norcini che macellano la Carne Porcina, s'intendano compresi sotto il detto Bando, come non sono, poi che essi non possono aprire il macello se non alla staggione, che si dà il prezzo, et la licenza di far la Porcina: per il presente pubblico Editto [...] dechiariamo, che detti macelli di Porco, che s'apriranno in Roma in detta staggione non se intendano compresi nel

Bando suddetto [...], et perciò comandiamo che, per vigore di detti Bandi, non siano molestati, ne impediti a fare i loro Macelli della Carne sodetta»].

Io senza licenza: perche non si possa dubitare se i Macellari Norcini che macellano la Carne Porcina, s'intendano compresi sot-

Fig. 100 - Decree on the 'Norcini' as butchers dating to 1593, from Cred. XIII, t. XXX preserved at the Archive of the Camera Capitolina (Rome), p. 105

«The 'Norcini' Butchers who slaughter Pigs», says the Cardinal Camerlengo (in Italian: «i Macellari Norcini che macellano la Carne Porcina»).

Thus, here are the 'Norcini', in Rome, in their full role as butchers of pork meat.

They slaughter pigs. And pigs can be slaughtered only after the month of December, so the 'Norcini', who only work during the winter season, are not subject to the decrees issued for the generality of Butchers. In addition to that, it seems that only the 'Norcini' can, or use to, slaughter pigs in Rome. So here the Butchers appear to be already excluded from this business (but we will see later than the Grocers are still in, even though they are not mentioned in this specific edict).

The above decree dates to 1593, when the sixteenth century was nearly over; however, this is to be considered as a sort of photographic shot of a situation that certainly was not occurring in the year 1593, but was the outcome of a long development phase that was in place since the very beginning of the sixteenth century, when an increasing flow of people from Norcia was migrating, seasonally or permanently, to Rome. In the course of a century, the 'Norcini' had won for themselves a remarkable market space in Rome with relation to pork meat. And they were there to stay.

A confirmation of the fact that the process was long and gradual is provided to us by the words written by Demetrio Andretti around 1750: «In old times, the slaughtering of the Black Animals [meaning the pigs, editor's note], as to what concerns fresh Meat, was carried out by the Guild of Butchers, and, as to what concerns Salted meat, those were processed by the Guild of Norcini, who from season to season used to come to this purpose from the Mountains to Rome. [...] Later, the Butchers themselves just gave up the pig slaughtering business: so this activity was only carried out by the Norcini and, rather than the Butchers, by the Grocers». At the time of Andretti, the 'Norcini' had been in Rome for around three centuries: they had started their business by processing salted pork meat, and later had superseded the Butchers in the slaughtering of pigs, an activity that they continued to share with the Grocers.

But did those 'Norcini' butchers run their own shops? In 1750 Andretti will write that «[The Norcini] when the season is right, as I said, travel to Rome to open their Shops». But were those shops already open at the end of the sixteenth century, or even before?

The answer is yes, because we also find other mentions which imply that the 'Norcini' were already well established in Rome, as they were owners of goods and properties, possibly shops and residential houses located at the very center of Rome.

In fact, many 'Norcini' appear in the documentation produced by the Council of the Thirty Notaries Public of the Capitol (in Italian, the Collegio of the Trenta Notai Capitolini), established by Pope Sixtus V in 1586. Scholars have been perusing the many volumes which contain the instruments and deeds recorded by notaries such as Giacomo Filippo Gilardi, who worked at the so-called Office no. 5, with branches in the

Rione Parione and Rione St. Eustachio (just near the Pantheon). In the year 1593, Gilardi drafted and signed many inventories of goods and properties belonging to various craftsmen, including a number of 'Norcini' (see catalogue edited by Orietta Verdi *et al.*, Rome, 2024, p. 24).

Archivio di Stato di Roma		Trenta notai capitolini		Ufficio 5		Istromenti	
Trenta Notai Capitolini		Vol.	Notaio	Estremi cronologici	Dorso	Carte	Note
Ufficio 5 (1554 - 1887) Voll. 1 - 785 Inventario A cura e con la direzione scientifica di Orietta Verdi Introduzione Orietta Verdi Schedatura volumi, rilevamento dati e indici Daniele Balduzzi Schedatura buste della serie "Testamenti chiusi" Luigi Arbia Revisione delle schede e dei testi Orietta Verdi Trattamento informatico e layout Daniele Balduzzi		32	Gilardus Jacobus Philippus	1593, lug. - dic.	Secunda Pars Instrumentorum 1593 Jacobus Gilardus notarius	1-464	Volume di atti del notaio Gilardi; sul dorso è scritto erroneamente "Grilard[us]". Il notaio Gilardi non sottoscrive gli atti; al suo posto Antonio Nardi sottoscrive con la formula "pro Jacobo Philippo Gilardi notario" i mandati per il Secondo Collaterale (cc. 62r, 328r). Si segnalano atti, soprattutto inventari di beni, di artigiani (pizzicaroli, molti dei quali esercenti a Macel de Corvi, norcini, macellari, ortolani, fruttaroli, fornai, sellari, funari, sarti, candelottari): inventario di Antonio Salvi, sarto, proprietario di tre case e botteghe "nel rione di S. Angelo nella strada di Catinari per andare alli Mattei, contigue apresso alli beni del signor Jacomo della Porta, nella quale una habita mastro Hyeronimo scolaro, l'altra mastro (...) catinaro et l'altra mastro Francesco coramaro", quattro case in Trastevere "passata porta Settignana" nel vicolo del Riario, due botteghe in Borgo "attaccate alla Traspontina vecchia" oltre ad un canneto ed una vigna (c. 63r). Porzia Salomonìa, autrice di molte transazioni in questo e nei precedenti volumi, acquista novemila rondini "bone raze", che si trovavano nell' "arundinetum in castro Nazzani", di proprietà di Giuliano Desideri, con la clausola di trasportarle "in porto et ripa fluminis" (c. 280r).

Fig. 101 - Instruments and deeds recorded by notary Giacomo Filippo Girardi in 1593, from *Inventory of the Thirty Notaries Public of the Capitol*, edited by Orietta Verdi (Rome, 2024), p. 24

So we can confidently state that at the end of the sixteenth century the 'Norcini' were permanently and durably present in Rome, and they were known as butchers of pigs, being recognised as such in the official edicts issued by the Papal States. And they carried out pig slaughtering activities instead of the Roman butchers, who dedicated themselves to the processing of other types of meat (cow, lamb).

But were those 'Norcini' all butchers and experts in the processing of cured pork meat? The answer is no.

There were other sorts of 'Norcini' in Rome: workers marked by lower skills, and seasonal migrants. As we will see in the next paragraph.

7.3.4 The 'Norcini' in Rome during the sixteenth century: the low-skilled workers and the fishmongers

Not all the people coming from Norcia and present in Rome were 'Norcini', meaning butchers and seasoners of pork meat, or even surgeons. There were also low-skilled, manual workers, who remained in the capital city on a temporary basis only, possibly to earn a living for their families when their farming activities at home could not be carried out, waiting for the right season of the year.

We find a hint to their presence in a letter written by Cardinal Vitellozzo Vitelli to his colleague Carlo Carafa on December, 1st 1557. In the letter Vitelli signals that «today, the Benevento [Bartolomeo Camerario, prefect of the food supplies, who was born in Benevento, southern Italy] issued an announcement in which he ordered all the people from Amatrice [a town in the Apennines not far from Norcia] to leave the town, following another announcement that asked all 'norcini' and people of that sort to leave Rome, out of the current shortage of bread» (in the original Italian language: «Hoggi il Benevento ha mandato un bando che tutti quelli della Matrice si vadino con Dio, havendone già mandato un altro prima che li norcini et ogni altra sorta di simil gente si partissero, dicendo di far questo per la carestia del pane»). The letter is contained in manuscript Vat. Lat. 12086 preserved at the Vatican Apostolic Library (folium 371r) and is reported by Alberto Aubert in his article *La politica annonaria di Roma durante il pontificato di Paolo IV*, (in *Archivio Storico Italiano — Deputazione di Storia Patria della Toscana*, n. 528, a. CXLIV, 1986, III, p. 284).

What sort of 'Norcini' was Cardinal Vitelli referring to? Basing on the letter's content, it is not probable that they might have worked in the food sector as butchers or experts in salted pork meat. The predicament described in the letter relates to a shortage of food in town, so we can imagine that the intention of the prefect Bartolomeo Camerario just was to expel from the city a class of seasonal, low-skill workers that only added to the burden of hungry populace which needed bread and food; there was no gain in having them in town in time of food shortage, so they were openly invited to leave.

In the subsequent years, the 'Norcini' also appear in Rome as sellers of foodstuff different from pork.

In an eighteenth-century document included in the Fondo Camerale II — Sezione 10 *Arti e mestieri* preserved at the Archivio di Stato di Roma (see the exhaustive catalogue edited by Claudio De Dominicis, 2005, p. 57-58), we find a reference to an agreement established between the Guild of Fish Dealers and the 'Norcini' (still not mutually associated within their own guild) on March, 1st 1583: the butchers from Norcia pledged to pay an annual amount of money to the Chapel of St. Andrew, lying in the Church of Sant'Angelo in Pescheria and dedicated to Roman fishmongers, so as to be granted the right to sell fish on their own (a specific right they will restate in their Charters in 1677 and later with a further agreement in 1699).

Claudio De Dominicis

INVENTARIO DEL FONDO
CAMERALE II
N. 10 - *Arti e Mestieri*
PRESSO L'ARCHIVIO DI STATO DI ROMA
CON APPENDICE ED INDICE ANALITICO

1737 (5 aprile) [23 gennaio] - (manoscritto e stampa) Causa dell'Università dei Venditori di Pesce contro quella dei Norcini ("Romana Juris Cottiandi", o "Romana Cottiationis Avium") per la vendita privativa degli uccelli ("avium") ed altri animali silvestri, come stabilito dallo Statuto confermato da Urbano VIII (14 giugno 1636) e da Innocenzo XI. Si fa riferimento ai cap. 6, 16 e 23 dello Statuto dei Pescivendoli. Il cap. 23 dello Statuto dei Pescivendoli prevede che, oltre al pesce, si possano cottiare "tutte sorti d'Animali silvestri spettanti alla detta Università, cioè Porci, Cervi, Capri, Lepori, Fagiani, Starne, Palombi, Palombelle, Tordi, Storni, et altri Ucelli

minuti". Testimoni del 1734 affermano che questo si faceva fino a 30-40 anni prima. Il cap. 15 dello Statuto dei Norcini, confermato da Innocenzo X (1677), stabilisce "che gl'Uccellami Salvaticini, e Tartufi non possono comprarsi dell'Huomini dell'arte nostra, se non che nelle Piazze, o Alberghi eccettuati li Cottij, li quali si possono fare in casa propria del Cottiatore, e dove gli sarà più comodo". I Norcini, sin dal 1 marzo 1583, si erano impegnati al pagamento annuale di sc. 15 alla Cappella di S. Andrea. Nel 1699 ("di presente sotto d.a Università di Norcia vengono compresi anco Casciani, Spoletini, e Rocchetani") i Norcini si accordano per avere "facoltà, et autorità di vendere il Pesce alli Banchi, e Pietre, e fare il solito Bollettino a quelli che lo vanno vendendo per Roma, senza che la d.a Università de Pescivendoli possa, ne debba ingerirsene, né che abbia sopra di loro autorità, o jus alcuno, né possa in qualsivoglia modo in futuro per qualsivoglia via, o concessione acquistarlo, intendendosi con questa totalmente divisa, e separata una dall'altra".

Roma, 2005
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Fig. 102 - The first agreement between the 'Norcini' and the Guild of Fish Dealers dating to 1583, as mentioned in Claudio De Dominicis' *Inventario del Fondo Camerale II - No. 10 Arti e mestieri presso l'Archivio di Stato di Roma* (Rome, 2005), p. 57 and 58

What does it all mean?

It means that, in the course of the sixteenth century, the 'Norcini' are in Rome: they own properties, they cut deals, they sell food. They are identified with their collective name — 'Norcini' — even though they still do not belong to any guild (their brotherhood will be established many

years later, in 1615). But what we begin to understand at this point of our research is that the 'Norcini' were not butchers or expert in pork meat salting only. Many of them, who were migrating to Rome out of necessity, adapted themselves to doing many low-skill jobs, thus turning into fishmongers (we will see that they also used to sell game and truffles), peddlers, manual laborers, and even handymen.

Can we provide further evidences of such a scenario?

Yes indeed. And the evidence will come from a totally unexpected direction, giving us a vision of what the 'Norcini' were and meant for the populace of Rome.

Let's go and consider the above evidences. To carry out this task, we are about to tread the planks of the stages of sixteenth-century theaters in Rome.

Thus let the show begin. With the 'Norcini' as guest stars.

7.3.5 The 'Norcini' in Rome during the sixteenth century: the theatrical appearance

Butchers, fishmongers, surgeons or peddlers, it is now apparent that the 'Norcini' begin to represent a persistent presence in central Rome; so much so that that their country-bumpkin, unmannered figure is readily portrayed on stage: the 'Norcino' will immediately become a funny, laughable character in farcical plays whose setting is sixteenth-century Rome.

The most significant instance of this is provided by *Injustices of love (I torti amorosi* in Italian), a comedy written by Cristoforo Castelletti, a Roman playwright, in 1581.

At that time, the 'Norcino' is fully known to the audiences of Rome, as they happen to meet him — and many of his fellow-citizens — everyday in the streets of the city. Thus it was easy for Castelletti to use the typical features of the people coming from Norcia as a lubricated comical gear for use in the general contrivance of his play.

Fig. 103 - Cristoforo Castelletti's humorous play *I torti amorosi* (Venice, 1581)

The setting of the play is Rome, where a 'Norcino', whose name is 'Tizzone' (meaning something like 'Ember', out of his disposition to anger and scurrility), presents himself in Act I Scene V:

«Tizzone Norcino, greengrocer — In the end I made a mistake when I decided to cultivate this vegetable garden together with Sir Zanobio. It would have been a hundred times better to do some of the jobs that are made by the other 'Norcini'. They sell chicory, watercress, turnips [... a long list of vegetables follows, editor's note], truffles, saffron, turtles, crabs, crayfish, snails, fish, thrushes, pigeons, small birds, [...], straw, hay, bundles of wood, coal...».

[In the original Italian text: «Tizzone Norcino, hortolano — Infine io ho pur fatto la mala capata a pigliare a mezzo l'orto di questo Messer Zanobio. Era meglio cento volte il fare qualche arte di queste che fanno gli altri Norcini. Essi vendono la cicoria, li crescioni, li raponzoli, li cacciaepori, le ramoracchie, le pastinache, li finocchi, li funghi, li triuoli, la frassinella e le ferule, la camomilla, li pignoli, li fiori della ginestra, il sarpollo, li tartuffoli, il zaffarame, le tartaruche, li granci, li gambari, le lumache, il

pesce, li tordi, li piccioni, gli uccelletti, li frisoni, la paglia, il fieno, li fascetti della legna, il carbone...»].

Fig. 104 - The first appearance of Tizzone 'Norcino' in Cristoforo Castelletti's humorous play *I torti amorosi* (Venice, 1581), p. 26 and 27

Here Cristoforo Castelletti is presenting the 'Norcini' as the multifarious peddlers that the people who watched his play could customarily meet in the markets of Rome (we already saw that they also had the license to sell fish and game). And, he continues, they also used to perform small manual work: «to saw the planks, cut the wood, bring the water needed for the

wash» (in Italian: «segano le tavole, steccano la legna, cacciano l'acqua per la bucata»).

Finally, last but not least, he describes the 'Norcini' in their double role as butchers and surgeons:

«They make sausages, cervelats; they pull the teeth, they castrate pigs, cats and even people; and at all times they find means to earn a living».

[In the original Italian text: «Fanno la salsiccia, li cervellati, cacciano li denti, castrano li porcelli, li gatti, le persone, et non manca mai loro da fare; et d'ogni tempo si guadagnano il pane»].

Tizzone is a real 'Norcino', as he actually comes from Norcia. «May I take the fever, if I should ever go away from Norcia» («mi venga la febre, s'io mi volessi mai partir da Norcia»), says Tizzone while thinking of his woman waiting for him at home. Then, when he happens to wear a gentleman's cloak, he notes that «if I went to Norcia with a dress like this, I would risk to be elected among the Priors» («s'andassi a Norcia così vestito, andrei a rischio d'esser imballottato tra li priori»).

Tiz. Non ci manca: ci son cauoli, rape, agli, radicci, ciò che uuor tu, ò uolto pinto; se fosse così bella Rosamìa, mi uenga la febre, s'io mi uoleffi mai partir da Norcia.

*70 A T T O
ill'uomo con questa cappanera, ne'ncaco li nostri Cittadini quando si cacciano de' priori. S'andassi a Norcia così uestito, andrei a rischio d'esser imballotato tra li priori: perche hoggidi non si ponmente se non*

Fig. 105 - Tizzone and Norcia in Cristoforo Castelletti's humorous play *I torti amorosi* (Venice, 1581), p. 28 and 70

And when being cheated by another character in the play, his curses make direct references to the legend of the Apennine Sibyl, to Mount Patino, the mountain which surmounts Norcia, and to the main church of the town:

«May you be cast from the mountain of the Sibyl, or from the cliff of Patino, or the belfry of St. Benedict; [...] may I receive from Norcia bad news from my Rose, if I do not thrust the cold blade of a knife up into your stomach. My name is Tizzone; and I want this Ember to burn with the greatest flame, and set your house on fire, and the vineyard, too, and all the

relatives of yours. [...] I will teach this drunkard what the 'Norcini' are made of» .

[In the original Italian text: «Possa esser gittato sù dalla montagna della Sibilla, o dal sasso di Patino, o dal campanile di San Benedetto; [...] mi possa venire da Norcia la mala nova di Rosa, se non ti caccio una punta di coltello freddo sù la bocca dello stomaco. Son Tizzone; voglio, che questo Tizzone faccia tanto foco, che t'abbrugi la casa, la vigna, e tutto il parentado tuo. [...] Insegnerò à questo imbriacone come son fatti li Norcini»].

huomini. Gli ho portate più insalate, più ci polle, più zucche, più meloni, che non ho peli nel capo; senza li quattrini, hoggi un grosso, & domani un carlino, & hora me ne da questo bello merito. Possa esser gittato sù dalla montagna della Sibilla, o dal sasso di Patino, o dal campanile di San Benedetto; la secca mi possa guastare tutto l'horto, mi possa uenire da Norcia la mala noua di Rosa, se non ti caccio una punta di coltello freddo sù la bocca dello stomaco. Son Tizzone; uoglio, che questo Tizzone faccia tanto foco, che t'abbrugi la casa, la vigna, e tutto il parentado tuo.

E che si, ch' insegnarò à questo imbriacone come son fatti li Norcini. E che si, che gl' insegnarò, come si procede con

Fig. 106 - An enraged Tizzone from Cristoforo Castelletti's humorous play *I torti amorosi* (Venice, 1581), p. 124 and 133

But Tizzone, 'Norcino' as he is, is imbued with the art of butchery; so even when raising his curses he cannot omit to mention the tools and methods of his craft, clearly referring to pig slaughtering:

«And I want they to go in front of him with those hooks, which are used to grasp the pigs; and they must take him by the ears, as if he were a boar. And as they hold him, I want to go to him from behind with one of those large knives, which they use to mash the sausages. [...] And I want to open him in two at the middle of his back; and as soon as he his parted in two pieces I want to take out his innards, and take his heart in my teeth, and eat it up, as if it were ravioli...».

[In the original Italian text: «E voglio, che essi gli vadano dalla banda dinanzi con quegli uncini, che ci si pigliano li porci, e che lo piglino per l'orecchie, come se fosse un Verre. Et come l'hanno fermato li voglio scappare dalla banda di dietro con uno di quei coltellacci grossi, che ci si pesta la salsiccia. [...] E poi voglio [...] partirlo per mezo il filo della schiena, e com'è partito cacciarli la coratella, e pigliarli il core co i denti, e mangiarmelo, come se fosse un ravuiolo...»].

re. E uoglio, che essi gli vadano dalla banda dinanzi con quegli uncini, che ci si pigliano li porci, e che lo piglino per l'orecchie, come se fosse un Verre. Et come l'hanno fermato li uoglio scappare dalla banda di dietro con uno di quei coltellacci grossi, che ci si pesta la salsiccia. Non uoglio andare dalla banda di dietro, perche habbia paura di lui, ma perche non mi uegga, perche se mi uedesse in faccia, mi riconoscerebbe subito, & mi potrebbe andare ad accusare alla Corte. Il primo colpo, che li meno, sarà tra capo, e collo, e s'ha a uedere saltare il capo in terra come se fosse uno di quei piccoli, co' quali giuocano i fanciulli. E poi uoglio raddoppiare, & dargli un colpo nella nucca, e partirlo per mezo il filo della schiena, e com'è partito cacciarli la coratella, e pigliarli il core co i denti, e mangiarmelo, come se fosse un ravuiolo. Traditore, come t'ho mangiato il

Fig. 107 - Reminiscences of pigs' butchery in Tizzone's curse, from Cristoforo Castelletti's humorous play *I torti amorosi* (Venice, 1581), p. 134

What does it all mean?

It means that in the sixteenth century the 'Norcini' are fully part of the landscape of Rome, playing multiple roles: butchers, for sure; but even surgeons (to this specific aspect is fully dedicated our previous essay *The Precian Surgical School*, 2026), and fishmongers, and sellers of game and truffles, and hucksters, and handymen, or jacks-of-all-trades.

So this sixteenth-century play is to be considered as a significant evidence to the fact that, at the time, there were in Rome both specialised 'Norcini' and less skilled people coming from Norcia, looking for their sustenance in the capital city. Like, for instance, Tizzone in the work written by Castelletti.

We will find the rude, ignorant 'Norcino' in another farcical play, too, dating to 1610. It's *The tangle and the tangled injustices* (*L'intrico et torti intricati*) by Paolo Veraldo, another comedy set in Rome and featuring a further 'Norcino', even more uncivilised than Tizzone himself. His name is Pan'onto ('bread with grease from flamed meat', a traditional shepherd's or farmer's snack lunch) and his participation in the play is mainly limited to his appearance and uttering of almost incomprehensible sentences in the dialect of Norcia (still in use today). For instance, here is what he says when addressing a lawyer in Rome to explain his case as a castrator of cats and pigs who hasn't received his wage:

«Oh you understand me well; please help me explain my case in good Latin, because he [the lawyer, editor's note] is such a man of letter that he does not understand the dialect of Norcia at all.»

O vii l'insennete bene; de ratia aiutate-me à dicere rù fattu meu in latinescu, per que è tantu litteratu què non intenne cica, cica, ruuolgaru da Norcia,

Fig. 108 - Another 'Norcino' drawn from Paolo Veraldo's play *L'intrico et torti intricati* (Venice, 1610), p.

[In the original Italian text: «O vui l'intennete bene; de gratia aiutateme à dicere rù fattu meu in latinescu, per que e' tantu litteratu què non intenne cica, cica, ru volgariu da Norcia»].

Again, at the beginning of the seventeenth century the people from Norcia is so well-known in Rome that people in theaters can easily laugh at hearing and recognising his ridiculous idiom, as if it were a real-life situation.

However, despite the plays in theaters, the mockery of the 'Norcini' was just pointless. Because there in Rome, and in real life, the 'Norcini' — the skilled ones, the butchers, and physicians like Francesco Fusconi and lawyers like Laerzio Cherubini, and the many proficient surgeons — were making money. And even big money.

7.3.6 *The 'Norcini' towards the seventeenth century*

So the 'Norcini', during the sixteenth century, were definitely there, in the town of the Popes, And their social position was growing and growing again. Their presence was manifest, definite, stable and fully accepted in Rome. They were known to all Romans, be they the populace or the papal aristocracy.

As a matter of fact the presence of the 'Norcini' in Rome was already part of the Roman landscape. And it was at the end of the sixteenth century that, Giulio Landi, who lived in Rome for many years, wrote his *Formaggiata di Sere Stentato* with an explicit reference to the top-quality hams of Norcia.

In this framework, time had come to publicly affirm their standing, by establishing their own brotherhood and guild. Just like the other 'Nations' that lived in Rome, and the many crafts that worked in town.

They wanted to be recognised amid the Romans, with formal decrees issued by the Popes. And the seventeenth century will be the right time to get it all.

So let's go and explore in full this subsequent periods in the next paragraphs.

7.4 The seventeenth century: the formal recognition of the established position of the people from Norcia in Rome

7.4.1 The 'Norcini' in the edicts of the 'Grascia'

At the beginning of the seventeenth century the presence of a significant community of people from Norcia in Rome is an indisputable, manifest fact.

Many 'Norcini' live permanently in Rome, some of them since more than a century. There are skilled butchers, there are peddlers and small food sellers; but there are wealthy professionals, too, and lawyers and physicians and surgeons. And seasonal workers, who come from Norcia to help their fellow-citizens, and even the local grocers, in the processing of pork meat to prepare sausages and other cured food products.

In their role as butchers, the 'Norcini' are now officially recognised by the government of the Papal States: the 'Grascia', the body which is in charge for ensuring that appropriate supplies of food reach the local Roman market basing on a reliable distribution chain and regulated prices, is well aware of the presence in Rome of a specific category of butchers originating from Norcia and providing a specific expertise on the slaughtering of pigs and the processing of pork meat. And the 'Norcini' begin to be referenced within the edicts which are related to butchery.

On January 10th 1607, the President of the Grascia, Cardinal Pietro Aldobrandino, issues an edict «against Butchers, and Norcini, oil Sellers, Tanners, Grocers, Makers of candles, and others» (in Italian, «contro Macellari, et Norcini, Mercanti d'oglio, Vaccinari, Pizzicaroli, Candelottari, et altri»).

What was the matter with all them? First, Cardinal Aldobrandino reminds them that the main mission of the administration he runs is «to ensure that in this illustrious City of Rome, and also in the whole State of the Church,

be the utmost abundance of any sorts of meats, cheese, salami, olive oil, and any other foodstuff for which the Grascia is in charge, so needed for human sustenance» (in Italian, «à provvedere, che in quest'Alma Città di Roma, et anco in tutto lo Stato Ecclesiastico sia quanto più si può abbondanza d'ogni sorte de carni, cascì, salami, oglio, et di tutte l'altre cose pertinenti alla grascia, tanto necessarie al vitto humano»).

The issue is that each and all of the listed professional categories always make attempts at eluding the rules, in search of additional earnings:

«For we heard from different sources, to our great displeasure, that the People complain that they cannot retrieve at present the pork meat they need, that is loin, ribs and other cuts; and that Butchers, Norcini and Grocers and others, who all sell pork meat, supply and sell covertly, and during the night, to the innkeepers and to other subjects at their own will; so they sell nothing to the People».

[In the original Italian language: «Perché s'intende da diverse bande, non senza gran nostro dispiacere, che il Popolo si lamenta di non trovare di presente a comprar carne di porco, cioè lombetti, costigliole, et altri tagli, et che li Macellari, Norcini, Pizzicaroli, et altri, che vendono carne porcina, la smaltiscono, et vendono di nascosto, et di notte, distribuendola tra gli hosti, et à chi li pare, senza venderne alcuna al Popolo»].

Fig. 109 - Decree on the 'Norcini' as butchers dated 1607, from Cred. XIII, t. XXX preserved at the Archive of the Camera Capitolina (Rome), p. 156

The contrivance is clear: the 'Norcini', and all the others, instead of selling their products at low, regulated prices as a legal trade, just prefer to sell pork meat to professional customers on the black market, a more profitable business. So the disappointed Cardinal is forced to threaten heavier punishments to be inflicted on transgressors, including the torture of strappado and a fine of fifty scudi.

But the 'Norcini' are there, as butchers; and they are butchers of pigs.

A few years later, in 1611, another edict is issued by the same Cardinal on the same issue (it is clear that the market regulation in Rome is not particularly appreciated by the professional players who are forced to work within the boundaries of its price limitations):

Item che li Macellari, Norcini, Salceicciari, & altri che tengono carne di qualsivoglia forte per riuendere, non le possano tener nascoste, ma le debbano mettere in mostra per venderle a chi le vorrà comprare così in piccola quantità, come in grande, & tenerne ancor dentro, se ve ne hanno affai, ma non in lochi nascosti, ne negare ad alcuna forte di persona carne di forte alcuna ne forzare li compratori a comprare à voglia loro d'una forte per hauere dell'altra, ne à pagar più del prezzo contenuto ne Bandi, de' quali ciacheduno de' sopraddetti debbia tenerne vno attaccato auanti le loro botteghe, sotto pena della perdita della carne, & di icudi vniucineque per ciacheduna volta, e di tre tratti di corda.

Fig. 110 - Another decree on the 'Norcini' as butchers dating to 1611, from Cred. XIII, t. XXX preserved at the Archive of the Camera Capitolina, Rome), p. 135

«We order, and command [...] that the Butchers, Norcini, Makers of Sausages, and others, who hold meat of any sort for sale, must not hide that, and instead must put that on display for anybody who may wish to buy that, either in small or in large quantity; they can keep it inside their shops, if the supply is huge, but never in hidden receptacles...».

[In the original Italian language: «Ordiniamo, e comandiamo [...] che li Macellari, Norcini, Salcicciari, et altri che tengono carne di qualsivoglia sorte per rivendere, non le possano tener nascoste, ma le debbano mettere in mostra per venderle à chi le vorrà comprare così in piccola quantità, come in grande, et tenerne ancor dentro, se ve ne hanno assai, ma non in lochi nascosti...»].

Here we also find our 'salcicciari', who in earlier times might have included the very first 'Norcini' in Rome. Here they are listed amid the category of butchers as a separate class; however, such lists, as contained in edicts, just intend to indicate that the orders detailed therein must be applied to all the players in the Roman meat market — but this time, for instance, they just forgot to include the Grocers.

The notable thing here is that the 'Norcini' are now part of the landscape of Rome, and a recognised player within the Roman food business. The people from Norcia are living and working in Rome, with a special presence as butchers. And everybody knows who they are and what they do for a living in Rome.

We note here that the decrees we mentioned are only a small portion of the many official documents that were issued by the authorities in Rome, during the seventeenth century, as to the 'Norcini'; for instance, a further decree, dating February 15th 1645 is mentioned by Claudio De Dominicis in his research on the Fondo Camerale II — Sezione 10 *Arti e mestieri* at the Archivio di Stato di Roma (2005, p. 99). Similar documentation, preserved at the Italian Archivio di Stato in Rome and still unpublished, is referred to by French historian Emmanuel Pierre Rodocanachi.

This means that further research will be certainly needed to collect additional pieces of information on the subject, for a complete reconstruction of the historical role and position of the 'Norcini' in papal Rome.

Nonetheless, it is clear that time has now come for a full, formal recognition of the 'Norcini' as one of the many 'Nations' that used to live in Rome. At the beginning of the seventeenth century, they need — and deserve — their guild.

And they will have it. As we will narrate in the next paragraph.

7.4.2 *The Brotherhood of St. Benedict and St. Scholastica — A new beginning for the 'Norcini' in Rome*

Just like other national groups living in town, the 'Norcini' begin to understand that their community is now large enough to make a leap others have already done: setting up their own guild, which is to be officially established through a formal decree issued by the Pope in person.

And this will be the very moment in which the public awareness in Rome about the people coming from Norcia will definitely change. Their successful presence in the capital of the Papal States will become conspicuous and even unexpectedly visible to everybody.

This interesting story is told in the original version of the *Charters* of the Archbrotherhood of St. Benedict and St. Scholastica, established by the 'Norcini' in Rome. The *Charters* were written in 1625, but the story they tell dates back to ten years earlier, when the Brotherhood was first devised and then approved by the Pope.

The protagonist of this story, and leading figure of the people of Norcia in Rome, was Laerzio Cherubini, the renowned lawyer, judge and public administrator at the papal court, and author of a fundamental collection of papal decrees, whom we already mentioned earlier in this same paper. An extremely wealthy man, he gathered in his house other pious, illustrious inhabitants of the land of Norcia («alcuni devoti Cittadini di Norcia» in Italian) who were fully living their life in Rome at the time — lawyer Benedetto Passerino, Sebastiano Masseroni, Olimpio Cistarelli, and Francesco Passerino. Let's hear what happened straight from his very words, as he wrote down the whole episode in the *Charters* he himself authored:

«In the year of our Salvation 1615, at the end of the month of February, having convened the said five Founders in the house of the said Mr. Laertio, they decided to establish a Company of secular Men and Women, with the aim that, practising together the Sacraments, attending the Holy

Masses and performing charitable activities, they all may deserve increasing merits to the glory of God and the Saints Benedict and Scholastica».

[In the original Italian text: «Nell'Anno adunque della nostra salute 1615, alla fine del Mese di Febraro, congregati detti cinque Fondatori in casa di detto Signor Laertio risolsero fondar' una Compagnia di Huomini, et Donne secolari, quali in unione, con la frequenza de' Sacramenti, et essercitio de' Divini Officij, et di opere pie s'avanzassero ogni giorno più in meriti à gloria di Dio, et de Santi Benedetto, et Scholastica»].

Nell' Anno adunque della nostra salute 1615, alla fine del Mese di Febraro, congregati detti cinque Fondatori in casa di detto Signor Laertio risolsero fondar' vna Compagnia di Huomini, & Donne secolari, quali in unione, con la frequenza de' Sacramenti, & essercitio de' Diuini Officij, & di opere pie s'avanzassero ogni giorno più in meriti à gloria di Dio, & de Santi Benedetto, & Scholastica.

Fig. 111 - The origin of the Brotherhood from *Statuti e privilegi della Venerabile Archiconfraternita de' Santi Benedetto e Scholastica di Roma* (Rome, 1625), Biblioteca Nazionale Centrale di Roma

Those men from Norcia were affluent and well connected. As soon as the decision was taken, they immediately acted to carry their resolution into effect, «because the Day of the said St. Benedict — which they wanted to celebrate with the utmost solemnity — was near» («perché la festa di detto San Benedetto — che con ogni solennità volevon si celebrasse — era prossima» in Italian), and they knew that «the submission of an application for the confirmation of a new brotherhood to Pope Paul V was a matter

somewhat lengthy» («il fare istanza della confirmatione a Paolo V [...] era negotio di qualche longhezza»).

Their knowledge of the main figures at the papal court was thorough and direct. So «they entrusted Mr. Benedetto Passerino with the task to beseech the most illustrious Cardinal Mellino, Vicar of His Holiness in order to obtain the confirmation of their wish, with the establishment of the Company» («fù data facultà al detto Signor Benedetto Passerino per supplicare l'Illustrissimo Signor Cardinale Mellino Vicario di sua Santità per la confirmatione di questo lor desiderio, et erttione delle detta Compagnia»).

As a first step, on March 1st 1615 a decree issued by Monsignor Fedele, the deputy of the Cardinal Vicar, provided the authorization for the establishment of the Brothehood at the Church of St. Eustachio, located a few steps from the Pantheon, through a deed of notary public Mazziotto, himself appointed as the secretary of the new company. The Prior, of course, was the eminent, illustrious, celebrated lawyer Laerzio Cherubini.

Now the die was cast. The success of the newborn aggregation among the 'Norcini' in Rome was straightforward, as Laerzio Cherubini himself recounts:

«As soon as the said confirmation was granted, with the institution of the Brotherhood, a Meeting was called that was attended by many pious persons, who gladly supported the new institution [...]. It was decided to hold a public procession to carry out a visit (as more than two hundred Brothers actually did, clothed in raw Tunics and carrying white waxen torches under the standard of St. Benedict, marching in nice ranks and showing great devotion) the Holy Sepulcher at the Pauline Chapel of the Apostolic Palace [...] having been spent a good amount of money».

[In the original Italian text: «Havuta che si hebbe tal confirmatione, et erttione, fu intimata una Congregazione di molte devote persone, che s'offersero concorrere à quest'instituto [...]. Fu risoluto [...] si dovesse fare una publica processione per andar' a visitare (come fecero con più di dugento Fratelli vestiti con Sacchi, et torcie di cera bianca sotto lo stendardo di San Benedetto con bell'ordine, et gran devotione) il

Santissimo Sepolcro nella Cappella Paolina del Palazzo Pontificio [...] essendosi [...] spesa buona somma de denari»].

Can you imagine the procession of two hundred brothers, mainly originating from the land of Norcia, each with a torch in his hands, slowly marching through the narrow streets of seventeenth-century Rome?

And can you imagine the lavish mass held, on the Day of St. Benedict, at the Church of St. Eustachio? The building was adorned with a profusion of tapestries, banners, standards and mottoes «representing the life and saintly deeds of Benedict»; in fact, the new brothers had arranged the whole celebration with the utmost care, with a specific target in their minds:

«[...] They intended] to confer a majestic appearance to the celebration, and to fully honor that Day, so that the whole occurrence might be beheld by the entire City of Rome, which actually considered with astonishment the sudden greatness of the Company, never mentioned before, and never seen by anyone prior to that day, so everybody thought that it had undergone a process of incredible growth in a time that was very short».

[In the original Italian text: «[...] per render maestevole, et honorando quel giorno, che tale certamente lo vidde tutta la città di Roma, che con gran stupore ammirò la subita grandezza della Compagnia non mai nominata, ne vista onde ne fece giudizio di grandissimo incremento»].

It was a great, almost unexpected display of magnificence and power. The 'Norcini' were there; there were ranks of them; and, now, they were rich and grand and respected and recognised.

Because, on St. Benedict's Day, they also showed the city of Rome that they, too, had their patron. A man of power, a man of the Church:

«In the meeting the first officials were appointed by election [...], in addition to the election, that they carried out first, of the Most Illustrious Cardinal Benedetto Giustiniani as their Patron».

[In the original Italian text: «Furono in dette Congregazioni eletti li primi Officiali [...] oltre all'elettione, che prima havevano fatta, dell'Illustrissimo Signor Cardinale Benedetto Giustiniani per loro Protettore»].

Fig. 112 - The Cardinal Patron of the Brotherhood from *Statuti e privilegi della Venerabile Archiconfraternita de' Santi Benedetto e Scholastica di Roma* (Rome, 1625), Biblioteca Nazionale Centrale di Roma

A new brotherhood. Hundreds of members. A Prior who was a high-rank personage in Rome. Lavish apparels for public celebrations. A patron who was one of the most prominent Cardinals at the papal court. A sudden, outstanding appearance amid the many national brotherhoods which were present in the town of the Popes.

The 'Norcini' had changed their skin.

Poor Tizzone, the rustic, funny 'Norcino' handyman who merely represented an ancillary character in a humorous play being performed in Rome to the enjoyment of the populace, was no more: that year, with the splendid procession that was trading the capital city of the Papal States, with the magnificent celebrations for the feast of St. Benedict, Norcia was putting on display its new standing, as one of the many wealthy 'Nations' that lived and had their business in Rome.

And on an equal basis.

7.4.3 The Brotherhood of St. Benedict and St. Scholastica — The papal confirmation

As we wrote in the previous paragraph, the die was now cast for the 'Norcini' in Rome.

The thorough initial success of the new association spurred the founding members — Laerzio Cherubini, the two Passerino, Masseroni and Cistarelli — to immediately proceed further ahead:

«Considering the said advancements, the five founders addressed a supplication to the late Pope Paul V so that He, through His Apostolic power, established the brotherhood as a Company of all Christian believers of both sexes».

[In the original Italian text: «Stante questo progresso supplicorno li cinque Fondatori suddetti la fel. mem. di Paolo Quinto, acciò volesse con l'autorità Apostolica erigerla in Compagnia di tutti li Fedeli Christiani dell'uno, et l'altro sesso»].

And Paul V Borghese, with his bull *Pastoris aeterni* dated November 9, 1615, answering the plea of his «beloved sons» («sicut dilecti filii») concerning the establishment of a new ecclesiastical institution «under the protection of St. Benedict and St. Scholastica and to the glory of God» (in Latin «sub invocatione eiusdem sancti Benedicti et sanctae Scholasticae, ad Dei gloriam»), the two illustrious patron saints of Norcia, «eternally establishes and instates a brotherhood of believers in Jesus Christ including both men and women» («unam utriusque sexus christifidelium confraternitatem [...] perpetuo erigimus et instituimus») entreated by those «who come from our land of Norcia and the adjoining bishopric of Spolegium, urged by their peculiar worship of St. Benedict, the beacon and dignity of Norcia» (in Latin «qui a terra nostra Nursiae et locis adiacentibus Spoletanae diocesis originem ducunt, peculiari devotione ducti erga sanctum Benedictum clarissimum Nursiae lumen et decus»).

This is the birth of the Brotherhood of St. Benedict and Scholastica in Rome. And this is the actual sign of the remarkable influence acquired at the papal court by the people coming from Norcia, who were now living in Rome.

As Pope Paul V points out in his bull, the new Brotherhood is not intended «for people belonging to a single, specific art or craft» («quae non sit pro hominibus unius specialis artis»): so the association certainly includes the butchers from Norcia in Rome, but also all the other categories of people

originating from the same town who have made their career in Rome, be it in the papal administration or as physicians and surgeons, or even peddlers and handymen: all held together by their common devotion towards St. Benedict and St. Scholastica, the patron saints of their Apennine lands.

Fig. 113 - Pope Paul V's bull *Pastoris aeterni*, from *Bullarum diplomatum et privilegiorum Sanctorum Romanorum Pontificum*, Tomus XII (Turin, 1867), p. 337-340

Following Paul V's bull, the news about the establishment of a new Roman brotherhood dedicated to St. Benedict and St. Scholastica begins to spread far and wide.

In May 1618, three years after the foundation, the general chapter of the Cassinese Congregation of the monasteries of St. Benedict, being held in Parma, sent an official message to the Brotherhood in Rome, in which the benedictine monks stated that «we most willingly adopt you as our beloved sons» («vos in dilectos filios nostros libenter adoptemus» in Latin). And the same did, in 1619, the Celestine branch of the benedictine world with another letter: «we gladly recognize you as our beloved brothers, and we willingly adopt you» («vos in nostros dilectos fratres benigne suscipimus, et libenter adoptamus» in Latin).

Fig. 114 - The message sent by the Cassinese Congregation to the Brotherhood of St. Benedict and St. Scholastica in 1618, from *Statuti e privilegi della Venerabile Archiconfraternita de' Santi Benedetto e Scholastica di Roma* (Rome, 1625), Biblioteca Nazionale Centrale di Roma, p. 90

Fig. 115 - The message sent by the Celestine Congregation to the Brotherhood of St. Benedict and St. Scholastica in 1619, from *Statuti e privilegi della Venerabile Archiconfraternita de' Santi Benedetto e Scholastica di Roma* (Rome, 1625), Biblioteca Nazionale Centrale di Roma, p. 90 and 91

Thus the secular Brotherhood in Rome, with all the people of Norcia associated to it and living in the town of the Popes, is now included in the great monastic family of the Benedictines: a giant result for the poor, rustic 'Norcini' who, some a hundred and fifty years earlier, had been migrating on a seasonal basis to Rome to earn their living.

The praise and recognition received from the benedictine world had an important secondary effect, as we read in the words written by Laerzio Cherubini:

«Not many months had elapsed when many pious people — who were inspired to give birth to similar brotherhoods in many parts of the World, and particularly in those places in which Monasteries of the Monks of the Order of St. Benedict are established, especially of the Cassinese and Celestine Congregations — more than once asked our Company to be associated to the Heavenly share that our fellow Brothers win for themselves by joining our standard of St. Benedict and St. Scholastica; they wanted to be aggregated, so as to join us as brotherhood's members».

[In the original Italian text: «Non passorno molti mesi, che ispirati in diverse parti del Mondo, et particolarmente in luoghi, dove sono fondati Monasterij de Monaci dell'Ordine di San Benedetto, et massime della Congregazione Cassinense, et de Celestini, molte pie persone à far il simile ad imitatione nostra, han fatto più volte istanza alla nostra Compagnia di esser partecipi della Celeste portione, che acquistano li Confratri, che militano sotto questo stendardo di S. Benedetto, et S. Scholastica con aggregarli, et farli membri di essa»].

What does it mean? It means that the success of the Brotherhood in Rome was so overwhelming that other brotherhoods, born elsewhere in the neighborhood of some benedictine abbeys, were sending in applications to join the Roman association, seen as a central hub dedicated to the devotion of the two saints originating from Norcia.

However, from the point of view of canon law their wish could not be fulfilled, as only archbrotherhoods could aggregate other brotherhoods, and the Brotherhood of St. Benedict and St. Scholastica had only been established as a plain confraternity.

So a further leap was necessary: the transformation of the company into an archbrotherhood. To take such a momentous step the support of a powerful patron was needed.

The Brotherhood's former champion, Cardinal Benedetto Giustiniani, had passed away in 1621; yet the new one was even more mighty.

In fact the 'Nation' of Norcia had always been well-connected with the top levels in Rome. Following the death of Giustiniani they got the backing of one of the most rich and powerful members of the papal court: Cardinal Ludovico Ludovisi, the nephew of Pope Gregory XV Ludovisi, who held apical posts and was the owner of an extraordinary collection of classical statuary (which is still existing in our present times), and even the initiator of the wondrous Villa Boncompagni-Ludovisi in Rome (which will be unfortunately destroyed by a greedy urban speculation in the nineteenth century).

As Laerzio Cherubini writes, «the Prior and Custodians of the time devised to submit a plea to the Most Illustrious and Most Eminent Cardinal Ludovisio, our extremely alerted Patron, so as to ask the late Pope Gregory XV, of whom he was the dignified nephew, for this concession».

[In the original Italian text: «Risolsero li Signori Priore, et Guardiani di quel tempo di supplicarne l'Illustrissimo, et Reverendissimo Signor Cardinale Ludovisio nostro vigilantissimo Protettore, acciò volesse intercedere per tal gratia appresso la fel. mem. di Gregorio XV, del quale n'era dignissimo Nipote»].

And the concession was «readily granted». Pope Gregory XV, with the further bull *Pias christifidelium confraternitates* released on February 4, 1623, raised the association to the dignity of Archbrotherhood, giving the association the right to aggregate and absorb other brotherhoods.

Now the company of the people from Norcia in Rome was ready to navigate the stormy sea of centuries. Up to our present day: it is still there, and it has more than four hundred years.

Confraternitatem Ss. Benedicti et Scholasticae, a Paulo V erectam, erigit in archiconfraternitatem, cum facultate

alias confraternitates aggregandi, illisque indulgentias et gratias spirituales communicandi ¹.

**Gregorius Papa XV,
ad perpetuam rei memoriam.**

Prooemium. Pias christifidelium confraternitates, ad pietatis et christianae charitatis opera exercenda praesertim in almâ Urbe nostrâ canonice institutas, ut in eorundem piorum operum exercitio magis accendantur et confoveantur, titulis et gratiis amplioribus libenter decoramus, prout conspicimus in Domino salubriter expedire.

Confraternitatem a Paulo V erectam, § 1. Cum itaque, sicut accepimus, aliâs in ecclesiâ sancti Eustachii de Urbe, una pia utriusque sexus christifidelium confraternitas sub S. Benedicti et S. Scholasticae invocationibus per felicitis recordationis Paulum Papam V praedecessorem nostrum apostolicâ auctoritate erecta et instituta fuerit, ac dilecti filii illius officiales et confratres in quamplurimis pietatis et charitatis operibus sese exercere consueverint, et in dies magis Deo dante exercere intendant:

Fig. 116 - Pope Gregory XV's bull *Pias christifidelium confraternitates*, from *Bullarum diplomatum et privilegiorum Sanctorum Romanorum Pontificum*, Tomus XII (Turin, 1867), p. 788 and 789

7.4.4 The Brotherhood of St. Benedict and St. Scholastica — The Nation of Norcia in Rome

As we wrote in an earlier paragraph, «as people from other Italian towns or even foreign countries gathered in Rome to reside in the capital city of the Papal States, they tended to associate in brotherhoods marked by a common origin [...] bringing together people who lived in town for the most diverse reasons, but all sharing the same origin, be it from an Italian town or a European country».

The same process applied to the case of our 'Norcini', whose presence in Rome, at the beginning of the seventeenth century, was manifest and appreciated, be they butchers of pigs, salters of pork meat, proficient Precian surgeons and physicians, or even handymen, colourfully described in humorous plays at Roman theaters.

The Brotherhood of St. Benedict and St. Scholastica just entered into existence by proudly aggregating many 'Norcini' who lived in the capital of the Papal States and besought recognition and a firmer standing in Rome, just like the people from Florence, Milan, Genoa, Naples, Sicily and other places in Italy and abroad (Spain, France, Germany, Portugal, etc.) who were in Rome in numbers and had long established their own brotherhoods.

Certainly enough, the new Brotherhood was not intended solely for the people of Norcia: the «said five founders», it is written on the original Charters dating to 1625, «devised to establish a Company of Men, et Women living their secular life, who jointly, by receiving the Sacraments and attending the Holy Masses, and through acts of charity, may improve in their everyday life as to their merits to the glory of God, and the Saints Benedict and Scholastica» (in the original Italian text: «detti cinque fondatori [...] risolsero fondar' una Compagnia di Huomini, et Donne secolari, quali in unione, con la frequenza de' Sacramenti, et essercitio de' Divini Officij, et di opere pie s'avanzassero ogni giorno di più in meriti à gloria di Dio, et de Santi Benedetto, et Scholastica»).

Fig. 117 - The scope of the Brotherhood from *Statuti e privilegi della Venerabile Archiconfraternita de' Santi Benedetto e Scholastica di Roma* (Rome, 1625), Biblioteca Nazionale Centrale di Roma, Chapter on the origin of the Brotherhood

Thus, it was not a main requirement for admission one's personal origin from the area of Norcia: the trust and devotion towards St. Benedict and St. Scholastica was the principal reason for becoming a member of the new Brotherhood.

Nonetheless, this trust and devotion were typical of the 'Norcini', as everybody knew in Rome and as Pope Paul V Borghese himself, in his bull

Pastoris aeterni dated November 9, 1615, openly points out when speaking of those «who come from our land of Norcia and the adjoining bishopric of Spolegium, urged by their peculiar worship of St. Benedict, the beacon and dignity of Norcia» (in Latin «qui a terra nostra Nursiae et locis adiacentibus Spoletanae diocesis originem ducunt, peculiari devotione ducti erga sanctum Benedictum clarissimum Nursiae lumen et decus»).

In addition to that, the Roman Norcini were obviously attracted towards the new Brotherhood by the fame and dignity of the founders, all coming from Norcia, and especially, among them, by the illustrious name of Laerzio Cherubini.

Let's put it this way: if you were a 'Norcino' in seventeenth-century Rome, which brotherhood would you join? Perhaps St. John of the Florentines? Or, maybe, St. Anthony of the Portuguese? Or any other 'National' brotherhood in Rome? Of course not: the Brotherhood of St. Benedict and St. Scholastica would be your association of choice. And the same applies the other way round: a merchant from Florence and a member of the diplomatic mission working for the King of Portugal wouldn't normally join the society of the 'Norcini' — unless they had a very strong personal devotion to St. Benedict and the benedictine world.

So the 'Confraternita dei Santi Benedetto e Scolastica' will fully begin to represent the 'Nation' of the people of Norcia in Rome, as reported by Pompilio Totti, an antiquarian and publisher in Rome originating from Cerreto di Spoleto, not far from Norcia, in his *Ritratto di Roma moderna* (1638):

«Of St. Benedict and St. Scholastica — In the Town of Norcia a thousand two hundred years ago were born those two luminous saints, [...] and though in some churches of Rome the great father St. Benedict was already celebrated, nonetheless his fellow-citizens, as they wished, just like the other nations, reach their fame in this common homeland of the whole world, devised in 1614 to establish a Company which may welcome all who placed their faith in St. Benedict».

Di S. Benedetto, e S. Scolastica. 8.

Nella Città di Norcia già mille, e dugent'anni nacquero questi due gran lumi, per illustrare nell'Occidente la monastica disciplina, come nell'Oriente fece s. Basilio; e con tutto, che Roma in alcune sue chiese hauesse honorato il gran patriarca s. Benedetto, nondimeno i suoi compatrioti desiderando anch'essi come l'altre nationi, farsi conoscere in questa patria commune del mondo, si risolsero il 1614. di

fare vna Compagnia, nella quale potess'entrare chiunque fosse diuoto di s. Benedetto, e per maggiormente animare le donne, v'aggiunsero l'iuocatione di s. Scolastica.

Hora militando questa Compagnia sotto l'insigne di questi due gran personaggi, celebravano il 1615. la festa di s. Benedetto con gran pompa nella chiesa di s. Eustachio, doue cominciarono ad vnirsi insino al numero di dugento, poi il seguente anno festeggiarono il giorno di s. Scolastica a' 10. di Febbraio in vn'Oratorio, che a tempo pigliarono presso di s. Maria a piazza Colonna, & alla fine comprarono questa habitatione, che lor seruira per farci vna chiesa, & vno spedale per quelli della natione. Per conformarsi poi con l'habito di s. Benedetto, vestono sacchi neri, con vna mozzetta di faia nera, & hauendo la confirmatione da Paolo V. trà gli altri priuilegi, concesse loro di poter liberare vn prigioniero per la vita.

Fig. 118 - The Archbrotherhood of St. Benedict and St. Scholastica as described by Pompilio Totti in his *Ritratto di Roma moderna* (Rome, 1638), p. 369-370

[In the original Italian text: «Di S. Benedetto, e S. Scolastica — Nella Città di Norcia già mille, e dugent'anni nacquero questi due gran lumi, [...] e con tutto, che Roma in alcune sue chiese hauesse honorato il gran patriarca s. Benedetto, nondimeno i suoi compatrioti desiderando anch'essi come l'altre nationi, farsi conoscere in questa patria comune del mondo, si risolsero il 1614 di fare una Compagnia, nella quale potess'entrare chiunque fosse diuoto di S. Benedetto»].

And Carlo Bartolomeo Piazza in his *Eusevologio romano delle Opere Pie di Roma*, dating to 1698, clearly specifies that the religious company of St. Benedict and St. Scholastica is the expression, in Rome, of «the Nation of the people from Norcia» in Rome (in Italian «la Nazione de' Norcini»):

«Of the [Archbrotherhood] of St. Benedict and St. Scholastica of the Nation of the 'Norcini' at the Arch of the 'Ciambella' [near the Pantheon, editor's note] — [...] Never disappeared in Rome the memory of so pious a Nation [of Norcia], which is proud to have given birth, and raised within the Church, so grand a Saint; so, following the example coming from other

Nations, it intended to match all others by establishing such a remarkable National Brotherhood».

[In the original Italian text: «De' SS. Benedetto, e Scolastica Della Nazione de' Norcini All'Arco della Ciambella — [...] Mai è cessata in Roma la memoria di sì pia Nazione [di Norcia], che vanta d'haver avuto, et allevato alla Chiesa un sì gran Santo; peroche emola della pietà dell'altre Nazioni, le ha voluto uggugliate, con istituire una così cospicua Confraternita Nazionale»].

Fig. 119 - The Archbrotherhood of St. Benedict and St. Scholastica as described by Carlo Bartolomeo Piazza in his *Eusevologio romano delle Opere Pie di Roma* (Rome, 1698), p. 416-418

So the relationship between Rome and Norcia is now officially highlighted and recognised: the 'Norcini' are there, in the capital of the Papal States, and they have their own brotherhood, just like many other 'Nations' in Rome.

A presence that will keep its cohesion and strength for the centuries to come.

7.4.5 The Brotherhood of St. Benedict and St. Scholastica — The 'National' church

Let's go back for a moment to the very first months of existence of our company of the 'Norcini' in Rome, in the year 1615.

The sudden fame won by the new Brotherhood of St. Benedict and St. Scholastica, recalls Laerzio Cherubini in the *Charters*, spurred the company into devising a specific taxation scheme amid the brothers themselves, so as to collect a convenient sum of money for the new association.

A few brothers, in the frenzy of enthusiasm, even surpassed what was asked of them:

«For sure there was no lack of instances of an excessive zeal of some Brothers, who, disregarding any concern for the preservation of their properties within their own families, and without any worry for the ensuing impoverishment of their relatives, decided to deprive them of their inheritance — which is by nature due to them — making the Company their heir general. This is exactly what Mr. Pier Mattheo Lucarucci did on August, 24th 1615 with his last will. Lucarucci passed away on August, 6th 1622, leaving all his properties to the Brotherhood».

[In the original Italian text: «Ne mancò eccesso d'affetto in qualche Confratre, che, senza haver riguardo alla conservatione de beni nelle lor famiglie, et alla povertà de proprij parenti, volse privarli di quella successione, che naturalmente se gli deve, et in lor luogo instituir la Compagnia, come fece alli 24 d'Agosto 1615, nel suo ultimo testamento, il quondam Signor Pier Mattheo Lucarucci, che poi fece passaggio da questa à miglior vita à di 6 d'Agosto 1622, lasciandola herede universale di tutti li suoi beni»].

Ne mancò eccesso d'affetto in qualche Confratre, che senza hauer risguardo alla conseruatione de beni nelle lor famiglie, & alla pouertà de proprij parenti, volse priuarli di quella successione, che naturalmente se gli deue, & in lor luogo instituir la Compagnia, come fece alli X X I V. d' Agosto M D C X V. nel suo vltimo testamento, il quon. Signor Pier Mattheo Lucarucci, che poi fece passaggio da questa à miglior vita à di VI. d' Agosto M D C X X I I. lasciandola herede vniuersale di tutti li suoi beni, facendo il simile ad imitatione sua il quon. Signor Capitano Gradasso Pitti nel suo vltimo testamento rogato dal Gargario Notaro Capitolino il di XIV. di Giugno M D C X V I I.

Fig. 120 - The Brotherhood as heir general of Pier Mattheo Lucarucci, from *Statuti e privilegi della Venerabile Archiconfraternita de' Santi Benedetto e Scholastica di Roma* (Rome, 1625), Biblioteca Nazionale Centrale di Roma

Pier Mattheo Lucarucci was a wealthy man. He was a notary public in Rome during the period 1576-1597 (he is included as 'Lucarutius Petrus Matthaeus' in the *Repertorio dei Notari Romani dal 1348 al 1927*, edited by Romina de Vizio, Rome, 2011, p. 132). He had properties. And he actually was from Norcia, as we can show from a document preserved at the Archive of the Camera Capitolina: on April 29th 1614 the Secret Council bestowed the citizenship of Rome on Lucarucci, and the official minutes report «Petrus Mattheus Lucaruccius de Nursia».

29. Aprilis 1614
 Consilium Secretum dimissis schedulis per Attandentarios Rubcos ad iij. kal. May 1614. conuocato pro terra, seu quocumque, et apud Capitolium mihi Angelo Fusco sac. sen. scriba in secundo senatulo relatum, ad quod uenerunt
 Tandem pro futura ciuitatis assequenda nominati fuerunt,
 Diomedes de
 Bernardinus de Grenfanellis
 Donatus Tosus Mediolanen
 Bernardus Bandinus Floren
 Crucianus Bona de camerino
 Carolus Corbius Conanus
 Io: Fabricius Besuffel Flander
 Ciues Nominati,
 Petrus Mattheus Lucaruccius de Nursia

Fig. 121 - Pier Mattheo Lucarucci, from Cred. I, t. XXXII preserved at the Archive of the Camera Capitolina, Rome), folia 75v, 76r and 76v

It is believed (but we could not find any clear evidence of that) that amid the properties owned by Lucarucci and conferred to the Brotherhood of St. Benedict and St. Scholastica after his death it is to be also counted the historical building which hosts the church of the association, located at the Via di Torre Argentina, in downtown Rome.

As detailed in Pope Paul V's original bull *Pastoris aeterni*, the Confraternita was initially headquartered at the Church of St. Eustachio: a few steps away from the Pantheon, which was the place where many shops opened by the 'Norcini' were located. Subsequently, as reported by Pompilio Totti in his *Ritratto di Roma moderna* (1638, p. 370), they availed themselves of «an Oratory, who rented at the Church of St. Maria at Piazza della Colonna» (in Italian, «un'Oratorio, che a tempo pigliarono presso di S. Maria a Piazza Colonna»); afterwards, «in the end they purchased a house, which will be used as a church and a hospital for those belonging to their nation» (in Italian, «alla fine comprarono questa habitatione, che lor servirà per farci una chiesa, et uno spedale per quelli della natione»). So the Brotherhood will establish itself in a small building raising in the area of the Arco della Ciambella, also lying near the Pantheon: a church, with adjoining apartments, that still exists today.

Fig. 122 - The Church of St. Benedict and St. Scholastica (Via di Torre Argentina - Rome)

The three-storey building also provides, on the upper floors, various rooms used, at the time, as a «hospital for those belonging to their Nation» (in Italian, «uno spedale per quelli della natione»), as noted by Pompilio Totti in his *Ritratto di Roma moderna* (1638), for the accommodation of their fellow-citizens from Norcia who were on a trip to Rome or ill when in town. The rooms can be accessed through the entrance door which is set on Vicolo Sinibaldi.

s. Maria a piazza Colonna, & alla fine comprarono questa habitatione, che lor seruirà per farci vna chiesa, & vno spedale per quelli della natione. Per conformarsi poi con l'habito

Fig. 123 - The building belonging to the Archbrotherhood of St. Benedict and St. Scholastica as described by Pompilio Totti in his *Ritratto di Roma moderna* (Rome, 1638), p. 370

We can fully appreciate the central position of the church of the 'Norcini' by observing its location in a fine map of Rome drawn by Antonio Tempesta and published by Giovanni Domenico de Rossi in 1645, just a few decades after the establishment of the Brotherhood: in it, we can see the Pantheon, the Arco della Ciambella (the ruins of the Baths of Agrippa), Vicolo Sinibaldi with its terminating arch, and the building which accommodates, still today, the Church of St. Benedict and St. Scholastica.

Fig. 124 - The location of Church of St. Benedict and St. Scholastica in a map of Rome drawn by Antonio Tempesta (Rome, 1645 - detail), The Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York

Was that really one of the buildings originally owned in Rome by Pier Mattheo Lucarucci and bequeathed to the Brotherhood? Or, was that purchased by his fellow-brothers using the money inherited from the notary public?

We don't know for certain, though other scholars might possibly have found specific clues concerning this particular issue. For sure, the round

dedicatory slate installed on the façade reads «1619» — a year during which Lucarucci was still alive.

Fig. 125 - The church-to-come from *Statuti e privilegi della Venerabile Archiconfraternita de' Santi Benedetto e Scholaſtica di Roma* (Rome, 1625), Biblioteca Nazionale Centrale di Roma, p. 55

Sure enough, this very small church is better to be ranked amid the class of oratories, or chapels. The same Laerzio Cherubini, in the brotherhood's *Charters*, envisages a future in which the 'Norcini' would have benefited, sooner or later, of a veritable «church [...] when it will be built up» («finché sarà quella fabricata», in Italian).

Unfortunately the time for a church will never come; and the community of the 'Norcini' in Rome will continue to attend for centuries their tiny oratory raising at Via di Torre Argentina (at any cases to their complete satisfaction).

Certainly enough, all the brothers of the 'Arciconfraternita' should manifest, still today, a sentiment of endless gratitude to Pier Matteo Lucarucci and his fellow-brother from Norcia Gradasso Pitti (or Pitta), a military captain who served King Charles IX of France, who also bequeathed all his properties to the 'Norcini' in Rome, as similarly reported by Cherubini in the *Charters*.

Fig. 126 - Tombstones of Gradasso Pitta (left) and Pier Mattheo Lucarucci (right) in the Church of St. Benedict and St. Scholastica (Via di Torre Argentina - Rome)

The two of them rest in peace under the floor of the Brotherhood's small church, their tombstones lying just in front of the altar. It is mainly because of them that the 'Arciconfraternita dei Santi Benedetto e Scolastica' still lives and thrives in Rome in our present days, within the small church they were able to own and adorn thanks to those far-away, seventeenth-century munificent brothers.

Fig. 127 - Tombstone of Pier Mattheo Lucarucci in the Church of St. Benedict and St. Scholastica (Via di Torre Argentina - Rome)

7.4.6 The Brotherhood of St. Benedict and St. Scholastica — The Charters

Just like all the other brotherhoods and guilds established in Rome by the various national communities and universities of arts, the Archbrotherhood dedicated to the saints of Norcia devised its own charters, too, «which provide the law, and rule for the conservation of the institution, and for his fellow-brothers» («qual danno la norma, et regola per il mantenimento di essa, et suoi Confratri»).

Fig. 128 - The first section of the *Statuti e privilegi della Venerabile Archiconfraternita de' Santi Benedetto e Scholastica di Roma* (Rome, 1625), Biblioteca Nazionale Centrale di Roma, p. 1

It is the year 1625 and the author of the *Statuti* is a highly-qualified professional: Laerzio Cherubini himself, the Archbrotherhood's Prior and reputable lawyer at the papal curia. He is assisted by the Custodian of the association, Luca Trugillo (a wealthy man who, a few years later, in 1632, will also appear as the head of the Roman district of Sant'Eustachio — 'caput regionis' in Latin, 'caporione' in Italian; on his death, he will bequeath a considerable amount of money to the monastery of Santa Maria Maddalena al Quirinale).

mente, con il patrocinio de nostri Santi Protec-
tori Benedetto, & Scholastica.
Vostri Deuotifs. Fratelli.
Laertio Cherubini Priore, & Deput.
Luca Trugillo Guardiano, & Deput.

Fig. 129 - The authors of the *Statuti e privilegi della Venerabile Archiconfraternita de' Santi Benedetto e Scholastica di Roma* (Rome, 1625), Biblioteca Nazionale Centrale di Roma, introductory remarks

M. D. C. X. X. X. I. I.
MAGIS TRAZVS NOVVS
ad futurum Trimesore,
A. P. R. I. L. I. S, M. A. I. I, E. T. I. V. M. I. I.
1632

101
123
0120

Cos ^{tes}	Occavius Alandapins	Vincostabrim,
	Marcus Casalis	Campi Martis
	Petrus Vincentius de canalongo	S ^c Eustachij
Capita Regionum,		
	Claudius Cremona	Moncium,
	Lucianus Fabianus	Trinij,
	Philippus Juschetius	Columna
	Cp. Prosper Bona familia	Campi Martis
	Viderius Albrinus	Poncis
	Jo. Anconius Annetus	Pationis
	Hieronymus à Porta	Arénula
	Lucas Trugillus	S ^c Eustachij

Fig. 130 - Luca Trugillo (bottom) as 'caporione' of Rione St. Eustachio in Rome, from Cred. I, t. XXXIII preserved at the Archive of the Camera Capitolina, Rome), folium 123 (or 101 or 120)

Keeping the habits typical of a meticulous attorney, Cherubini sets out his *Charters* with the utmost accuracy and outstanding detail, with a view to clearly outline scopes, roles and procedures as if it were a contractual agreement being drafted for one of his clients. For this reason the '*Statuti*' include more than a hundred pages of clauses, arranged in fifty-eight chapters.

If we remember, more than two hundred brothers attended the very first procession held across the streets of Rome in 1615; and we can imagine

that in the subsequent years the Brotherhood, later Archbrotherhood, continued to grow, with a few hundreds of people from Norcia and the Valnerina joining the new association. So in 1625 Prior Cherubini was dealing with a company, including people of all sorts — from the rich notary public to the poorest manual worker — which definitely needed an internal regulation, as it appears from the concerned words he writes down in the introductory section:

«No town, though full of wise Citizens and encircled by strong walls, can enjoy the dear advantage of harmony and peace, if it is not steered and driven by the authority of law [...] Without the existence of a law and compliance to it, easily, and in a very short time, the town is led to total ruin. [...] Our spiritual town [... following] its growth with many munificent fellow-brothers [...] lacked a fundamental portion of itself, that is the Charters [...], and we were beginning to fear for its very cohesion, if God's Providence had not enlightened our mind, showing to us this clear and present danger...».

[In the original Italian text: «Niuna Città, anchorche di prudenti Cittadini ripiena, et di fortissime mura circondata, gode il caro frutto della concordia, et pace, se non viene governata, et retta con l'auttorità della legge [...] Et senza l'essentia, et osservanza di essa facilmente, et in brevissimo tempo si riduce ad una perpetua ruina. [...]. Questa nostra spiritual Città [...dopo] essersi accresciuta con moltitudine de buoni, et caritatevoli Confratri [...] mancava la principale, et essential parte di essa, che sono li Statuti [...] facilmente haveressimo temuto della stabilità sua, se la providenza divina non ci havesse illuminato l'intelletto, et fattoci conoscere questo imminente pericolo...»].

Too rapid a growth; too many people joining the new brotherhood, many of them affluent, many of them used to command. We can easily imagine that disputes and conflicts were beginning to arise amid the brothers, especially when we consider that the association was getting increasingly funded with money and properties: we can see it in the sentence written by Cherubini in Chapter XXI of Part II of the *Charters*:

«If the said Pier Mattheo [Lucarucci], in the said year 1615, when he wrote his last will and testament, could have known that at the time of his death, in 1622, so many goods would be available as there actually were in our

Archbrotherhood, he would have imparted instructions to effect them both [referring to two alternative testamentary dispositions, editor's note]».

[In the original Italian text: «Se il detto Pier Mattheo [Lucarucci], nel detto anno 1615, che fece il suo testamento havesse creduto, che nel tempo della sua morte, che fù dell'anno 1622, ci fossero stati tanti beni, quanti i furno trovati dalla nostra Archiconfrat. haveria ordinato si essequisse l'uno, e l'altro [riferendosi a due alternative disposizioni testamentarie, n.d.r.]...»].

Fig. 131 - The increasing wealth of the Archbrotherhood in the *Statuti e privilegi della Venerabile Archiconfraternita de' Santi Benedetto e Scholastica di Roma* (Rome, 1625), Biblioteca Nazionale Centrale di Roma, p. 58 and 59

The solution adopted by Laerzio Cherubini to close ranks and appease the brothers implied the creation of a multitude of Archbrotherhood's officers and posts, so as to satisfy the greed for power of the many would-be leaders and, at the same time, confine each officer within the strict, clearly-defined boundaries of his post.

That's why we find in the *Charters* a somewhat astounding list of officials, headed by the Prelate (formerly the Prior), who keeps «the great seal of the Archbrotherhood» (in Italian, «il sigillo grande dell'Archiconfraternita»). Then the Custodians («Guardiani») follow: the three of them, like ministries in a government, manage the day-by-day activities and affairs of the association, including the control over the incoming properties and money conferred by donors. The Chamberlain («Camerlengo») takes care of the financial administration of the Archbrotherhood, assisted by an Accountant («Computista»). A notary public, who is also a brother, holds the post of Secretary («Segretario»), with the task of writing down the decrees, resolutions and minutes of all meetings.

In addition, we also have a Superintendent («Proveditore») who is in charge of the management of the church and furniture; two Supervisors («Sindici») who will inspect the work carried out by all the other officers, keeping an eye on possible mistakes or misbehaviours; two Masters of the Novices («Mastri de' Novitij») responsible for the correct execution of all ceremonial procedures and the training of the new brothers. And there are also a Physician («Medico») and four Caregivers («Infermieri»), who will pay visits to the brothers suffering from sickness, providing medical services free of charge, praying together and giving the Holy Communion to them; and even an Attorney («Procuratore»), representing the Archbrotherhood in all litigations.

Fig. 132 - The (incomplete) list of officers of the Archbrotherhood in the *Statuti e privilegi della Venerabile Archiconfraternita de' Santi Benedetto e Scholastica di Roma* (Rome, 1625), Biblioteca Nazionale Centrale di Roma, p. 9 and 10

Is the officers' list over? Not at all. We must not forget the Archbrotherhood's sisters, who will enjoy their own, dedicated Prioress, flanked by two advising sisters and fourteen nurses (one for each district of Rome), in charge for charitable activities and the provision of medical assistance to the sisters.

This is not the end, as we also have specific officials dedicated to the management of the religious practices at the Archbrotherhood's church: a Prefect, who is a priest; two assistants; four sextons; and — last but not

least — twenty members of the choir. Then, a chaplain, who will live by the church («when it will be built», hopefully writes Cherubini, «edificata che sarà» in Italian), and a cleric. Furthermore, two envoys will physically reach all the brothers and sisters when needed, calling for their participation to celebrations, events, processions and general meetings. And we close this endless list with the Archivist, who will keep the Book of Brothers, the Book of Sisters, the Book of Donors, and many other books and registries.

Fig. 133 - The official seal of the Archbrotherhood in the *Statuti e privilegi della Venerabile Archiconfraternita de' Santi Benedetto e Scholastica di Roma* (Rome, 1625), Biblioteca Nazionale Centrale di Roma, closing pages

It is beyond the scope of the present paper to enter into the many details of the *Charters'* provisions. It will suffice, here, to note the following: since the very moment of its birth in Rome, the Archbrotherhood of St. Benedict and St. Scholastica has experienced an outstanding success, with a large number of people, mainly from Norcia, who decided to join the new

association — possibly many hundreds of brothers, if we consider the crowd of officials that Laerzio Cherubini devised to establish when editing his *Statuti*.

This is a clear sign of the fact that the 'Norcini' were now a significant presence in the capital of the Papal States. They were a lot, and some of them were remarkably affluent and influential.

That was the seventeenth century. And Norcia was manifestly in Rome, with all its people and crafts and skilled professionals.

Tizzone, the rustic 'Norcino', was still certainly there; but now, he was alone no more.

For he had his own Archbrotherhood. Like all other 'Nations' who lived and worked in the town of the Popes.

7.4.7 The Guild of the people from Norcia and Cascia in Rome — Their specific Charters

We saw in earlier paragraphs that trade, arts and crafts in Rome were strictly regulated by the papal authority, in an attempt to streamline the critical process of food provisioning to a city that was growing in population and whose economy was confined to the urban area itself, with virtually no export activities and a dramatic need for goods of all sorts, basically to be imported from other territories of the Papal States.

Since the fifteenth century, a plethora of guilds of all sorts had been appearing in town, subject to the formal approval of the Popes; those associations were intended to limit a specific trade or art, or even a profession, to its registered members, which made up a 'university', or community of workers, in Rome. Two instances of guilds we described earlier in the present paper were those of the Butchers and the Grocers.

In 1615, as we narrated in the previous paragraphs, the people from Norcia in Rome established their own 'national' Brotherhood, dedicated to the names and cult of St. Benedict and St. Scholastica. However, still they did

not have any guild for the association, within a specific university or community, of the 'Norcini' — to be intended as the people from Norcia who practised some particular art or arts in Rome, like for instance pig slaughtering or pork meat salting, for which the 'Norcini' were already known in the town of the Popes.

Could the Roman 'Norcini' miss this chance? Of course not.

So it is in this same seventeenth century that saw the foundation of the 'Arciconfraternita dei Santi Benedetto e Scolastica', the association of people from Norcia in Rome, that we also find the establishment of the *Università dei Norcini e Casciani di Roma (Guild of the people from Norcia and Cascia in Rome)*: a further association whose scope was the formal assignment to the 'Norcini' of a particular market area, a reserved trade conferred to them on an exclusive basis.

The problem was that they were too late. Many other guilds in Rome had already been in existence for two centuries, like the Butchers and the Grocers. So how could the 'Norcini' hope to win for themselves any portion of a food market that had already been carefully partitioned since hundreds of years?

While Laerzio Cherubini, a most influential man at the papal court, had fully centered his objective by setting up his Archbrotherhood with a perfect timing, so determining the total success of his initiative, the less illustrious 'Norcini' butchers (who were already late) even waited sixty years more: for their Charters (*Statuti, ordinazioni e facoltà*) got the approval by Pope Innocent XI only on July, 28 1677.

As we will see later, most probably this guild was already existent prior to this year; nonetheless, it had not obtained any previous recognition on a formal basis, as the first official approval of their newly-elaborated charters dates, as we said, to the year 1677.

So what sort of market share could they secure with such a late guild?

Sure enough, they did not succeed in getting any formal recognition of their actual, long-established role in the pigs' trade, as we will see below. They just obtained a very small portion of the existing food business: a limited

segment, of no interest to Butchers and Grocers at all. And let's see what we are talking about.

Fig. 134 - *Statuti, Ordinazioni e Facoltà dell'Università dei Norcini e Casciani di Roma* (manuscript Cred. XI, t. 106 preserved in the Archive of the Camera Capitolina, Rome), front page and folia 20 and 21

In the *Charters*, the people coming from Norcia are associated with those from Cascia, a small town sitting ten miles from the homeplace of St. Benedict, in the same area of the valley of the river Nera. They all are considered as practising the same crafts and arts in the capital city of the Papal States.

In the magniloquent introductory remarks, the *Charters* celebrate the role of the people from Norcia and Cascia in Rome, with a description of the activity carried out by them, aimed at supplying the capital city of luscious food:

«Almighty God, after creating Man out of His infinite knowledge, liked to create, to his benefit, also the Animals of the earth, the Birds in the Air, and Fish in the Sea [...] so that Man could feed on them as he liked. In his capacity Man introduced Hunting and Fishing, which were practiced since the very beginning of the World [...] for utility and professionally, as the

University of the Norcini and Casciani does in this Ancient City of Rome; they, for this practice, keep their Shops open, and sell Game and Fish all around Rome, and also they rent Bushes and Woods, where they keep Fowlers and Hunters to catch four-legged Animals as well as birds, and bring them all to the City of Rome to the benefit and convenience of Princes and all the people...».

[In the original Italian text: «L'Onnipotente Iddio, creato con la sua infinita sapienza l'Uomo, si compiacque a suo beneficio creare anco gli Animali della Terra, Ucelli dell'Aria, e Pesci del Mare [...] per cibarsene a suo piacere. Con questa facultà l'Uomo introdusse la Caccia e Pescagioni, che insino dal principio del Mondo sono state esercitate [...] per esercizio e professione, come in questa Alma Città di Roma fa l'Università de Norcini, e Casciani, li quali per detto esercizio, non solo tengono Botteghe aperte, e vanno vendendo la Caccia, e Pesce per Roma, ma anco prendono in affitto Macchie e Selve, dove ritengono Ucellatori, e Cacciatori, tanto a' volatili come a' Quadrupedi, e quelli fanno introdurre nella detta Città di Roma per Benefizio, e Commodità di Prencipi, e di tutto il Popolo...»].

Fig. 135 - The introductory remarks to the *Statuti, Ordinazioni e Facoltà dell'Università dei Norcini e Casciani di Roma* (manuscript Cred. XI, t. 106 preserved in the Archive of the Camera Capitolina, Rome), folium 3

So it seems that the main business conducted by the 'Norcini' and 'Casciani' in Rome is linked to hunting and fishing. No explicit reference to pigs and pork meat (a sensitive topic for both Butchers and Grocers) can be found here.

Why is it so? Let's try, in the next paragraph, to probe further into this specific issue.

7.4.8 The Guild of the people from Norcia and Cascia in Rome — Game, truffles and 'hidden' pigs

Let's analyse this issue in detail by reading Chapter II of the Charters, whose title is «Those who are included in the University» («Quelli che sono compresi nell'Università»):

«We state that the men of our University, and included in it, are all those who sell or resell Birds, and wild Animals, and Truffles, be it in the markets where auctions are held or at the Shops, Squares, and anywhere in the City of Rome, provided they are Norcini and Casciani, but even of any other Nation and Country, because this specific and particular prerogative is assigned to our University, and to no other».

Fig. 136 - Chapter II of the *Statuti, Ordinazioni e Facoltà dell'Università dei Norcini e Casciani di Roma* (manuscript Cred. XI, t. 106 preserved in the Archive of the Camera Capitolina, Rome), folium 5

[In the original Italian text: «Dichiariamo, che siano compresi, e siano Uomini della nostra Università tutti quelli, che vendano, ò rivendono Ucellami, e Salvaticini, e Tartufi, tanto nelli Cottij quanto nelle Botteghe, Piazze, e per la Città di Roma siano Norcini, e Casciani, ò pure d'altra Nazione, e Patria, essendo questo proprio, e particolar privilegio, et esercizio della nostra Università e non d'altra»].

We note, as a first observation, that the University includes all people from Norcia and Cascia who practice this trade, but does not intend to leave out the sellers working in the same business even if they are not from the two Apennine towns: this means that their business has an exclusive character, and all those who wish to work in this specific sector must forcibly join the University and be subject to its control, rules and regulations.

The second observation relates to «Birds, and wild Animals». Where are pigs? Where is pork meat? Why aren't they mentioned here?

This question has been a puzzling one for long («not a single word, as it can be noted, is dedicated to the processing of pork meat», writes D. Brignone in her article *La tradizione norcina della lavorazione delle carni suine nel tempo*, 2008, p. 16). However, the answer is simple: this late document could not overrun nor violate the market positions already set down, since centuries, in the *Charters* of the Butchers and Grocers, even though we know that the 'Norcini' worked with them and for them, and were also superseding the Butchers in the business of pig slaughtering. Nonetheless, the two Guilds would never accept to formally leave the market of pork meat to the 'Norcini', by allowing them to set down in writing a transfer of their own prerogatives to others. So the craftsmen from Norcia and Cascia just could not include any explicit reference to pigs in their own charters.

But what about 'hidden' references? The 'Norcini' — as cunning as their renowned theatrical champion Tizzone — succeeded in injecting a concealed mention about pigs in the *Charters'* text, subsequently approved by Pope Innocent XI.

In fact pigs are actually mentioned in the text, though they are hidden in the wording «wild Animals» («Salvaticini» in seventeenth-century Italian).

Because «wild Animals» do include pigs.

This is not a mere guess. We find an explicit evidence of such an inclusion in another Charter: namely, the *Charters of the University and Art of Fishmongers (Statuti dell'Università et Arte de' Pescivendoli)*, dating to 1636.

In Chapter XXII, the fishmonger's *Charters* list all the animals to be considered as included in the category of «Animals of the woods», or — in other words — wild:

«[...] The same is to be applied to the auctions of all sorts of Animals of the woods assigned to the said Art [the Fishmongers', editor's note], namely Pigs, Deers, Hares, Pheasants, Partridges, Pigeons, Doves, Thrushes, Starlings, and other small birds...».

[In the original Italian text: «[...] Il simile s'intenda circa il cottiare tutte sorte d'Animali silvestri spettante alla detta arte, cioè Porci, Cervi, Capri, Lepori, Fasciani, Starne, Palombi, Palombelle, Tordi, Storni, et altri Uccelli minuti...»].

Fig. 137 - Chapter XXII of the *Statuti dell'Università et Arte de' Pescivendoli* (manuscript Cred. XI, t. 60 preserved in the Archive of the Camera Capitolina, Rome), front page and folium 20

Here are the pigs. At that time, in the seventeenth century (just like in previous centuries), pigs were raised in woodlands and fed on acorns: so it's no surprise to find them listed together with wild animals, which live in the woods and are customarily considered as game to be chased by hunters.

So we can state, with a good degree of confidence, that the *Università dei Norcini e Casciani di Roma* was dealing with pigs, too, as they are included in the expression «wild Animals» (in old Italian «Salvaticini»).

Nonetheless, pigs are not explicitly mentioned in the Charters of the guild of the 'Norcini'. Why aren't they? As we said earlier, we think that the problem lies in the hard struggle being fought amid different Roman guilds as to the monopoly on pork butchery and related activities, as we will see later.

We must note that we are dealing with a text — approved by the top-level authority, Pope Innocent XI — which establishes the exclusive character of a specific trade: the *Charters* state that the business concerning the selling and reselling of wild animals and birds in Rome is assigned to the guild of 'Norcini' and 'Casciani' solely. So we may assume that, despite their efforts with the papal court, the 'Norcini' did not succeed in obtaining the approval of a draft version of the text possibly envisaging an exclusivity on, or even a share in, the trade of pigs and pork meat, out of the strong opposition raised by other guilds; and therefore they resorted to the submission, for papal approval, of a final document that mentioned no pigs. However pigs were there all the same, hidden in the wording; and this sort of subtlety left open to them the chance to litigate for claiming their grasp on pork meat trade in Rome, in an environment full of guilds, each with their own Charters, each loudly claiming a piece of the Roman market and related earnings.

That is why, in 1677, the 'Norcini' and 'Casciani', too, felt the need to mark their own territory, at least as much as they could obtain from the Pope, against a plethora of competitors.

Because one thing is sure: the 'Norcini' and 'Casciani' were not new to all that. Their trade was a long-established business.

They had been living and working in Rome for a very longtime; they had been constantly quarrelling with other guilds for their right to sell the goods they used to deal with; and now, in 1677, they were just trying to write down a regulation that intended to guard the boundaries of their exclusive markets, substantially in place possibly for at least two centuries, as it is

apparent from the Charter's introductory statement, which hints to the fact that this specific guild was already existent in 1677, but with no previous formal approval:

«[...] And though this University is utterly old in this city, which has always been the See to Kings and Princes from all over the World; nonetheless, owing to the good disposition of Men, the University has been led following a good natural beacon, and with no formal Charters; but we now see that all the Universities, for a better regulation of their Arts, live with their own Charters and Decrees. So we, the Men of the University of the Norcini and Casciani in Rome, gathered in our usual meeting [...], determined to devise the present Charters, and Chapters...».

Fig. 138 - The need for charters in the introductory statement to the *Statuti, Ordinazioni e Facoltà dell'Università dei Norcini e Casciani di Roma* (manuscript Cred. XI, t. 106 preserved in the Archive of the Camera Capitolina, Rome), folium 3

[In the original Italian text: «[...] e benché questa Università sia antichissima in questa città che è stata sempre la Sede de' Monarchi, e Prencipi di tutto il Mondo; tuttavia per la bontà degli Uomini l'Università è

stata guidata con un buon Lume naturale, e senza Statuti, ma vedesi che tutte l'Università per buona regola dell'Arti vivono con li Loro Statuti, e Riformanze. Però Noi Uomini tutti dell'Università dei Norcini e Casciani di Roma congregati in piena Adunata secondo il solito [...] abbiamo stabilito di fare li presenti Statuti, e Capitoli...»].

It was a sort of trade war, amid goods and markets, guilds and charters, each group looking for their profitable share of the business. And the 'Norcini', though already in the course of becoming leaders in the pigs' business, just arrived too late to obtain a formal recognition of their growing market position.

7.4.9 *The Guild of the people from Norcia and Cascia in Rome — The link to the Archbrotherhood*

Nonetheless the 'Norcini' and 'Casciani' had their own, qualified protection: their patron saints were St. Benedict, St. Scholastica and the blessed Rita of Cascia, as stated in the very first chapter of the *Charters*. And the consuls of the guild would celebrate annually a mass in the same place we already know from the history of the Archbrotherhood of the 'Norcini' in Rome: the small «Church of the said Saints lying near the Arco della Ciambella» (in Italian «nella Chiesa di detti Santi situata vicino all'Arco della Ciambella»).

Fig. 139 - The annual mass at the Church of St. Benedict and St. Scholastica in Rome, from Chapter I of the *Statuti, Ordinazioni e Facoltà dell'Università dei Norcini e Casciani di Roma* (manuscript Cred. XI, t. 106 preserved in the Archive of the Camera Capitolina, Rome), folia 4 and 5

That is why the Church of St. Benedict and St. Scholastica has always been the beloved place of the people from Norcia in Rome. Too much history has passed between its walls, from brotherhoods to guilds. And its story, the story of this small Church sitting near the Pantheon in downtown Rome, still continues in our present days.

Fig. 140 - The Church of St. Benedict and St. Scholastica (Via di Torre Argentina - Rome)

7.4.10 The Guild of the people from Norcia and Cascia in Rome — The seventeenth-century litigations

In the previous paragraph, we have seen that in 1677 a new Guild was born in Rome, that of the 'Norcini' and 'Casciani', with their assigned market

concerning game, truffles and — even though in a sort of covert, non-exclusive way — pork meat.

But we must consider that Rome was already populated with an amazing number of guilds, each managing its own market on an exclusive basis. What happened when the Guild of the 'Norcini' and 'Casciani' plunged with their new *Charters* into this multifarious, turbulent sea?

The answer is simple: they began to litigate.

As we already illustrated in a previous paragraph, starting from the late fifteenth century the local economy in Rome had begun to be arranged in guilds of crafts and arts that covered all the possible market segments of goods and services. A comprehensive list is provided by Emmanuel Pierre Rodocanachi, who analysed in detail the Roman guilds and their characteristics in his study *Les corporations ouvrières a Rome depuis la chute de l'Empire Romain* (Paris, 1894).

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Cappellari	II, 133	Nevaroli	I, 325	Sensali di Ripa e Ripetta	I, 233
Caprettari	I, 167	Norcini	I, 187	Setajoli	II, 93
Carbonari	I, 393	Notari capitolini	II, 429	Speziali	II, 277
Carrettieri	II, 25	Ogliarari	I, 355	Tabacari	I, 299
Casciani	I, 187	Orefici	II, 267	Tamburini	II, 415
Cocchieri	II, 267	Orefici lavoratori	II, 323	Tavernari	I, 259
Cordari	II, 319	Ostai	I, 45	Tessitori	II, 73
Coronari	II, 229	Ostai di Borgo	I, 289	Tintori	II, 107
Cottiatori di pesce	I, 147	Parrucchieri	II, 259	Vaccinari	II, 157
Credenzieri	I, 211	Pasticcieri	I, 263	Vascellari	I, 381
Cucchi	I, 265			Vermicellari	I, 101
Doratori	I, 451			Vermicellari garzoni	I, 111
Droghieri	I, 315			Vignaroli	I, 41
Fabbricanti di tessuti	II, 33				
Falegnami	I, 439				

Fig. 141 - The full list of historical guilds in Rome as presented by Emmanuel Pierre Rodocanachi in his *Les corporations ouvrières a Rome depuis la chute de l'Empire Romain* (Paris, 1894), Vol. 2, p. 457

According to Fiorenza Gemini (*Due parrocchie romane nel Settecento: aspetti di storia demografica e sociale*, in *Quaderni della rassegna degli Archivi di Stato*, no. 67, 1992, p. 124), «it can be perceived a veritable atomization of the food sector», with a proliferation of guilds and charters: «it was a clear sign», adds Gemini, «of the drawbacks of a corporative arrangement [of the businesses], which on one side stifled all business endeavours, with a rigid protection of the various positions of exclusivity and traditional productive balances; and, on the other side, this arrangement left open no other path than the appropriation of market segments belonging to others, with a giant waste of resources in quarrels and court litigations».

Actually, explains Gemini with effective words, «in the food trade it was to be seen, to the highest degree, a chronic pathology that affected the whole business in Rome: everybody was seeking to sell everything».

Yes, because if I cannot expand my business outside Rome (let's remember that the export of goods and services was virtually non-existent, owing to a limited local productions of goods and the isolation of the capital city of the Papal States, encircled by the almost-inhabited Roman Campagna), the only chance I have to make more money is to win additional portions of the local market for myself. But market shares were regulated by guilds' Charters: so the history of local trade in Rome is also a history of litigations, sentences and decrees, with each guild working on specific trade area and each wishing to expand its own business to the detriment of the other guilds.

Let's consider, as a most significant instance, our 'Norcini'. First, they have their monopolistic food segments, formally including game and truffles, and — as we saw in the previous paragraph — an actual, informal standing in the pork meat market; secondly, they have in place agreements with other guilds to sell other types of food (namely fish); third, they litigate and pursue legal cases to defend their established market position. Let's enter this turbulent arena to illustrate the three points listed above (monopoly, agreements, litigations) to see how a guild's life could be adventurous in seventeenth-century Rome.

The area of activity formally assigned to the 'Norcini' was the trade of game and truffles, as stated in the Charters of the *Università dei Norcini e*

Casciani di Roma. However, as we find in the *Trattato sopra il Presidentato della Grascia di Roma* written by Demetrio Andretti and the studies conducted by Emmanuel Pierre Rodocanachi, the principal business segment occupied by the 'Norcini' was pork meat, including butchery and seasoning: this sector could not be explicitly mentioned in their *Charters*, but is hinted to in the «wild Animals» locution.

Secondly, the 'Norcini' had in place a specific agreement on a particular food, namely fish: they had arranged a deal with the Guild of Fishmongers (*Università dei Pescivendoli*) to sell sea products, too. The deal is clearly stated in Chapter II of the *Statuti, Ordinazioni e Facoltà dell'Università dei Norcini e Casciani di Roma*:

«Then [in our University are included] all the people from Norcia and Cascia who sell fish, be this in the fish market at the Pescaria grande or at Piazza della Rotonda, Piazza di Panico and any other squares, and anywhere in Rome, because the right to sell Fish was conferred to our University through public deeds from the University of Fishmongers in Rome by paying fifteen scudi per Year in favor of the Chapel of the Illustrious Apostle St. Andrew, which is located at the Church of St. Angelo in Pescaria».

Fig. 142 - 'Norcini' selling fish from the *Statuti, Ordinazioni e Facoltà dell'Università dei Norcini e Casciani di Roma* (manuscript Cred. XI, t. 106 preserved in the Archive of the Camera Capitolina, Rome), folium 5

[In the original Italian text: «Item tutti li Norcini, e Casciani, che rivendano Pesce, si in Pescaria grande, come alla Rotonda, Panico, et altra Piazza, et anco per Roma, perché questa facultà di vender Pesce l'ha havuta la nostra Università per istrumenti publici dalla medesima Università de Pescivendoli di Roma col peso di scudi quindici l'Anno per la Cappella del Glorioso Apostolo Sant'Andrea situata nella Chiesa di Sant'Angelo in Pescaria»].

Since the Middle Ages, the Pescaria, or fish market, was held at the Porticus Octaviae, where the Church of St. Angelo was actually incorporated within the Roman ruins. In the church is still present the Chapel of St. Andrew, the fisherman Apostle, together with his brother Peter: this holy place was established as the Chapel of the University of Fishmongers in 1571, and since March 1st, 1583 the 'Norcini' had been handing out 15 scudi per year to the same Chapel in order to have the right to sell fish in Rome, as attested in an eighteenth-century litigation retrieved in the Fondo Camerale II — Sezione 10 *Arti e mestieri* preserved at the Archivio di Stato di Roma (Claudio De Dominicis, 2005, p. 58).

So the 'Norcini' legally expanded their activities, mainly devoted to the trade of game and pork meat, so as to include fish.

But the 'Norcini', late as they were in terms of elaboration of their charters, also craved to conquer the market mainly controlled by other guilds: we find a curious instance of this in the documents which describe the litigations involving the people from Norcia and Cascia and the University of the Sellers of Chicken Meat, (in Italian, the 'Pollaroli').

The Charters of the 'Pollaroli', written in 1605 (seven decades before those of the 'Norcini'), detailed in Chapter XXXIV the list of the food that the 'Pollaroli' were allowed to sell with full exclusivity:

«We state and order and declare that the 'pollaroli' of Rome can raise and sell all the foodstuff below, that is Chickens, Capons, Poultry, Pigeons, Doves, Turkeys, Eggs, Partridges, Pheasants, Hares, Rock pigeons, Quails and any other sorts of Birds, and all such foodstuff must be intended as food and goods assigned to the Art of the 'Pollaroli'».

[In the original Italian text: «Statuimo et ordiniamo e dichiariamo, che li pollaroli di Roma possino tenere e vendere tutte le Infrascritte robbe cioè Galline, Capponi, Pollami, Piccioni, Palombi, Polli d'India, Ova, Starne, Pernici, Fagiani, Lepori, Palombi Palombelle, Quaglie et ogni altra sorte di Ucellami e tutte queste robbe Siano e S'intendono esser robbe e Mercanzie Spettanti all'Arte de Pullaroli»].

Fig. 143 - The food trade assigned to the 'Pollaroli' from the *Statuti et Arte de Pollaroli di Roma* (manuscript Cred. XI, t. 47 preserved in the Archive of the Camera Capitolina, Rome), folium 23

And what did the 'Norcini' and 'Casciani' do? In their Charters, written in 1677, thus more than seventy years later, as we already saw they reserved for themselves, in Chapter II, the trade of «Birds, and wild Animals, and Truffles», even if pertaining to «any other Nation and Country, because this specific and particular prerogative is assigned to our University, and to no other». For good measure, they also added a Chapter XI, in which they boldly stressed the following points:

«Considering that our University has the right to sell all sorts of Birds, Wild animals, and Truffles, being this our profession and art of the Norcini and Casciani since time immemorial, and up to the present time; and considering that many others belonging to different Universities of our City of Rome, not included in Ours, dare sell and keep in their Shops for sale Birds, and Wild animals, without acquiring the Licence from our Consuls

and Chamberlain, and without paying the due tax, so we state and order that no one, belonging to any other Nations, Universities, Charters or Licences nor Faculties, is allowed for the future to sell or resell, in both retail or wholesale quantities, any sort of Birds, Wild animals or Truffles, without getting in advance the written licence, or authorising form, from our Consuls and Chamberlain, and paying the due tax...».

Fig. 144 - The 'Norcini' invade the market originally assigned to the 'Pollaroli', from the *Statuti, Ordinazioni e Facoltà dell'Università dei Norcini e Casciani di Roma* (manuscript Cred. XI, t. 106 preserved in the Archive of the Camera Capitolina, Rome), folia 12r and 12v

[In the original Italian text: «Perché la nostra Università ha la facultà di vendere tutte sorti d'Ucellami, Salvaticini, e Tartufi, essendo questa la propria professione, et Arte de Norcini, e Casciani da tempo immemorabile in qua, E perché molti d'altra Università della Città di Roma, non compresi in questa Nostra, ardiscono rivendere e ritenere nelle Loro proprie Botteghe per vendere Ucellami, e Salvaticini, senza prendere alcuna Licenza da Nostri Consoli e Camerlengo, né pagare la nostra Tassa, però ritiniamo, statuimo, e comandiamo, che nessuno di qualsivoglia Nazione, et Università, Statuto o altra Licenza, e facultà possa per l'avvenire vendere,

rivendere, né a minuto, né all'ingrosso, alcuna sorte di Ucellami, Savaticine, e Tartufi, se prima non avere preso la Licenza in scriptj, ò Bollettino da nostri Consoli e Camerlengo, e non gli pagarà la Tassa...»].

Heaven forbid! With their unacceptable Chapter XI, the 'Norcini' had dared too much. They were entering, by brute force, the traditional field fully belonging to the 'Pollaroli', who certainly did not restrain from striking back against such impudent invaders.

In November 1680, the University of 'Pollaroli' sued the University of 'Norcini' and 'Casciani' before the President of the Grascia, Giovanni Battista Costaguti: an epical fight took place between Chapter XXXIV of the 'Pollaroli' and Chapter XI of the 'Norcini', with their mutually-conflicting provisions.

Who was the winner? At last the 'Norcini and Casciani', who had veritably gone too far, were severely chastised by the President of the Grascia and his court, «pro Tribunale sedentes et solum Deum pre oculis habentes», using a very harsh wording:

«We state, resolve and declare and [...] pronounce the following sentence: it is fully legitimate for the University, the Consuls and all the Men of the art of the 'Pollaroli', at the agreed time in their shops, to freely buy and keep and sell chickens, Capons, poultry, Doves, [...] and any sort of birds and flying animals, both domesticated and wild, as allowed by the Charters of their art at Chapter XXXIV [...]; therefore the Charters of the 'Norcini' and 'Casciani', of very recent publication, as to Chapter XI [...] is invalidated: thus the University, Consuls and Men of the art of the 'Pollaroli' effectively resist and in no way they are compelled to be subject to the said taxes and obligations, no matter how they are imposed or will be imposed by the Consuls and the said University of the 'Norcini'; nor any tax and burden is to be imposed, either directly or indirectly; nor any unjust and rash nuisance, abuse and trouble be carried out or envisaged by the said Consuls and University of the 'Norcini' and 'Casciani'...»

[In the original Latin text: «Pronunciamus, decernimus, declaramus ac [...] sententiamus: Licisse et licere Universitati, Consulibus et Hominibus artis pullariae debitis temporibus in eorum Apothecis Libere emere et retinere et vendere gallinas, Capones, pullos, Columbas, [...] et cuiusuis generis aves

et volueres sive domesticos sive silvestres iuxta tenore Statuti eorum artis Cap. XXXIV [...]; et proinde Statutus ab Universitate Nurcinorum et Cascianorum novissime editum, quatenus Cap. XI [...] suppositis nullatenus officere Universitate, Consulibus et Homines artis Pullariae eosque propterea minime sublacere predictis taxibus seu oneribus quavis modo impositis vel imponendi à Consulibus et Universitate Nurcinorum predicta vel ratione huiusmodi taxationum et oneribus posse ab his gravari neque directe neque indirecte molestationesque vexatione et quaeunque perturbationes temerarias et iniustas fuisse ac defacto presumptas eisdemque Consulibus et Universitati Nurcinorum et Cascianorum...»].

Fig. 145 - An excerpt of the sentence concerning the litigation between 'Pollaroli' and 'Norcini', from the *Statuti et Arte de Pollaroli di Roma* (manuscript Cred. XI, t. 47 preserved in the Archive of the Camera Capitolina, Rome), folia 4r and 4v

For the 'Norcini', the above litigation proved to be a total, downright defeat, with the judge also adding that the defendants «shall from now on and forever be silent on the sentenced matter» (in Latin «de et super premissis perpetuum silentium imponendus»), with the further obligation to reimburse the litigation costs («in expensis condemnantes»).

So the attack carried out by the 'Norcini' against the 'Pollaroli' ended in utter failure.

But what can we say about the attempts carried out by other guilds to expand their own activities in the native markets of the people from Norcia and Cascia? What about pork meat and game?

Many Universities were looking greedily at those markets. And many tried to step into the traditional business area of the *Università dei Norcini e Casciani*.

Let's take into consideration those same Fishmongers who had in place a specific agreement with the 'Norcini' on fish. They, too, demanded a share in the meat market, and strived to win increasing portions of it for themselves.

As we already saw in a previous chapter, they had included the meat business right into their Charters (Chapter XXII) so as to confer a legal basis to their claims: «[...] all sorts of Animals of the woods assigned to the said Art [the Fishmongers', editor's note], namely Pigs, Deers, Hares, Pheasants, Partridges, Pigeons, Doves, Thrushes, Starlings, and other small birds...».

Their Charters dates back to 1636, and the Charters of the Norcini and Casciani to 1677: a century later, in 1737, they still had litigations with one another on the exclusivity of the respective trades, as shown by the legal proceeding which we mentioned earlier in this same paragraph (Fondo Camerale II — Sezione 10 *Arti e mestieri*, Archivio di Stato di Roma — Claudio De Dominicis, 2005, p. 58). Other litigations, involving the 'Norcini', are reported by De Dominicis in his research (p. 99). An endless story, whose origin lies in the confused regulation model established with the introduction of mutually-conflicting charters.

But, beside the litigations concerning the market segments formally assigned to each specific guild within their charters, we must always remember that the actual situation, beyond the clauses written in those same charters, was seeing a competing community of 'Norcini' that, leveraging on their skilled craft, had gradually conquered the market of pork meat in Rome, though informally and on a non-exclusive basis.

What was the situation in this specific business area? What the Butchers and Grocers had to say about it? We will try to investigate these tricky points in the following paragraph.

7.5 The 'Norcini' and the Guilds of the 'Macellari' and 'Pizzicaroli'

7.5.1 How to win for themselves a portion of a strictly-controlled market

Even though in the *Statuti* of the *Università dei Norcini e Casciani di Roma* pigs and pork meat are not referenced, we must always bear in mind the fundamental references we started from in the present essay: the words written by Demetrio Andretti, the president of the Roman 'Grascia' at the middle of the eighteenth century, and the additional remarks provided by French historian Emmanuel Pierre Rodocanachi in the subsequent century.

They both refer to a primary, established role of the 'Norcini' in Rome as to the supply of pork meat, both fresh and processed.

Andretti wrote that «the first to introduce in Rome the art of salting Pork Meat were the Norcini» and that «salted meat [... was] processed by the Guild of Norcini», because «without them, the Grocers [in Rome] would never be able to skillfully process that sort of meat; so they necessarily need to avail themselves of the Norcini». Furthermore, «in the course of time [...] the Butchers themselves just gave up the pig slaughtering business: so this activity was only carried out by the Norcini and, rather than the Butchers, by the Grocers».

Rodocanachi strains this scenario even further, by bestowing on the 'Norcini' a full, exclusive control on the Roman market of pork meat: «Since ancient times [...] the inhabitants of two small towns, Norcia and Cascia [...] had an exclusivity over the provision to Rome of game and pigs. [...] The Umbrian traders created a monopoly to their advantage and a papal decision was needed to abolish it. The Roman butchers were, on this specific subject, dependent on the 'Norcini'; and the papal decrees concerning butchery, which are numerous, are intended for the 'Norcini' rather than for the butchers».

In this framework, even though all this is not reported in the *Charters* of the *Università dei Norcini e Casciani*, we know for sure that the 'Norcini' processed and even sold, at the very center of the Papal States, «Loin and Sausages, and the remaining parts are conveniently salted, especially for the preparation of Salami, which are then sold to the Grocers at Easter» (in

Italian «Lombetto e di Salsicce, et il restante procura di salare, in specie col fare dei Salami quali poi à Pasqua di Resurrezione [...] procura di farne contratto di vendita alli Pizzicaroli»), as further detailed by Andretti.

The above scenario is also confirmed by the seventeenth-century papal decrees we could retrace — they were illustrated in a previous paragraph — which mention «Butchers, Norcini and Grocers and others, who all sell pork meat», including fresh meat («loin, ribs and other cuts»), and also «Butchers, Norcini, Makers of Sausages, and others, who hold meat of any sort for sale».

How did the 'Norcini' win for themselves such a relevant position within the food market in Rome? And what was their relation with the powerful, existing Guilds of the Butchers and the Grocers?

The 'Norcini', as we held earlier in this same article, knew how to do the job. So, thanks to their craft and a full knowledge of the secrets of their art, developed in Norcia throughout many centuries, they conquered a principal position in the food market of Rome: they waged no war against the existing Guilds, they just made themselves indispensable to those Guilds, which earnestly began to look for their valuable professional services.

The result of this sort of stealthy penetration process into a market criss-crossed by fixed exclusive domains, assigned to guilds, was that the 'Norcini' could never formally state, in the Charters of their own Guild, with full papal approval, the notable condition and significant role that they had achieved in the trade of pork meat and salted pork meat in Rome. Not a single word will be written down in the Charters as to this topic (apart from a hidden reference to pigs, as we explained earlier), because the other Guilds were on the watch and would not allow any formally-stated invasion of their captive markets. As a confirmation of all this, we saw that when the 'Norcini' tried to grasp a portion of the chicken market in Rome, they were immediately chastised by the Guild of 'Pollaroli' before the papal court, whose sentence was a hard blow for the people from Norcia.

That is why it is so difficult to find explicit written references to the role of the 'Norcini' in Rome. Their market position could not be fully formalised. Yet we have many confirmations of their established renown and

recognition within the Roman population at all levels, as reported by Andretti and many papal decrees.

And we must not forget, as we will see in later paragraphs, that their renown will continue to grow across the centuries, until we will find that, in the nineteenth century, the word 'Norcino' in Rome will mean 'butcher' par excellence, and their 'norcineria' shops will spread across all urban districts of the city.

But before we proceed with a brief description of what the 'Norcini' will be in Rome in the subsequent centuries, let's confront with a final question concerning their actual role in Rome: was their market position on pigs ever marked by the golden medal of full exclusivity, as a certain popular opinion holds?

On the basis of the convoluted history we have been retracing in the previous paragraphs, the answer is obviously in the negative. And let's see why.

7.5.2 The 'Norcini', a mythical monopoly on pork meat in Rome, and a recap of the whole story

A certain popular feeling — supported here and there by non-professional articles on the history of the 'norcineria' in Rome — claims that the 'Norcini', throughout various centuries, have been the sole suppliers of pork meat in the capital of the Papal States, with a presumption of exclusivity which would be confirmed by the actual presence of many 'norcinerie' (shops that sell salted pork meat products) in contemporary Rome.

However, we think that we can consistently state that the above claim is not true: the 'Norcini' have never enjoyed the advantages of a captive market in Rome, as they have always been striving for business space across hundreds of years of competition with the Butchers and the Grocers (after all, the same occurs today).

This incorrect vision was initially introduced by Emmanuel Pierre Rodocanachi during the nineteenth century. The French scholar appears to

be fully confident in what he states: «the rights of hunting and selling pork meat were only reserved to the traders of Cascia and Norcia», he repeats, «and the regulations on the subject in the area of Rome applied in particularly to them».

But where did he draw this piece of information from? At the present stage of our research, we could find no single document hinting to such a drastic exclusivity; so we cannot confirm this specific point at all.

Further work is certainly needed at the Vatican Apostolic Library and Italy's national archives, both preserving the official administrative documentation issued by the Papal States throughout many centuries, to better investigate the matter and find the specific documents Rodocanachi is referring to.

Nonetheless, after having retraced in the present paper the whole story of the presence of the 'Norcini' in Rome, we can only subscribe in full to Demetrio Andretti's qualified testimony: no monopoly by the 'Norcini' could exist on pigs and cured meat, provided that those specific market domains were formally assigned to the 'Macellari' and 'Pizzicaroli' as exclusive trades of theirs.

If we re-open the pages of their respective Charters, we find, as to the Butchers, that «anybody who intends to open a slaughterhouse in Rome, must pay for his own admission [to the Guild of Butchers] to the Consuls» and that «no Butcher can sell in his Slaughterhouse any meat without the permission of the Consuls» («se alcuna persona volchi nuovamente far Macello in Roma, di per se sia tenuto et debba paghare per suo introito et admissione alli Consoli [dei Macellari] [...] che nessuno Macellaro possa vender ne far vender nel suo Macello carne, et altri senza Licenza di Consoli», in Italian); and, as to the Grocers, that «all the listed stuff and goods, that is Pork Meat, salted of any sort, like Bacon, Lard, Soppressata, and Sausages of all sorts, Pork and Buffalo tongues, [...] are intended to be, and must be, by legal statement, called and recognised as Stuff and Goods pertaining to the Art and University of the Grocers of Rome» («tutte e singole infrascritte robbe, e mercanzie, cioè Carne di Porco salata d'ogni sorte, come Ventresche, Lardo, Strutto, e Sogna, Sopprassate, e Salsiccioni di tutte le sorti, Lingue di Porco, e di Bufala [...] s'intendono, esser debbiano, e siano con effetto nuncupate, chiamate, e dette Robbe, e

Mercanzie dell'Arte, et Università de Pizzicaroli di Roma, et ad essa Università, et Arte spettante», in Italian).

Fig. 146 - Exclusive markets for Butchers (left) and Grocers (right) from the *Statuta Artis Macellariorum de Urbe* (manuscript Cred. XI, t. 87 preserved in the Archive of the Camera Capitolina, Rome), folia 6v-7r, and from the *Statuti dell'Università, ed Arte de Pizzicaroli di Roma* (manuscript Cred. XI, t. 48 preserved in the Archive of the Camera Capitolina, Rome), p. 52

So fresh meat (including pork meat) and salted pork meat were exclusive markets assigned to the Guilds of Butchers and Grocers. And, formally speaking, this assignment will remain substantially unchanged throughout the centuries.

Thus the 'Norcini' in Rome have never enjoyed any exclusive rights of production and sales within the market of pork meat in the town of the Popes. They did not even succeed in including pork meat in their *Charters*, out of the opposition of the two powerful, existing Guilds.

However, this does not mean that the 'Norcini' hadn't their stance — and a principal one — within the business of pork meat in Rome.

Actually, and throughout the centuries, the 'Norcini' won a market space for themselves by cunningly insinuating into the market of Butchers and Grocers with their offer of specialised services, by virtue of their art and craft.

They began to enter this market quietly, at the middle of the fifteenth century, with their first migration to Rome. As we guessed in a previous paragraph, possibly they first popped up in town as simple, uncontrolled 'makers of sausages' ('salcicciari'), soon constrained under the Guild of Butchers.

But in a short time the 'Norcini', leveraging on the attractiveness of their specific know-how on pig slaughtering and taking advantage of people's love for their salted meat products, began to find their own space and succeeded in entering a market that was jealously guarded by the existing brotherhoods and guilds.

During an earlier phase, surely the 'Norcini' just slaughtered pigs for the Butchers, and also processed and cured pork meat to obtain sausages and other salted products on behalf of the Grocers. They were good at doing all that, and the existing Guilds just used them as manual, skilled workers.

But then, in the course of the sixteenth century, things began to change.

The Butchers started to leave the pigs' market: in fact we must consider that the core business of the Guild of Butchers were not pigs, but mainly beef and lamb, as the fresh meat of slaughtered pigs need additional processing to salt and season it — a skill, time and techniques that Butchers did not have. So, as Demetrio Andretti reports, «later, the Butchers themselves just gave up the pig slaughtering business: so this activity was only carried out by the Norcini and, rather than the Butchers, by the Grocers», with the latter already provided by the Butchers with «the license to slaughter pigs [...] under the payment of an annual tax».

And the 'Norcini', still lacking their own Charters and missing any formal recognition of their actual market role, just continued to gradually expand their activities until they got to carry out the full cycle of pork meat processing, including slaughtering, butchery and preparation of cuts, and finally salting and seasoning, therefore superseding the local butchers and leaving them out of this specific business line, as the same Rodocanachi writes: «the Roman butchers were, on this specific subject [pigs, editor's note], dependent on the 'Norcini'».

But the Grocers were still there. And they were fully active in the pig business, as they, too, carried out slaughtering and salting.

This obviously means that the 'Norcini' could never conquer any exclusivity on that. And when they tried to draft their own *Charters*, sure enough they were not permitted to write down, in it, anything about pigs (except a 'hidden' reference to 'wild animals'), lest they got any formal recognition of their actual market position.

The Grocers were a powerful Guild. And, as Demetrio Andretti explicitly writes, they would have certainly liked to expel those annoying 'Norcini' from the pig market, yet with no success:

«The Grocers [...], not placated by the license they got from the Butchers which allowed them to slaughter pigs and salt their meat, and wishing to be the only players in this specific meat market, have tried, and still are trying, to pursue all means to drive the Norcini out of Rome».

[In the original Italian language: «Li Pizzicaroli [...] non bastandogli l'ottenuto permesso di macellare li Porci e di farne le Salate, ma per voler essere soli à tal mercimonio di Carni hanno cercato, e tuttavia cercano ogni strada possibile per discacciare da Roma li Norcini»].

But the Grocers' attempts proved unsuccessful. The 'Norcini' in Rome were there to stay, because the market (both the populace and the aristocracy) craved for their toothsome products. And the same Grocers still were forced to address those most-hated 'Norcini' as their suppliers, as clearly recounted by Demetrio Andretti:

«Without them [the 'Norcini', editor's note], the Grocers [in Rome] would never be able to skillfully process that sort of meat; so they necessarily need to avail themselves of the Norcini, who year after year come to Rome and work the said meat».

[In the original Italian text: «Senza di questi neppure essi Pizzicaroli potrebbero ad uso di arte farne il lavoriero, dovendosi necessariamente valersi dei Norcini, che di anno in anno vengono a lavorargli dette Carni»].

So, at the very end of this quick recap of the findings of our research, we can confidently state that French historian Emmanuel Pierre Rodocanachi was wrong: the 'Norcini' never had, as he writes, «an exclusivity over the provision to Rome of [...] pigs»; it is not true that «the Umbrian traders created a monopoly to their advantage».

There has never been any formal monopoly, nor any actual one on field.

Nonetheless, the 'Norcini' were remarkably good at doing their work. And they won for themselves a market in Rome, as primary de facto suppliers of pork meat to the town of the Popes, together with the 'Pizzicaroli'.

And, in the seventeenth century, they could set up their own rich, influential, illustrious, Archbrotherhood, that still exists today.

A great achievement, which was obtained by the people from Norcia through hard work. And outstanding craft.

7.6 How things went in the end: from the eighteenth century onwards

We leave now the seventeenth century, the period during which the 'Norcini' in Rome eventually achieved their full success with a complete recognition of their social presence in the capital city of the Papal States. An Archbrotherhood was born, a University was established, their respective Charters were approved, and a de facto relevant position in the Roman market of pork meat had been conquered.

Now history, in Rome, was on their side.

The subsequent centuries will be a story of further renown and additional successes.

Because the butchers par excellence, in the town of the Popes, will be known under the name of 'Norcini'. And their shops, the 'norcinerie', will be the places where the citizens of Rome will buy the most luscious products based on pork meat. For hundreds of years and up to our present days.

A market position they will always share with the 'Pizzicaroli', as we highlighted in the previous chapters and fully confirmed by the further witnesses, spanning across the eighteenth, nineteenth and twentieth centuries, which we will illustrate in the present paragraph.

We cannot retrace the whole story of the 'Norcini' until contemporary Rome, as we contented to shed a new, unprecedented light on their early history in the capital of the Papal States; yet we will provide some glimpse about their ceaseless presence in Rome, with the same role as masters of the most toothsome food.

In the second half of the eighteenth century, the report on the Roman 'Grascia' written by Cardinal Fabrizio Ruffo, treasurer-general of the Apostolic Camera, fully acknowledges the fundamental role of the 'Norcini', together with the Grocers, in the supply of pork meat to Rome, with the presence in the text of many direct references to both of them.

Fig. 147 - 'Norcini' and 'Pizzicaroli' from *Memorie economiche di Monsignor Fabrizio Ruffo tesoriere generale della Reverenda Camera Apostolica su vari articoli concernenti l'approvvigionamento delle Grascie per Roma* (Cesena, 1789), p. 14, 33, 34 and 56

So now both the 'Norcini' and the 'Pizzicaroli' are the main suppliers within the Roman business related to pigs. And who is the most important between the two? The answer is contained in a paper dedicated to the 'Grascia' and relating to the same period of time (Marina D'Amelia, *La crisi di un mercato protetto: approvvigionamenti e consumo della carne a Roma nel XVIII secolo*, in *Mélanges de l'Ecole française de Rome. Moyen-Age*,

Temps modernes, Vol 87, no. 2, 1975, p. 530), based on a detailed analysis of the original documentation:

«On the basis of 12,000 heads of cattle (pigs) slaughtered [on average during a year, editor's note], 8,000 went to the 'norcini' butchers and 4,000 to the grocers; the ['norcini'] butchers processed on average salami for 200,000 pounds and ventricina for 40/45,000 pounds, and the major portion was sold as fresh meat. The grocers, on their side, processed on average during a year: hams for 120,000 pounds; ventricine for 120,000 pounds, mortadella for 140.000 pounds...».

[In the original Italian text: «Sulla base di 12.000 capi suini macellati [mediamente in un anno, nota dell'autore], 8.000 andavano ai macellai 'norcini' e 4.000 ai pizzicagnoli; i macellai [norcini] producevano in media 200.000 libbre di salame e 40/45.000 libbre di assogna, e il grosso veniva venduto come carne fresca. I pizzicagnoli, invece, producevano in media ogni anno: prosciutti per 120.000 libbre, ventresche 120.000 libbre, mortadelle 140.000 libbre...»].

According to D'Amelia, annually two thirds of the pigs were conferred to the 'Norcini' for slaughtering and the subsequent production of both fresh cuts and salted pork meat. The Grocers handled only one third of the pigs, even though they, too, processed a most considerable quantity of hams, mortadella, and other salted meat.

So the eighteenth-century Roman market of pork meat was securely in the hands of both the 'Norcini' and the Grocers, in accordance to a process that had been starting in the previous centuries, with the gradual exclusion of the Butchers from this specific business. And we must remember that many 'Norcini' also worked for the Guild of Grocers, so part of the products processed by the Grocers were actually prepared by 'Norcini' craftsmen.

Let's give now a glimpse of the life of the 'Norcini' in Rome during the nineteenth century. We could not but choose the brilliant visionary masterpiece written by Costantino Maes, a Roman librarian and passionate historian, in his work *Curiosità romane (Fun facts about Rome)* published in 1885:

«The grocers at Easter — The faith of the grocers, or, as they are called in Rome, the 'pizzicaroli' is great [...]. On this festivity the said shop keepers earn a real lot of money. [...] The day before Easter's Sunday, their shops are turned into temples and chapels; the grocers become architects, the foodstuff transforms into columns, cornices, capitals, tympana and any other architectural features. Hams and sausages and white dried bladders and lemons and laurel leaves, they all turn into a mosaic and make up a roof; parmesan cheese wheels, stacked one over the other, create veritable columns; [...] butter and ricotta are cast into whole statues [...] The entire little shop becomes a bright temple, shining with stars of gilded paper [...] and reflecting in the mirrors immense heaps of eggs. The Roman grocer does not put in place all that out of a mere crave for money [...]: the grocer, even those coming from Norcia and accustomed to Rome, feels in his heart a taste for architecture, and endures all this labour [...] with a view to please his customers with the vision of such a pomp, and also to rejoice himself of the sight».

[In the original Italian text: «I pizzicagnoli a Pasqua — La devozione dei pizzicagnoli, o come dicono a Roma, 'pizzicaroli' è grande [...]. sotto queste feste i detti industrianti fanno affari grassi, affari d'oro. [...] La vigilia di domenica di Pasqua le salsamenterie si trasformano in templi e cappelle; i pizzicagnoli in architetti, i commestibili in colonne, cornicioni, capitelli, timpani e ogni altra membratura architettonica. I prosciutti, le salsiccie, le bianche vesciche, i limoni, le foglie di lauro si convertono in mosaico e formano il soffitto; le forme di parmigiano e d'altri formaggi sovrapposte l'una all'altra si aggiustano in colonne; [...] con burro e ricotta si fondono delle statue intere [...]. Tutta la piccola bottega si converte in un chiaro tempio, scintillante con le stelle di carta dorata [...] riflettendo negli specchi gli sterminati mucchi d'ova. Il pizzicagnolo romano fa tutto questo non per il solo e puro amore del guadagno [...]: il pizzicagnolo, sia pure di Norcia, acclimatizzato in Roma, sente il gusto architettonico, e dura tutta questa fatica [...] per dilettere colla vista di quella pompa il suo pubblico, e per dilettersene egli stesso»].

I PIZZICAGNOLI A PASQUA

La devozione dei pizzicagnoli, o come dicono a Roma, *pizzicarioli*, è grande, profonda pel solenne anniversario dell'alto mistero della Redenzione umana.

Egli è indubitato, per altro, che *sotto queste feste* i detti industrianti fanno affari *grassi*, affari d'oro; e l'elemento dell'interesse ci entra per un coefficiente certo non piccolo nel loro fervore pasquale artistico.

In conseguenza, del sacro e del profano si fa il più stupendo miscuglio nelle pizzicherie di Roma la vigilia di domenica di Pasqua. Le salsamenterie si trasformano in templi e cappelle; i pizzicagnoli in architetti, i commestibili in colonne, cornicioni, capitelli, timpani ed ogni altra mem-

bratura architettonica. I prosciutti, le saliscie, le bianche vesciche, i limoni, le foglie di lauro si convertono in mosaico e formano il soffitto; le forme di parmigiano e d'altri formaggi sovrapposte l'una all'altra si agguistano in colonne; con le candele di sevo si fanno le frangie ad una cortina di mosaico, che ricopre le parti interne; con burro e ricotta si fondono delle statue intiere, dei gruppi storici di soggetti cristiani e biblici, che lo spettatore stupefatto è tentato a prendere per lavoro in alabastro. Tutta la piccola bottega si converte in un chiaro tempio, scintillante con le stelle di carta dorata, ed illuminato graziosamente con palloncini qua e là sospesi, e riflettendo negli specchi gli sterminati mucchi d'ova.

Il pizzicagnolo romano fa tutto questo non per il solo e puro amore del guadagno (deve rendersi questa giustizia), ma ben si accorge essere in questa reggia dell'arte trasportato anch'egli dal sentimento del bello: il pizzicagnolo, sia pure di Norcia, acclimatizzato in Roma, sente il gusto architettonico, e dura tutta questa fatica scupa due giornate di tempo, per diletta-

colla vista di quella pompa il suo pubblico, e per dilettersene egli stesso.

Il seme dei primitivi Quiriti non è morto nei nostri abitanti; la scintilla del genio di Roma non è spenta; le turbe dei forastieri non l'hanno potuto pervertire, esso è sempre *popolo* e non plebe anche nelle bisogne più ordinarie della vita.

Fig. 148 - 'Norcini' and 'Pizzicaroli' from Costantino Maes' *Curiosità romane* (Rome, 1885), p. 49-51

What a vision of happiness, celebration and popular joy in this short description, in which Maes, even though with his typical ironical touch, describes the beauty of food, and its abundance, and the connected art, as proposed by the Roman grocers, and the Roman 'Norcini', to their affectionate clients and to all passers-by! This is nineteenth-century Rome, with all its splendours and wonders (including hams and sausages, prepared by the skilled hands of the 'Norcini').

We have now got to the twentieth century, and at the very beginning of this period we find another significant testimony to the ceaseless presence of the 'Norcini' in Rome. We take it from *Croquis romains (Roman sketches)*, a book written in 1913 by Aventino, the nickname of Charles Belin, a French journalist enamoured of Rome and its fascinating ambiance:

«The grocer and his brother, the salter, would be nothing in this world without their relative, the 'norcino', who never disavowed his rural origin and comes to town only in winters. In the 'norcineria' [his shop, editor's note] he processes fresh pork meat. A number of strong hooks hold large quarters to be processed on a daily basis; thousands of pink sausages hang from the roof like garlands; as to hams, which are smoked in the back of the shop, they are legions; they cover walls and roof. The 'norcino' and his family, standing in front of a large, heavy wooden table, dismember, cut, slice and mince portions of meat, of which they will fill, in the form of porridge, the guts that a lad washes and readies in advance. When summer arrives again, he will go back to his mountains and villages. And the shop,

cleaned, whitewashed, refurbished, will accommodate its new shopkeepers, as usually happens: the traders of Florence's straw hats».

[In the original French text: «Le 'pizzicagnolo' et son frère le 'salsamentario' ne seraient rien dans ce monde sans le cousin, le 'norcino' qui n'a pas renié ses origines paysannes et qui ne vient à la ville que durant les mois d'hiver. Dans la 'norcineria', on travaille le porc frais. Des séries de crocs puissants retiennent de gros quartiers pour la consommation journalière; des milliers de saucisses toutes roses festonnent dans tous les sens; quant aux jambons, fumés dans l'arrière-boutique, ils sont légion; ils tapissent murs et plafond. Le 'norcino' et sa famille, debout devant une énorme table en bois massif, dépècent, découpent, hachent et pilent des blocs de viande dont vont s'emplier, sous forme de bouillie, les boyaux qu'un gamin lave et prépare. Quand reviendra l'été, on regagnera ses montagnes et ses villages. Le magasin, nettoyé, blanchi, remis à neuf, recevra ses nouveaux hôtes coutumiers: les marchands de chapeaux de paille de Florence»].

Le *pizzicagnolo* et son frère le *salsamentario* ne seraient rien dans ce monde sans le cousin, le *norcino* qui n'a pas renié ses origines paysannes et qui ne vient à la ville que durant les mois d'hiver. Dans la *norcineria*, on travaille le porc frais. Des séries de crocs puissants retiennent de gros quartiers pour la consommation journalière; des milliers de saucisses toutes roses festonnent dans tous les sens; quant aux jambons, fumés dans l'arrière-boutique, ils sont légion; ils tapissent murs et plafond. Le *norcino* et sa famille, debout devant une énorme table en bois massif, dépècent, découpent, hachent et pilent des blocs de viande dont vont s'emplier, sous forme de bouillie, les boyaux qu'un gamin lave et prépare.

Quand reviendra l'été, on regagnera ses montagnes et ses villages. Le magasin, nettoyé, blanchi, remis à neuf, recevra ses nouveaux hôtes coutumiers: les marchands de chapeaux de paille de Florence.

Fig. 149 - 'Norcini' and 'Pizzicaroli' from Charles Belin's *Croquis romains* (Paris, 1913), p. 117-118

Nothing seems to have changed since the late fifteenth century: the people of Norcia come and go, they settle in Rome for the winter season, with all

their amazing craft on salted pork meat, and with their toothsome products joyfully displayed on the roof and walls of their small shops; then, when the work is done, they go back home to Norcia, amid the imposing peaks of the Sibillini Mountain Range, leaving space to friends and colleagues from Florence (as we saw earlier, the Tuscan town was another historical destination for the migrating people of Norcia), who will provide the citizens of Rome with most useful summer products (straw hats). Then, the 'Norcini' will come again when the season is right. And they have been doing all of that for centuries.

But many 'Norcini' — as we saw, for instance, with their Archbrotherhood and Guild, hundreds of years earlier — lived, and still live, permanently in Rome, and had, and still have, their own shops in town: at the Pantheon, at Campo dei Fiori, and in many other places around downtown Rome.

As we will see in the final, concluding chapter.

8. The 'Norcini' in Rome: a heritage that still lives today

In the previous chapters, we have fully retraced the story of the presence of the 'Norcini' in Rome, starting from the fifteenth century onwards.

After briefly illustrating the history of salted pork meat from Roman times through the Middle Ages, we initially diverted our steps toward fourteenth-century Florence, in which we began to find a significant local community of 'Norcini'; and then we entered Rome while the capital city of the Papal State was experiencing a new age of development and wealth under Popes Martin V, Eugene IV, Nicholas V, Pius II. It is in the course of this period that people from Norcia began to move to Rome, both seasonally and permanently, in search of work and trade opportunities. They will give birth to the category of the 'Norcini': manual workers and peddlers, but also butchers and experts in the salting and seasoning of pork meat, and even skilled Precian surgeons and physicians.

With the first 'makers of sausages' in town, we faced the first quarrels with the established guilds of Butchers and Grocers; nonetheless, those soon began to favourably value the quality of the art of butchery and pork meat salting that those rustic newcomers from Norcia were bringing in town.

So the 'Norcini' could step into the regulated food market in Rome, first by working for the existing guilds' members, and subsequently winning for themselves their own business space out of the toothsome of their seasoned pork meat products, fully appreciated by both the populace and the most affluent members of the aristocracy and the Church.

Their successful presence in the city of the Popes included proficient surgeons and doctors from the area of Preci, many of them skilled, celebrated and rich (enormously rich in some cases, like Francesco Fusconi), and handymen of all sorts, the latter even humorously portrayed on theatrical stages: all of them were called 'Norcini', and their extraordinary success eventually brought, at the beginning of the seventeenth century, to the establishment of their own brotherhood, dedicated to their beloved patron saints, St. Benedict and St. Scholastica. Now the 'Nation of Norcia' in Rome, just like many other 'nations' which were present in town at the time, was fully and powerfully represented by a well-funded association, headed by a prominent lawyer at the Roman

Curia, Laerzio Cherubini, and set under the protection of eminent Cardinals of the Holy Roman Church. Their oratory, small but cozy, was set not far from the Pantheon, with an annexed 'hospital' for the accommodation of their fellow-citizens.

Subsequently, and with a remarkable delay, the 'Norcini', jointly with the 'Casciani', also established their own guild for the regulation of their trades and businesses; however, they had to face the strong opposition of the other guilds, which would not allow them to formally step into their exclusive trades, like pig's butchery, pork meat salting, sale of birds and other flying animals: the new guild had to restrain to selling game and truffles, even though the actual, established reality saw the 'Norcini' as the kings of salted pork meat in Rome, together with the Grocers, and with the Butchers not active anymore in the area of pig's slaughtering and butchery.

This situation will go on through the eighteenth, nineteenth, and twentieth centuries, and up to our present times. Actually, the presence of the Roman 'Norcini' will be so successful as to indelibly mark the local society in Rome for hundreds of years, especially with their specific penchant for pig's butchery and the processing of salted, seasoned pork meat.

Their shops, picturesquely adorned with festoons of sausages, ranks of hams and piles of cheese wheels, will inhabit for centuries the districts of downtown Rome, with a visible, specific presence in the area of the Pantheon, not far from their national oratory, Campo dei Fiori and other main squares in the centre of the city.

So now we want to conclude our incredible ride across the centuries with the astounding, wondrous, almost never-stopping presence of the 'Norcini' in the streets of today's Rome.

Yes, it is amazingly unbelievable: today, the 'Norcini' are still here, in the town of the Popes, after centuries and centuries of history through the age of the Papal States and beyond. And with a very same role.

They are the magicians of sausages, hams and salami. Even now, in the twenty-first century.

Fig. 150 - 'Norcinerie' in contemporary Rome

From Campo dei Fiori to Via Appia, from Via Merulana to Trastevere, the shops of the 'Norcini', still run by families originating from Norcia, are scattered throughout Rome, offering their palatable products to the modern citizens of the capital of Italy.

And there is more to it. Because the Archbrotherhood of St. Benedict and St. Scholastica is still in full existence, following various occurrences and predicaments, and still owns the small church and building lying at the intersection between Via di Torre Argentina and Vicolo Sinibaldi.

Out of the passionate, unremitting efforts of Monsignor Luigi Di Giannicola, born in the small hamlet of Valcaldara, lying in the Plains of St. Scholastica at Norcia, in the 1980s the national church of the 'Norcini' was restored and the Archbrotherhood reopened: now the association is one of the many ancient, established Roman brotherhoods which still inhabit the

central area of the town of the Popes and are set under the direction of the Bishopric of Rome, with a further, full listing in the Italian civil and administrative registries. With its four hundred years, and counting, of age the Archbrotherhood is still a source of cohesion and inspiration for all the people from Norcia who lives in present-day Rome, keeping its strong connection with the land of origin that lies at the foot of the Sibillini Mountain Range.

It seems almost incredible, yet everything is still in place today, in our contemporary world: the relationship between Norcia and Rome, the palatable craft of the 'Norcini', their Archbrotherhood, their shops.

And one of the most illustrious shops, a beautiful 'norcineria', is located right in front of the Pantheon, at the Piazza della Rotonda, just two hundred meters from the little Church of St. Benedict and St. Scholastica, the oratory of the Archbrotherhood of the Roman 'Norcini': at the very center of the ancient life of the people from Norcia in Rome, still a 'norcineria' opens its doors, the whole building belonging to the community of Agriano, one of the small hamlets that surround the hometown of St. Benedict, and it is managed by a family which bears one of the typical surnames of the native territory of the 'Norcini'.

Fig. 151 - The 'norcineria' at Piazza della Rotonda in Rome (the edge of the Pantheon's rounded dome is on the left of the image)

Right from here, from the Pantheon's square, its 'Norcini' and its shops we will start our next paper belonging to the present series *The Norcia Historical Papers*: it will be dedicated to an ancient criminal case occurred in a shop set at this very square, before the illustrious columns of the Pantheons. A criminal case which occurred in the second quarter of the seventeenth century and involved the 'Norcini', at the time an appreciated presence in Rome and fully recognizable as known characters animating the ordinary, everyday life of the capital of the Papal States.

And we like to conclude the present monographic paper, fully dedicated to the 'Norcini' as butchers in Rome, with this last picture: the «Antica Bottega di Norcia» («The Ancient Shop of Norcia»), whose name resounds today in the immediate vicinity of Piazza Navona, a few meters only from the palace which hosts the Senate of the Italian Republic.

Fig. 152 - The «Antica Bottega di Norcia» at the intersection between Corso del Rinascimento and Via S. Giovanna d'Arco in Rome, a few steps from the Italian Senate (outside the picture to the right)

Norcia is still here today. In Rome. And, after more than six centuries of established history, its high-quality, most-excellent salted pork meat products still provide delicious taste — and sheer happiness — to all Romans.

Michele Sanvico